

HEALTH AND ENVIRONMENT

**Research and Advances from
the 1st International Meeting of
Biological and Health Sciences.**

**Vítor Sampaio Minassa
Juliana Barbosa Coitinho
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**Universidade Federal
do Espírito Santo**

Health and Environment:

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Biological and Health Sciences.

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E-BOOK PRESENTATION

This e-book brings together the abstracts of the studies presented at the 1st International Meeting of Biological and Health Sciences, offering a representative overview of the scientific discussions promoted during the event. By organizing and making this body of research available, the publication seeks to document the diversity of themes, methodological approaches, and theoretical perspectives that characterized the meeting, thereby contributing to the dissemination and visibility of the knowledge produced.

This initiative also responds to the goal of building and preserving the event's historical record, strengthening its academic identity and projecting its future editions. By systematizing the presented works, this volume becomes a documentary milestone that highlights the growth, consolidation, and reach of the scientific collaboration networks fostered through the meeting.

Finally, the e-book aims to encourage the continuity of and dialogue among the studies developed from the advances and discussions that emerged in the mini-talks, oral presentations, and posters, organized within the event's seven thematic axes. It is expected that this material will inspire new investigations, expand partnerships, and contribute to the strengthening of the fields involved.

The Editors.

IBHS Mini Talks: **Health and** **Environment by** **Young Minds**

MINI-TALK 1: WATER STRESS, DROUGHTS AND CLIMATE CHANGE: A DIGITAL GUIDE ON HEALTH IMPACTS

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Introduction: *Water stress, characterized by insufficient water to meet human, agricultural, and environmental needs, has intensified due to climate change, which alters rainfall patterns, increases average temperatures, and enhances evaporation, thereby reducing water availability in soils, rivers, and aquifers. According to reports from the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), global warming of 1.5°C to 3°C could expose hundreds of millions of people to extreme drought conditions by 2050, increasing social and health vulnerabilities. This scenario not only favors the occurrence of prolonged droughts, but also compromises water and food security, affecting public health through malnutrition, a higher incidence of waterborne diseases, increased heat stress, and worsening respiratory diseases. Vulnerable populations, particularly those in arid regions, with low income, or dependent on subsistence agriculture, are among the most affected, highlighting the close relationship between climate change and health inequalities. In this context, an informative digital guide was created to help the population understand the issue, promoting awareness of the impacts of drought and water stress on human, animal, and environmental health, as well as possible mitigation measures, such as sustainable food production, forest management, soil carbon conservation, reduction of deforestation and food waste, and adaptation strategies, including rainwater harvesting, restoration of degraded soils, and investment in green infrastructure.* **Materials and Methods:** The information for the development of the educational resource came from bibliographic research in databases such as PubMed and SciELO, with analysis of articles that explored the relationship between drought, water stress, climate change, and their impacts on human health. IPCC reports were used as the main reference for the preparation of the guide. Based on the collected content, a script was prepared containing the main information on the topic addressed. All materials were created using Canva software, using images and other visual elements, with the aim of making the content attractive for the public. **Results:** Based on the information obtained, three formats of educational guide were produced: (i) a 5-minute video, intended to provide a broader and more detailed explanation of the topic; (ii) a 1-minute video, with a summarized approach, designed for quick and accessible dissemination of the content; and (iii) a sequence of 10 informative cards, covering key information about drought, water stress, and their impacts on health. **Conclusion:** The material developed has significant educational, informational, and scientific dissemination potential, contributing to the public's understanding of the risks associated with climate change. Moreover, it contributes to social awareness and strengthens consciousness about the ongoing need for preventive and adaptive measures to protect human, animal, and environmental health in times of climate change.

Keywords: Climate change. Droughts. Health. Water stress.

MINI-TALK 2: LABORATORY OF SCIENTISTS: INTEGRATING RESEARCH INTO EDUCATION

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Introduction: Science and technology are two of the pillars that hold modern society, however, they are often perceived as distant or inaccessible, reinforcing disinformation and social inequalities. Therefore, promoting scientific knowledge in education is essential for students to understand the scientific method, develop critical thinking and recognize science's role in social transformation. In the project "*Laboratory of Scientists 2.0: analysis of the biotechnological potential of the school community through the scientific literacy of young researchers*", the students from elementary school (ninth grade) assess the biotechnological potential of microbiota from their school environments and its surroundings, so that scientific awakening begins from the reality in which they are inserted, promoting scientific literacy and environmental education, in addition to fostering the desire to assess higher education. **Objectives:** The project's primary objective is to promote scientific literacy among elementary students through research practices. It seeks to develop an understanding of the scientific method, stimulate academic skills and foster school-university integration. Specifically, it aims to evaluate the biotechnological potential of microorganisms isolated from the school environment by investigating enzymatic activities of scientific and industrial interest. Concurrently, it empowers students to become critical, autonomous, and socially engaged citizens. **Methodology:** The project takes a pedagogical approach focused on scientific education, articulating formative activities, experimentation and dissemination of knowledge. Initial theoretical meetings cover core themes, fundamentals, methodology, reliable sources and academic writing. Subsequently, the students visit university laboratories to observe scientific practice in different contexts, encouraging pursuit of higher education. Following, students are trained in biosafety and microbiological handling for collecting environmental samples. In the laboratory, the samples are inoculated onto a nutrient medium for growth and subsequent analysis for amylolytic, proteolytic, lipolytic, and cellulolytic activities. **Results:** Through participation in all stages of research, from theoretical to practical execution, students will learn to interpret results and apply them to problem-solving, thereby solidifying their scientific literacy. Regarding the mini-project, the identification of microorganisms producers of enzymes of industrial interest, contributing to the valorization of local biodiversity and environmental education. More importantly, these activities are designed to provide an enriching experience that

encourages the students to express their ideas with confidence and familiarizes them with academic environments, expanding their future professional opportunities. **Conclusion:** The project contributes to the development of scientifically literate individuals capable of interpreting scientific information and applying this knowledge to their social context. By integrating teaching, research, and outreach, it not only fosters students' connection to the university but also promotes the appreciation of scientific knowledge as a tool for transforming reality. Thus, the initiative reinforces the importance of critical and inclusive science education, consolidating its position as a strategy for human and social development.

Keywords: Scientific literacy; Biotechnology; Microorganisms; Social transformation.

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MINI-TALK 3: INCLUSIVE DERMATOLOGY: PERSONALIZED SUNSCREENS FOR DARK SKIN AS A PATHWAY TO HEALTH EQUITY

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Introduction: The use of sunscreen to prevent skin cancer and other diseases associated with sun exposure is recommended for all skin tones. Despite this, there is a shortage of aesthetically suitable sunscreens for Black skin. The whitish appearance left by tinted photoprotective formulations and the limited availability of shades tailored to darker skin tones represent the main barriers encountered by Black consumers in selecting appropriate dermal photoprotection. The lack of options that serve this population, exacerbated by the misconception that individuals with darker skin phototypes do not require photoprotection, results in low adherence to sunscreen use among this population. These factors contribute to the higher prevalence of aggressive skin cancer and high mortality rates in this group compared to White people, creating a public health problem. In this context, this study aimed to develop customized tinted sunscreens for Black individuals, including those of Black and Brown descent, and to assess the suitability of these products on the patient's skin. **Methods:** Six volunteers participated in this study (CAAE 7.095.964). Facial photographs were collected and analyzed using the softwares Ibis Paint X[®] (13.1.1 version), GNU Image Manipulation Program[®] (3.0.4 version) and Trycolors[®] (2025 version) to accurately determine skin tone and calculate the proportions of primary pigments (yellow, red, blue, black, and white) required for formulating personalized sunscreens. Based on this analysis, personalized sunscreens were developed for each participant. After applying the products, new photographs were taken, and the volunteers completed a questionnaire that assessed the suitability of the sunscreen color for their individual skin tone, as well as aspects related to the effect on the skin, spreadability, and sensory characteristics of the product. **Results:** Four patients reported satisfaction with the customized sunscreen, and two reported being dissatisfied, particularly due to a mismatch between the product's shade or undertone and their skin tone. Ocular irritation was reported by two patients following application of the tinted sunscreen, an adverse event not observed with the non-tinted formulation. The amount of sunscreen applied directly influenced both sensory perception and the product's shade match. Therefore, it is essential to consider clinical efficacy alongside patient satisfaction when developing customized formulations. **Conclusion:** Customizing sunscreens is a challenging task due to the complexity of human skin, individual subjectivity, and the difficulties associated with accurately defining skin tone and undertone from images,

which directly impacts the appropriate selection of pigment ratios in the formulation. Despite limitations, such as the small number of volunteers and the subjective assessment of color suitability, expanding the diversity of tinted photoprotective formulations is essential to ensure inclusive and effective sun protection for the Black population.

Key-words: photoprotection, skin cancer, customized products.

Funding: Supported by Federal University of Espírito Santo scientific initiation scholarship (UFES, Brazil)

MINI-TALK 4: INFLUENCE OF BIOLOGICAL SEX ON CORONARY ENDOTHELIAL FUNCTION IN DIABETIC RATS

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Introduction: Diabetes Mellitus (DM) is a metabolic disease characterized by persistent hyperglycemia, frequently associated with endothelial dysfunction and increased cardiovascular risk. Furthermore, studies indicate that sex differences may influence vascular function, leading to distinct management strategies and complications in DM, since sex hormones, such as estrogen and testosterone, directly modulate nitric oxide bioavailability, vascular tone, and endothelial responses. Considering the impact of these differences on health equity, we hypothesized that diabetic rats present distinct alterations in coronary vascular bed endothelial-dependent relaxation compared to non-diabetic rats, with possible variations between males and females. The aim of this study was to investigate the effect of DM on endothelium-dependent coronary relaxation, analyzing potential sex differences in this response. **Materials and Methods:** Wistar rats of both sexes (8–9 weeks; CEUA-UFES no. 12/2024) were divided into four groups: diabetic and non-diabetic females (F-DM and F-C) and males (M-DM and M-C). DM was induced by a single dose of alloxan (150 mg/kg, i.p.). After 30 days, hearts were perfused using the Langendorff system. Vasodilation was evaluated by the response to bradykinin (0.1–1000 nM), before and after inhibition of nitric oxide synthase (NOS) with L-NAME (100 µM). Data were expressed as mean ± standard error of the mean and analyzed by two-way ANOVA followed by Sidak's *post hoc* test ($P < 0.05$). **Results:** Baseline coronary perfusion pressure (CPP) was higher in females, regardless of the presence of DM or NOS inhibition (F-C: 90 ± 6 ; F-DM: 89 ± 3 ; M-C: 55 ± 2 ; M-DM: 64 ± 6 mmHg). Bradykinin promoted similar vasodilation among groups; however, NO pathway inhibition reduced the response only in diabetic females. In addition, uterine atrophy was observed (F-C: 0.009 ± 0.003 ; F-DM: 0.005 ± 0.001 mg/g), as well as alterations in the estrous cycle, with longer duration in the metestrus phase (F-C: 1.755 ± 0.3288 ; F-DM: 3.222 ± 0.1422 dias) and reduced time in the proestrus phase (F-C: 1.000 ± 0.1470 ; F-DM: 0.1611 ± 0.07222 dias). **Conclusion:** The findings demonstrate that DM affects males and females differently, with females showing greater dependence on the NO pathway for coronary vasodilation. These results contribute to the understanding of cardiovascular alterations associated with DM and highlight the importance of considering sex as a biological variable.

Keywords: Diabetes Mellitus. Endothelial dysfunction. Coronary circulation. Sex differences. Nitric oxide.

Funding: Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa e Inovação do Espírito Santo (Fapes).

MINI-TALK 5: IN SILICO INVESTIGATION OF THE BIOAVAILABILITY, TOXICITY AND MOLECULAR MECHANISMS OF THE ANTI-HELICOBACTER PYLORI ACTIVITY OF COMPOUNDS OBTAINED FROM AVOCADO SEEDS

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Introduction: *Helicobacter pylori* infection is a global public health problem, associated with gastritis, ulcers, and even gastric cancer. Conventional treatment of the infection, based on antibiotics and proton pump inhibitors, has limitations due to bacterial resistance and adverse effects, reinforcing the need for new therapeutic alternatives. In this context, *Persea americana* (avocado) seeds contain secondary metabolites with antimicrobial properties. The objective of this study was to investigate, using *in silico* approaches, the molecular mechanisms of the anti-*H. pylori* activity of these compounds, testing the possibility of interactions between these molecules and the bacteria's target proteins, evaluating their potential as drug candidates. **Methods:** An *in silico* study was performed, including analysis of physicochemical, pharmacokinetic, and toxicity properties (SwissADME and ProTox 3.0), prediction of biological activity spectrum (PASS), structural similarity with conventional antibiotics (Tanimoto coefficient), and molecular docking studies (AutoDock Vina). The selected target proteins were related to critical processes of *H. pylori* pathogenicity, such as motility (FliS and FliM), DNA replication (DnaB and β -clamp), chemotaxis (CheY), and nitrogen metabolism (glutamine synthetase - GS - and UreE). Binding energies and molecular interactions were analyzed, in addition to validation by redocking. **Results:** The evaluated compounds conformed to Lipinski's rule and had good oral bioavailability, with emphasis on malic (56%), quinic (56%), oleic (85%), and palmitic (85%) acids. Toxicological analysis classified most compounds in classes 5 and 6, indicating low relative toxicity, with a predominance of nephrotoxic effects. The predicted spectrum of activity revealed potential for mucosal protection, anti-infective, and anticarcinogenic action, with relevant values for fatty and phenolic acids. In molecular docking, the best performances were observed for chlorogenic acid, which presented binding energies of up to -8.6 kcal/mol with glutamine synthetase and -7.8 kcal/mol with the FliM protein, indicating strong affinity. Other promising compounds including malic acid, quinic acid and perseitol had significant interactions with enzymes such as glutamine synthetase, tRNA nucleotidyltransferase, and pseudouridylate synthase. The molecular interactions demonstrated recurrent contact with critical residues in the active sites of the target proteins, with a low number of steric clashes, suggesting good conformational complementarity. For example, the chlorogenic acid formed more diverse molecular interactions compared to the other metabolites. It had strong interactions with GS at polar residues (GLU223, HIS279, ARG349, GLU230), and with DnaB, it had several van der Waals and pi-alkyl interactions, favoring the molecule's accommodation in the enzyme's hydrophobic pocket. Redocking validated the protocol,

demonstrating that avocado seed compounds can exhibit superior affinity even to cocrystallized ligands, especially in the CheY protein. **Conclusion:** The results showed that compounds from *Persea americana* seeds exhibit favorable pharmacokinetic profiles, low relative toxicity, and high affinity for essential *H. pylori* proteins. Notable among these are chlorogenic acid, malic acid, quinic acid, and perseitol, which demonstrated multiple potential mechanisms of bacterial inhibition. These findings suggest that these metabolites may contribute to the development of novel pharmacological approaches against *H. pylori*. Further studies *in vitro* and *in vivo* are required to confirm therapeutic efficacy and explore their future clinical applications.

Keywords: *Helicobacter pylori*. avocado. *in silico* evaluation.

Funding: Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa e Inovação do Espírito Santo (Fapes) and UFES

ORAL PRESENTATIONS

**Symposium – Integrating Physiology, Toxicology and Therapeutics in
Cardiorespiratory disease**

**METABOLIC SYNDROME RISK FACTORS IN FIREFIGHTERS: A
CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY**

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Introduction: Firefighters are exposed to multiple occupational risks coming from emergency operations and routine professional activities. In this context, cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) stand out as the leading cause of death among this population, aggravated by the combination of intense physical effort, acute stress, and pre-existing metabolic factors. Studies report a high prevalence of overweight, obesity, and metabolic syndrome among these professionals, posing a significant risk for morbidity and mortality. The present study aimed to assess the prevalence of metabolic syndrome among military firefighters and to identify its association with sociodemographic, occupational, lifestyle, and family history factors. **Methods:** This is a cross-sectional study based on secondary data analysis from the institutional program “Bom Estar” (Well-Being), carried out in 2024 by the Military Fire Department of Espírito Santo (CBMES). The study was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the Health Sciences Center, Federal University of Espírito Santo (CAAE 78629724.5.0000.5060/2024). Data collection included three components: (1) anthropometric and hemodynamic evaluation (weight, height, waist circumference, blood pressure); (2) a structured electronic questionnaire addressing socioeconomic, occupational, health, and lifestyle information; and (3) biochemical indicators, including glucose and lipid profile (HDL and triglycerides). Metabolic syndrome was defined according to NCEP-ATP III criteria. Data were organized in spreadsheets and analyzed using SPSS® version 25.0. **Results:** A total of 1,039 firefighters were evaluated, predominantly male (85.8%) and aged 30–49 years (69.4%). Obesity prevalence was 12.6%, and 49.7% reported a family history of hypertension. Regarding metabolic syndrome components, the most frequent were elevated blood pressure (29.6%), reduced HDL (17.3%), altered glucose (13.3%), elevated triglycerides (12.2%), and increased waist circumference (9.1%). Overall, 6.7% of participants presented three or more risk factors, characterizing them as having metabolic syndrome, while 46.1% presented one or two isolated risk factors. In multivariate analysis, the presence of three or more risk factors was significantly associated with obesity (OR=46.05; 95%CI: 20.75–102.23; p<0.001), male sex (OR=7.99; 95%CI: 2.06–31.05; p=0.003), age ≥50 years (OR=7.71; 95%CI: 2.08–28.54; p=0.002), sedentary lifestyle (OR=3.03; 95%CI: 1.53–5.99; p=0.002), and family history of hypertension (OR=2.15; 95%CI: 1.16–3.99; p=0.015). **Conclusion:** Obesity, male sex, older age, sedentary behavior, and family history of hypertension were determinants for the presence of metabolic syndrome among firefighters. These findings highlight the need

for preventive strategies focused on weight control, promotion of regular physical activity, and continuous monitoring of cardiovascular risk factors in this population.

Keywords: Firefighters; Occupational Health; Cardiovascular Risk Factors; Metabolic Syndrome; Biomarkers.

Funding: No funding was received for this study, except for KNS scholarship (CNPq/FAPES; Grant No. 2025-H5S1W).

Symposium – Integrating Physiology, Toxicology and Therapeutics in Cardiorespiratory disease

INVOLVEMENT OF COX-DERIVED PRODUCTS AND INFLAMMATION ON THE IRON OVERLOAD VASCULOPATHY

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Introduction: Iron is an essential element for the human body; however, its excess is toxic for multiple organs, including to the cardiovascular system. Recent evidence suggests an iron overload vasculopathy characterized by vascular remodeling, increased vasoconstriction and atherosclerosis, due to oxidative stress. However, the arachidonic acid/cyclooxygenase (AA–COX) pathway, which is highly involved in inflammation, oxidative stress, and endothelial dysfunction in several conditions, has not yet been investigated in the vasculopathy induced by iron overload. Therefore, this study aimed to test the hypothesis that the vascular AA–COX pathway and inflammatory state are upregulated in chronic iron overload and may contribute to dysfunction. **Methods:** Male Wistar rats, 8 weeks old (~200 g), were assigned into two groups: control (Ct) and iron (Fe). Iron-dextran was administered via i.p. injections (100 mg/kg/day, 5 times/week for 4 weeks), while Ct received 0.9% NaCl. After 4 weeks, animals were euthanized by exsanguination under general anesthesia. Blood was collected for iron and C-reactive protein analysis; thoracic aortas were isolated for in vitro reactivity studies, prostanoid releasing, scanning electron microscopy, gene expression, and inflammatory cytokine assays. Data were analyzed using unpaired Student's t-test, two-way ANOVA with Bonferroni post-hoc, and differences of area under concentration-response curves (dAUC). Statistical significance was set at $P < 0.05$. The protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee on Animal Use (CEUA-UFES, #18/2023). **Results:** Rats from the Fe group exhibited elevated serum ferritin (Ct: 161 ± 9 vs Fe: 424 ± 24 $\mu\text{g/dL}$), while C-reactive protein levels remained unchanged. Vasoconstriction to phenylephrine was enhanced in Fe aortas (R_{max} Ct: 75 ± 8 vs Fe: 120 ± 4), but it was inhibited by the incubation with COX inhibitor indomethacin (10 μM) (dAUC Ct: 0.55 ± 19 vs Fe: -76.56 ± 18). Also, EP₁ receptor antagonist SC-19220 (10 μM) (dAUC Ct: 33.43 ± 16 vs Fe: -35.91 ± 16) and selective COX-2 inhibitor NS-398 (1 μM) (dAUC Ct: 294.82 ± 17 vs Fe: -39.5 ± 22) reduced contractile responses only in the Fe group, whereas TP receptor antagonist SQ-29548 (1 μM) had no effect. Conversely, the IP receptor antagonism with CAY-10441 (100 nM) increased contractile responses in Ct (dAUC: 85.02 ± 11), but not in Fe aortas. Scanning electron microscopy revealed disrupted endothelial cell confluence associated with greater iron deposition in the Fe group. Moreover, prostaglandin I₂ release was increased by the Fe aortas (Ct: 87.18 ± 19 vs Fe: 413.68 ± 101 ng/mL/mg), whereas prostaglandin E₂ remained unchanged. Finally, macrophage activity (Ct: 0.003 ± 0.0004 vs Fe: 0.005 ± 0.0004 OD/mg) and gene expression of M1 phenotype activation markers CD86 (Ct: 1 ± 0.26 vs Fe: 2.59 ± 0.59) and F4/80 (Ct: 1 ± 0.16 vs Fe: 1.37 ± 0.12) were

elevated in Fe aortas. **Conclusion:** The vascular AA–COX pathway contributes to iron overload vasoconstrictor hyper-reactivity, involving increased COX-2 and EP₁ receptor activation, and impaired IP receptor counteraction. These are associated with inflammatory responses characterized by macrophage activation, increased prostanoid release, and endothelial structural injury.

Keywords: iron overload; COX; arteries; inflammation; prostanoids.

Funding: CAPES; FAPES; CNPq

**Symposium – Integrating Physiology, Toxicology and Therapeutics in
Cardiorespiratory disease**

**SPONTANEOUSLY HYPERTENSIVE RATS HAVE GREATER
ATRIAL BUT NOT VENTRICULAR CHOLINESTERASE
ACTIVITY COMPARED TO NORMOTENSIVE ANIMALS**

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Introduction: Hypertension (HT) is a chronic and multifactorial disease that affects approximately 33% of global population. Evidence from literature suggests that its development is associated with genetics and environmental factors, including dietary habits and sedentary lifestyle. One of the mechanisms involved in the pathophysiology of HT is an imbalance in the cholinergic system, which directly participates in cardiovascular modulation through the autonomic nervous system (ANS) and the non-neuronal cholinergic system (NNCS) of cardiovascular system. Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) catalyzes the rapid hydrolysis of acetylcholine (ACh) through a specific binding site, whereas butyrylcholinesterase (BChE) exhibits broader substrate specificity due to its larger binding site. Although the precise physiological role of BChE remains unclear, evidence supports its involvement in lipid metabolism and the NNCS. Preclinical studies have shown that spontaneously hypertensive rats (SHR) have reduced intrinsic plasma BChE activity compared to normotensive animals. Based on these findings, we hypothesize that SHR present an imbalance in organs involved in blood pressure modulation, which may contribute to the development of HT. **Materials and Methods:** SHR (N = 11) and normotensive rats Wistar (N = 10) and Wistar-Kyoto (N = 10) were used (CEUA Approval Numbers 17/2022 and 05/2023). Animals were euthanized by decapitation, and plasma, atrial, and right ventricle samples were collected. Plasma was aliquoted, and the cardiac tissues were homogenized. Plasma samples were analyzed for BChE activity, while cardiac homogenates were used to assess AChE and BChE activity using Ellman's method and Ellman's method modified by Perin and collaborators, respectively. For statistical analysis, we used a one-pathway ANOVA followed by post-hoc of Tukey for cholinesterases activity between strains and a two-pathway ANOVA for AChE and BChE activity at the same tissue. **Results:** SHR showed lower plasma BChE activity compared to normotensive strains. In the atria, SHR showed lower intrinsic AChE and BChE activity compared to Wistar-Kyoto (WKY) rats, but not when compared to Wistar rats. In the right ventricle, AChE and BChE activities showed no statistically differences between the strains; however, SHR tended to have lower BChE activity

compared to Wistar rats. Notably, AChE activity was higher in atrial tissue, whereas BChE activity predominated in the right ventricle. **Conclusion:** This study demonstrated that SHR exhibit alterations in AChE and BChE activity in cardiac structures and plasma when normotensive strains (Wistar and WKY). These findings suggest that the cholinesterase system is altered in HT and may participate in the pathophysiology of disease development. Consequently, these results pave the way for future investigations of the cholinesterase system in other organs involved in cardiovascular modulation to contribute to elucidate its role in the pathophysiology of HT and exploring its potential as a therapeutic target.

Keywords: Hypertension; Cholinesterases; Spontaneously Hypertensive Rats; Cardiovascular system.

Financial support: Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa e Inovação do Espírito Santo (FAPES, Grant Codes: 2022- 78KWB; 749/2024), CNPq/FAPES 2025-H5S1W; CNPq/MCTI/FNDCT N° 44/2024. LJC and VSM were supported by CAPES scholarships (Grant codes 01). VFC was a recipiente of UFES scholarship (PIBIC UFES. KBS was a recipiente of FAPES scholarship. BGF was a recipiente of FAPES scholarship.

**Symposium – Integrating Physiology, Toxicology and Therapeutics in
Cardiorespiratory disease**

**SINGLE EXPOSURE TO TRIBUTYLTIN INCREASES ROS
PRODUCTION AND INDUCES ENDOTHELIAL DYSFUNCTION**

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Introduction: Organotin, particularly tributyltin (TBT), are environmental contaminants with cytotoxic properties. In animal models, chronic TBT exposure induces vascular dysfunction via excessive reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation. **Objective:** To determine whether a single TBT exposure is sufficient to impair vascular function. **Hypothesis:** A single exposure to TBT is sufficient to induce endothelial dysfunction. **Methods:** Female Wistar rats (240–260 g, 3 months old) were divided into control (CT, n=29) and TBT-exposed (n=27) groups. Vascular reactivity of isolated aortic rings was assessed 24 h after a single oral dose of TBT (500 ng/kg). Aortic rings were mounted in Krebs solution and subjected to concentration–response curves using the vasoconstrictor phenylephrine (PE), while vasodilatory responses were evaluated by relaxation induced by acetylcholine and sodium nitroprusside. Nitric oxide (NO) and ROS production were quantified by fluorescence intensity of 4,5-Diaminofluorescein diacetate (DAF-2) and dihydroethidium (DHE) oxidation, respectively. Data are presented as mean \pm SEM and analyzed using two-way ANOVA followed by Fisher's test and paired or unpaired t-tests, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$. Study approved by CEUA/UFES (n^o 027/2016). **Results:** TBT exposure did not alter relaxation induced by acetylcholine (Rmax: TBT 100 ± 1.93 vs. CT $102 \pm 2.46\%$) or sodium nitroprusside (Rmax: TBT 102 ± 2.02 vs. CT $104 \pm 1.73\%$). However, the TBT group showed a significantly enhanced contractile response to phenylephrine (Rmax: TBT $118 \pm 2.29^*$ vs. CT $98 \pm 1.95\%$, $*p = 0.001$), as well as impaired endothelial (dAUC: TBT $268 \pm 53^*$ vs. CT $447 \pm 61\%$, $*p = 0.04$) and nitregic (dAUC: TBT $63 \pm 8^*$ vs. CT $284 \pm 18\%$, $*p = 0.0001$) modulation following endothelial removal and incubation with L-NAME (100 μ M), respectively. Interestingly, *in vitro* treatment with the superoxide scavenger SOD (300 U/mL) prior to L-NAME incubation prevented the TBT-induced loss of nitregic modulation (dAUC: TBT 228 ± 18 vs. CT $248 \pm 17\%$). Tiron (1 mM), catalase (1000 U/mL), and allopurinol (100 μ M) reduced vascular reactivity only in the TBT group, whereas the non-selective NOX inhibitor VAS-2870 (10 μ M) had no effect. Moreover, TBT reduced *in situ* aortic NO production (a.u.: TBT $33 \pm 4^*$ vs. CT 47 ± 3 , $*p = 0.02$) and increased ROS levels (a.u.: TBT $38 \pm 1^*$ vs. CT 26 ± 2 , $p = 0.01$). **Conclusion:** A single dose of TBT (500 ng/kg) induces vascular dysfunction, which appears to result from impaired endothelial and nitregic modulation, likely mediated by increased ROS production derived from xanthine oxidase.

Keywords: Tributyltin, vascular reactivity, aorta, ROS, environmental contaminant.

Financial support: CNPq, CAPES e FAPES.

Symposium – Drugs and Exposures: Xenobiotics and Health Effects

EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTS OF BERBERINE AND LIRAGLUTIDE ON ETHANOL CONSUMPTION AND PREFERENCE IN THE TWO-BOTTLE CHOICE MODEL

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Introduction: Alcohol is the most widely consumed psychoactive substance in the world and, despite its broad social acceptance, it is strongly associated with the risk of developing Alcohol Use Disorder (AUD), a condition within the spectrum of Substance Use Disorders. However, the therapeutic arsenal available for the treatment of AUD is limited in terms of availability, efficacy, adherence, and tolerability, highlighting the need for new therapeutic approaches. A promising strategy to accelerate the discovery of new treatments is drug repurposing, which consists of identifying new therapeutic indications for medications already approved and used in other clinical conditions. In this context, drugs such as liraglutide and berberine stand out, as they possess several pharmacological properties already described in the literature and are currently used in the treatment of diabetes and obesity. Furthermore, preclinical evidence demonstrates the ability of these drugs to reduce key behaviors associated with drug-seeking and compulsive use.

Material and methods: 36 adult C57BL/6 mice were used in the non-operant self-administration Two-Bottle Choice model. For nine weeks, animals were exposed for 24 hours on alternate days (Mondays, Wednesdays, and Fridays) to two bottles: one containing ethanol and the other water, with consumption recorded on the following days (Tuesdays, Thursdays, and Saturdays). In the tenth week, animals were divided into control and treatment groups, receiving injections of saline or liraglutide 0.1 mg/kg immediately before individual housing (one-week period). After the treatment week, animals were re-exposed to the paradigm for an additional two weeks without drug administration before the introduction of the next treatment with berberine 2.5 mg/kg. (CEUA/UFES 20/2024). **Results:** *Liraglutide treatment* – the intragroup analysis of ethanol consumption, corrected for body weight, showed that liraglutide significantly reduced consumption ($p < 0.0001$; $t = 4.987$; $df = 36$). Similarly, a significant reduction in ethanol preference was also observed ($p = 0.0006$; $t = 3.792$; $df = 36$). Consistently, the intergroup data demonstrated that animals in the liraglutide-treated group exhibited lower consumption compared to the control group ($p < 0.0001$; $t = 4.328$; $df = 34$). In addition, ethanol preference was also significantly reduced in the treated group compared to controls ($p = 0.0002$; $t = 4.208$; $df = 34$). *Berberine treatment* – the intragroup analysis showed that berberine treatment significantly reduced ethanol consumption ($p = 0.0245$; $t = 2.347$; $df = 36$), although it did not alter preference ($p = 0.6954$; $t = 0.3947$; $df = 36$). In contrast, the intergroup analysis revealed no statistically significant differences between the treated and control groups, either in ethanol consumption ($p = 0.1585$; $t = 1.442$; $df = 34$) or in preference ($p = 0.4209$; $t = 0.8148$; $df = 34$). **Conclusion:** Taken together, these findings

indicate that liraglutide consistently reduced both ethanol consumption and preference, with significant effects observed in both intra- and intergroup analyses. In contrast, although berberine produced a significant intragroup reduction in ethanol consumption, this effect was not accompanied by changes in preference and was not confirmed in the intergroup comparison. These results suggest that liraglutide exerts a more robust and consistent impact on ethanol-related behaviors compared to berberine.

Keywords: liraglutide; berberine; alcohol use disorder; two-bottle choice.

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Symposium – Drugs and Exposures: Xenobiotics and Health Effects

***IN SILICO* EVALUATION OF THE ENDOCRINE-DISRUPTING POTENTIAL OF SUNSCREENS AGAINST THE HUMAN ANDROGEN RECEPTOR**

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Introduction

The use of sunscreen is essential to reduce the harmful effects of ultraviolet (UV) radiation on the skin, preventing burns, photoenvelope and skin cancer. However, the UV filters present in the formulations may present inappropriate destinations for application, such as skin permeation and bioaccumulation in biological tissues, generating potential risks to human health and environmental impacts. Despite the wide use of these compounds, the information available on the possible effects of endocrine deregulation is still limited, evidencing the need for studies that investigate, at the molecular level, the mechanisms of recognition and interaction between these molecules and hormone receptors. **Methods** The research was entirely based on *in silico* studies, employing computational chemistry tools such as molecular docking (AutoDock Vina program) and molecular dynamics simulations (GROMACS 4.6.5 program). **Results** A computational screening of commercially available synthetic UV filters was conducted against 19 crystal structures of 14 nuclear receptors (NRs) to predict endocrine-disrupting (ED) potential. The results indicated an ED profile in classes of synthetic filters, such as benzophenone and camphor derivatives. Among the receptors analyzed, the Androgen Receptor (AR) stood out, showing interaction with all molecules. Camphor derivatives (4-MBC and 3-BC) exhibited a high probability of interaction, broadening the spectrum of targets, including estrogen receptors. In contrast, benzophenone derivatives showed intermediate probability across several NRs, such as AR, Progesterone Receptor (PR), and thyroid receptors. Most cinnamate derivatives, however, demonstrated low probability of interaction. Due to its interaction profile and concerns about the risk of prostatic hyperplasia and cancer, the AR was selected for detailed studies. Molecular docking assays evaluated the interaction energies, and the results showed that camphor derivatives (3-BC: -9.4 kcal/mol; 4-MBC: -9.5 kcal/mol) and benzophenones (BZF-8: -8.9 kcal/mol; BZF-3: -8.5 kcal/mol) exhibited energies close to that of the endocrine disruptor Bisphenol A (BPA: -8.3 kcal/mol), while Testosterone displayed higher affinity. The detailed interactions at the AR AF-2 active site revealed binding modes similar to the AR-Testosterone and AR-BPA complexes. Benzophenone-3 (BZF-3) was the only synthetic filter to form a hydrogen bond with the Gln711 residue and a cation- π interaction with Arg752, both also observed in Testosterone. Octocrylene (OCR) showed interactions coinciding with the AR BF-3 region. Molecular dynamics simulations performed with BZF-3 and Cinoxate (MCE) showed that the presence of UV filters conferred greater conformational stability to the AR compared to the receptor without a ligand (AR-Apo). However, the increase in the Radius of Gyration (Rg) and the Solvent-Accessible Surface

Area (SASA) indicated receptor expansion and reduced hydrophobicity at the AR site. The free interaction energy calculated using the MMPBSA method confirmed higher affinity for Testosterone (-186.47 ± 9.69 kJ/mol), followed by MCE (-111.79 ± 12.55 kJ/mol) and BZF-3 (-60.08 ± 10.87 kJ/mol), demonstrating lower binding potency but suggesting an endocrine-disrupting profile for MCE and BZF-3. Van der Waals forces were the main stabilizing factor of the complexes. **Conclusion** The study demonstrates that the UV filters BZF-3 and MCE, although showing lower affinity than Testosterone, interact with key residues of the AR active site and promote relevant structural changes, providing useful information for the development of safer sunscreens.

Keywords: Endocrine Disruptor, Molecular Docking, Molecular Dynamics, Photoprotector, Androgenous Receptor.

Funding: FAPES

Symposium - Integrative Therapeutics: Advances in Non-Conventional Approaches to Health

HISTATIN-5 AS A PROMISING NATURAL PRODUCT: RATIONAL MODIFICATION AND LIPOSOMAL ENCAPSULATION FOR CANDIDA ALBICANS CONTROL

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Introduction: Histatin-5 (Hst5), a naturally occurring peptide in human saliva, exhibits potent antifungal activity against resistant strains of *Candida albicans*. However, its therapeutic potential is limited due to rapid proteolytic degradation by salivary enzymes. To enhance its antifungal efficacy and stability, this study explores two complementary strategies: rational peptide modification via solid-phase peptide synthesis (SPPS) and encapsulation within liposomal carriers. **Materials and Methods:** Using SPPS, three novel peptides derived from the Hst5 sequence (8WH5, 7WH5, and 6WH5) were designed and synthesized. Their stability in human whole saliva (WS) was evaluated through cationic-PAGE and HPLC over time (Research Ethics Board, University of Saskatchewan, review #1597, July 2, 2019). Liposomes were prepared via the thin-film hydration method to protect the peptides from enzymatic degradation. These systems were characterized by dynamic light scattering (DLS), atomic force microscopy (AFM), and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). Biofilm inhibition assays were conducted using *Candida albicans* strains ATCC 90028, 18804, and 10231. **Results:** Cationic-PAGE and HPLC analyses revealed that the modified peptides (8WH5, 7WH5, and 6WH5) degraded more slowly in saliva compared to native Hst5. Notably, the modified peptides remained detectable after 8 hours in WS, whereas Hst5 was completely degraded within 1.5 hours. Liposomes containing peptides exhibited diameters ranging from 90.0 to 120.0 nm and negative zeta potentials (−11.6 mV for empty liposomes; < −8.7 mV for peptide-loaded liposomes). The polydispersity index (PDI) ranged from 0.200 to 0.300, and encapsulation efficiency exceeded 90% for all peptides, indicating successful incorporation despite their hydrophilic nature. AFM and FTIR data suggested electrostatic interactions between the peptides and the liposomal bilayer. Liposomal formulations demonstrated superior inhibition of mature biofilms, requiring concentrations eight times lower than those of free peptides. **Conclusion:** The modified peptides 8WH5, 7WH5, and 6WH5 showed enhanced resistance to salivary proteases and effectively prevented biofilm formation. Although liposomal encapsulation offered limited protection against proteolytic degradation, it significantly improved antifungal activity against mature biofilms. These findings support the potential of peptide modification and liposomal delivery as a promising strategy for controlling *C. albicans* infections in the oral cavity.

Keywords: *Candida albicans*, peptides, saliva, liposomes, biofilms

Funding: FAPESP grant number 2022/07949-5

Symposium - Integrative Therapeutics: Advances in Non-Conventional Approaches to Health

GUT DYSBIOSIS EXACERBATES SEIZURE SUSCEPTIBILITY AND DISRUPTS INTESTINAL INTEGRITY

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INTRODUCTION: Epilepsy is a chronic neurological disorder that affects nearly 70 million people worldwide and is characterized by recurrent abnormal neuronal discharges. Approximately 30% of patients are refractory to antiseizure medications or experience intolerable side effects. Increasing evidence indicates that the gut microbiota plays a key role in regulating the gut–brain axis, influencing systemic inflammation, neuronal excitability, and seizure susceptibility. **OBJECTIVE:** To evaluate the effects of gut dysbiosis on the severity of pentylenetetrazol (PTZ)-induced seizures and on neuronal and intestinal integrity in mice. **METHODS:** Thirty male C57BL/6 mice (20–30 g) from the Universidade Vila Velha animal facility (CEUA 666-2023) were randomly distributed into three groups (n=10): Control (oral and intraperitoneal 0.9% saline), PTZ (oral saline and PTZ 50 mg/kg, i.p.), and Antibiotic (oral antibiotic cocktail, 200 μ L, plus PTZ 50 mg/kg, i.p.). Gut dysbiosis was induced by antibiotic administration for three consecutive days, followed by PTZ injections on days 1 and 4. Seizure activity was recorded for 15 minutes and blindly evaluated using a modified Racine scale, along with behavioral assessments (locomotion and immobility). After experimentation, animals were euthanized, and biological samples (small intestine, cecum, brain, and plasma) were collected. Data were expressed as mean \pm SEM and analyzed by ANOVA (GraphPad Prism 8.0) with Tukey's post hoc test or unpaired t-tests for seizure behavior ($p < 0.05$). **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:** Gut dysbiosis significantly increased seizure incidence (PTZ+ANT: 18.5 ± 2.07 vs. PTZ: 8.0 ± 1.77), reduced locomotor activity (29.0 ± 2.0 s vs. 56.0 ± 5.49 s), and prolonged immobility (620.9 ± 20 s vs. 533.1 ± 23 s). Body weight was unchanged among groups. However, the PTZ+ANT group showed higher intestinal permeability (0.60 ± 0.09 μ g/mL vs. PTZ: 0.30 ± 0.03 μ g/mL), greater cecal weight (0.84 ± 0.08 g vs. PTZ: 0.36 ± 0.04 g), and shorter small intestine length (32.0 ± 0.75 cm vs. PTZ: 36.4 ± 0.60 cm). Oxidative stress was markedly elevated in the brain (PTZ+ANT: 850.5 ± 19.41 a.u. vs. PTZ: 468.2 ± 17.22 a.u.) and intestine (PTZ+ANT: 762.8 ± 26.57 a.u. vs. PTZ: 406.2 ± 7.31 a.u.), accompanied by higher apoptosis in both brain ($32.24 \pm 2.15\%$ vs. PTZ: $24.79 \pm 1.33\%$) and intestinal tissues ($17.32 \pm 1.01\%$ vs. PTZ: $11.60 \pm 0.58\%$). These findings demonstrate that gut dysbiosis enhances seizure susceptibility, impairs motor behavior, and compromises intestinal barrier integrity. The pronounced increase in oxidative stress and apoptosis suggests that microbiota disruption amplifies neuroinflammatory and systemic responses, leading to greater neuronal excitability. The absence of body weight differences indicates that these effects are independent of

nutritional status, reinforcing the direct influence of microbiota alterations on brain and intestinal physiology. **CONCLUSION:** Gut dysbiosis aggravates seizures and promotes neuronal and intestinal damage. Restoring microbial balance may represent a promising therapeutic strategy to reduce seizure frequency and severity, emphasizing the pivotal role of the gut–brain axis in epilepsy pathophysiology.

Keywords: Epilepsy; Gut microbiota; Gut–brain axis; Antibiotic cocktail; Inflammation.

Funding: Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível Superior (CAPES); Espírito Santo Research and Innovation Foundation (FAPES).

POSTER PRESENTATIONS

THEMATIC AXIS I

Human Health and Climate Change:
Global Challenges, Rights, and Future Perspectives

EVALUATION OF MICROPLASTIC CONTAMINATION IN TABLE SUGAR: A GLOBAL STUDY ACROSS 24 COUNTRIES

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Introduction: Microplastic (MPs) contamination is a global concern with serious implications for environmental integrity and human health. These synthetic particles, resulting from plastic degradation, have already been reported in several foods and beverages. However, table sugar, a commodity consumed daily worldwide in its pure form and as an additive in processed products, has received little attention in this context. Given its large-scale production and universal consumption, evaluating MPs contamination in sugar is essential to understand dietary exposure. This study aimed to assess the occurrence, abundance, and characteristics of MPs in sachet-packaged table sugar consumed in different countries, identifying this overlooked route of human contamination. **Methodology:** One hundred table sugar samples were obtained from 24 countries in Europe, the Americas, and Asia, and analyzed in triplicate. Each 3 g replicate was dissolved in filtered deionized water and filtered on qualitative filter paper. MPs were quantified and categorized using a stereoscope with an attached camera, distinguishing filaments and fragments as well as particle color. A subset of particles was analyzed by Raman spectroscopy to determine polymer composition. The Estimated Dietary Intake (EDI) was calculated using the formula $EDI = (SgC \times MPp)/SM$, combining MPs abundance with sugar consumption data provided by FAO/WHO. Quality control measures, including the use of cotton lab coats, filtered water, and sealed samples, were applied to minimize external contamination. **Results:** MPs were detected in all samples, representing a 100% contamination rate. A total of 3,977 particles were identified, with filaments (56.63%) predominating over fragments (43.37%). Blue and black were the most frequent colors, reflecting their likely industrial origin. Raman spectroscopy identified three main polymers: polyurethane (PU), polyethylene terephthalate (PET), and polyethylene (PE). MPs abundance varied from 4 to 312 particles per sample, but contamination was universal. EDI estimates indicated Brazil and the United States as the countries with the highest potential ingestion of MPs via sugar, due to both contamination levels and high per capita consumption. **Conclusion:** This study demonstrates that table sugar is a significant and widespread pathway for MPs ingestion. The 100% contamination rate across 24 countries confirms the ubiquity of this issue, regardless of geographic region or economic development. Considering documented risks of MPs, such as inflammation, oxidative stress, and potential impacts on reproduction and metabolism,

these findings raise critical concerns for food safety and human health. Regulatory measures and improved processing protocols are urgently required to mitigate MPs contamination during sugar production and packaging. By highlighting sugar as an important vector of dietary exposure, this research contributes to the growing debate on microplastic contamination and underscores the necessity of global strategies to address this emerging hazard. Additional analyses of samples from Africa, Asia, and Oceania are currently underway to expand these findings and compare them with Schuab et al. (2025).

Keywords: Dietary Exposure; Food Safety; Polymer Identification; Anthropogenic Contaminants; Ingestion Pathway.

Funding

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PHARMACEUTICAL DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF BAR SOAP FORMULATIONS FROM RESIDUAL COOKING OIL

Laura Gregório Assunção, Mariana Santos Pinheiro

The improper disposal of used cooking oil poses a significant environmental threat, contributing to water and soil contamination and clogging of sewage systems. In this context, reusing this waste through the production of artisanal soaps represents a sustainable alternative that mitigates environmental impacts and promotes a circular economy. This study aimed to develop and evaluate bar soap formulations using filtered residual oil (FRO), both untreated and treated with activated carbon, in order to reduce undesirable properties and obtain a functional and safe final product. The experiments were conducted at the Health Sciences Center of the Federal University of Espírito Santo (UFES), and included the physicochemical characterization of FRO through analyses of acid value, saponification value, peroxide value, density, and viscosity. Activated carbon treatment was applied to improve the quality of the raw material, followed by the production of soap formulations, which were evaluated for organoleptic properties (color, odor, consistency, and appearance), pH, foam formation, and free alkalinity/acidity. Additionally, the three formulations were comparatively analyzed using a radar chart. The results indicated that the activated carbon treatment did not significantly reduce acid or saponification values, while it led to a statistically significant increase in the peroxide value ($p = 0.042$). The high viscosity (87.93 cSt) further reflected the advanced oxidation of the residual oil, although the density remained within reference values (0.9195 g/mL). The soaps showed no excess alkali in free alkalinity tests and presented measurable free acidity. Among the formulations, formulation 3 demonstrated the best overall performance, with superior results in odor, consistency, appearance, and foam production, despite limited improvements in the lipid profile of the treated oil. Formulation 2 showed the lowest free acidity (0.53%) but exhibited a firmer texture. In conclusion, the reuse of FRO is a viable strategy for producing stable and functional bar soaps, emphasizing its potential as a sustainable, low-cost, and high-quality raw material for eco-friendly cleaning products.

Keywords: Residual cooking oil; Soap production; Reuse; Formulation; Activated carbon treatment; Environmental sustainability.

This research was funded through the Scientific Initiation project conducted with students from EEEFM Major Alfredo Pedro Rabayolli, supported by FAPES Call No. 12/2023, addressing the theme “Sustainable Transformation: An Analysis of the National Solid Waste Policy, Reverse Logistics, and Soap Production from Used Cooking Oil.”

THEMATIC AXIS II

Environmental Exposure: Health, Biomarkers
and Ecosystem Integrity

PRE-GESTATIONAL CO-EXPOSURE TO MERCURY AND TRIBUTYLTIN LEADS TO HEPATIC OFFSPRING CONSEQUENCES IN BOTH GENDERS

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Introduction: The contaminants mercury (Hg) and tributyltin (TBT) are present in the environment, and their main route of human exposure is through the consumption of contaminated food. Studies showed that these contaminants individually can cause reproductive toxicity in both genders. However, the consequences of prenatal exposure to these contaminants as a mixture are poorly understood. Therefore, this study was conducted to evaluate the hepatic offspring consequences of both genders after pregestational co-exposure to the Hg+TBT contaminant mixture. **Materials and methods:** This research used adult female Wistar rats (n=4/group, 8-12 weeks old, with an average weight of 216 g) and adult male controls for mating, provided by the Central Animal Facility/UFES. This proposal was approved by CEUA-UFES No. 04/2023. Subacute exposure was performed over 15 days, during which the Hg+TBT group (MIX) was exposed via gavage to 100 ng/kg/day of TBT simultaneously with intramuscular (im) exposure to Hg at 4.6 µg/kg (initial dose) and 0.07 µg/kg/day (maintenance dose). The control group (CON) was exposed to the same administration stress to their respective vehicles. After treatment, a harem was formed in a 2:1 male ratio for 90 consecutive days. The pups were removed from the mother on the first postnatal day and separated by sex according to the anogenital distance. The data obtained were expressed as mean ± SEM. The D'Agostino and Pearson omnibus tests were used to assess the normality of the data and Student's t-test and Mann-Whitney test for Gaussian and non-Gaussian data, respectively. A p < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. **Results:** A reduction in body weight was noted in the MIX group vs. the CON (CON: 6.1 ± 0.1; MIX: 5.7 ± 0.1, p<0.05). An increase in blood glucose level was observed in the MIX vs. CON pups (CON: 60.5 ± 2.1; MIX: 67.8 ± 1.7, p<0.05). A decrease in hepatic glycogen deposition was observed in the MIX vs. CON group (CON: 5.1 ± 0.5; MIX: 0.7 ± -4.3, p<0.05). A reduction in the number of hepatic nuclei in the MIX vs. CON group was observed (CON: 120.9 ± -3.6; MIX: 117.2 ± 1.5, p<0.05). Furthermore, there was an increase in the number of mast cells in the MIX vs CON group (CON: 4.2 ± 0.3; MIX: 8.12 ± 0.5, p<0.05) and high collagen deposition in the MIX vs CON group (CON: 0.2 ± 0.06; MIX: 0.3 ± 0.03, p<0.05). **Conclusion:** Therefore, these data suggest that exposure to the Hg+TBT mixture generates potential impacts on metabolism, glycemia, and liver development of pups.

Keywords: reproductive toxicity; prenatal; contaminated food; environment.

Funding: CNPq (307224/2021-0) and FAPES (Announcements No. 19/2022 and No. 03/2021).

MICROPLASTIC CONTAMINATION IN EDIBLE BIVALVES FROM THE ESPÍRITO SANTO COAST AND ITS POSSIBLE IMPLICATIONS FOR HUMAN HEALTH

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Introduction: The contamination by microplastics (MPs) in marine organisms of ecological and economic importance has received increasing attention, especially due to the risk of transferring these contaminants along the food chain to humans. On the coast of Espírito Santo, several studies have quantified MPs in bivalves sold for consumption, revealing both the magnitude of contamination and recurrent patterns in shapes, colors, and polymer types. Since bivalves such as oysters, mussels, and clams are eaten whole, without removal of the digestive tract, direct ingestion of MPs is a public health concern due to potential toxic effects of polymers and additives. These studies not only provide an overview of plastic pollution in Espírito Santo but also highlight the implications of this exposure for food safety and human health. **Materials and Methods:** Our research group investigated MPs in economically important bivalves from Espírito Santo. The studied species were *Crassostrea rhizophorae*, *Mytella strigata*, *Crassostrea brasiliiana*, *Perna perna*, *Tivela mactroides*, and *Donax hanleyanus*, collected from coastal ecosystems in both urbanized and preserved areas. Soft tissues were digested in 10% KOH solution at 60 °C for ~48 h. The digests were sieved (90 µm), and retained MPs were transferred to Petri dishes. Quantification and classification were performed under a stereomicroscope, while polymer identification employed Raman spectroscopy and/or µ-FTIR. **Results:** Several studies have revealed MPs contamination in Espírito Santo bivalves. Dalbó et al. (2025) reported 361 MPs in *Donax hanleyanus*, whereas Otegui et al. (2024) identified 3,427 MPs in *Tivela mactroides*. Menezes et al. (2025) quantified 1,242 MPs in *Crassostrea rhizophorae* and *Mytella strigata*. Da Costa et al. (2023) recorded 1,386 MPs in *C. brasiliiana*, *M. strigata*, *P. perna*, and *T. mactroides*. In a follow-up study, de Paula et al. (2025) found 6,272 MPs in the same four species. Across studies, filaments and fragments predominated, with filaments being the most abundant. Blue and black were the most common colors, often linked to fishing gear and urban waste. The most recurrent polymers were Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET), Polypropylene (PP), and Polyethylene (PE). Other polymers identified included Polyurethane (PU), Polystyrene (PS), Nylon, polyester, and polyacrylic acid. **Conclusion:** MPs contamination in bivalves from Espírito Santo confirms their role as bioaccumulators and indicates potential trophic transfer and biomagnification. Since the studied species are widely consumed, these findings reveal a direct pathway for human exposure to MPs through food. This risk extends beyond ingestion of polymers, as MPs can also act as vectors of toxic chemical pollutants. Addressing this issue requires specific legislation to establish limits for MPs in foods, filling the current regulatory gap in Brazil. Furthermore,

reducing plastic use — especially single-use plastics — and strengthening public awareness are essential measures to ensure food safety and protect marine ecosystems.

Keywords: Bioaccumulation; Trophic Transfer; Polymers; Food Safety; Bioindicators

This work was supported by the Foundation for Support of Science and Technology of the State of Espírito Santo (FAPES/VALE) no 01/2015 (Process no 521/2016).

GENETIC DIVERSITY OF ANTIMICROBIAL-RESISTANT ENTEROBACTERALES FROM ENVIRONMENTAL SOURCES IN A BRAZILIAN AGRICULTURAL HUB

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Introduction

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a global health challenge strongly associated with the intensive use of antimicrobials in human medicine, agriculture, and animal production. In Brazil, resistant bacteria and novel resistance genes have been identified in diverse environmental sources, raising concerns about their dissemination within the One Health context. Santa Maria de Jetibá (Espírito Santo, Brazil) is the country's leading egg producer and also a significant regional center for vegetable production. The intensive practices adopted in this area increase the risk of environmental contamination and AMR spread. Our previous study described the phenotypic resistance profiles and genes of bacterial isolates from this region. To complement these findings, we aimed to genetically characterize isolates and investigate potential relationships among bacteria from distinct environmental niches. **Methods** Environmental isolates collected from water, bathroom surface swabs, crop soil, and poultry litter, antimicrobial resistance testing, and detection of resistance genes were performed as previously described (Mothé, 2025). Clonal diversity of 15 *Enterobacterales* isolates with similar resistance profiles — 12 of which were classified as multidrug-resistant and predominantly resistant to beta-lactams — was assessed using *Enterobacterial* Repetitive Intergenic Consensus Polymerase Chain Reaction (ERIC-PCR). Amplicons were separated on 1.5% agarose gels, stained, and visualized under LED transillumination. Banding patterns were analyzed with GelJ v.2.0 software, and isolates showing $\geq 85\%$ similarity were considered clonally related. **Results** For *Escherichia coli*, eight isolates generated distinct banding patterns, forming multiple clusters with similarity below 85%. This indicates high genetic diversity and the absence of dominant clonal lineages among resistant strains, suggesting that resistance traits were acquired independently rather than through clonal spread. *Enterobacter cloacae* isolates

(n=5) also displayed heterogeneous patterns, with no evidence of close clonal relatedness. The results reinforce the genetic variability of this species in environmental samples, which may reflect its adaptation to different ecological niches. In contrast, *Enterobacter asburiae* isolates (n=2) exhibited higher genetic similarity, clustering together, collected from swab of private and poultry litter, which suggests the presence of a more closely related lineage. This finding may indicate localized dissemination or persistence of a resistant clone within the sampled environment. Overall, the ERIC-PCR profiles showed predominance of genetic diversity among resistant isolates, supporting the hypothesis that resistance in these settings is driven more by horizontal gene transfer and selective pressure than by clonal expansion. **Conclusion** ERIC-PCR revealed predominantly diverse clonal profiles among resistant environmental isolates, with limited evidence of clonal dissemination. These findings highlight the role of environmental reservoirs as sources of genetically heterogeneous resistant bacteria and reinforce the importance of monitoring AMR within the One Health context.

Keywords: Antimicrobial resistance; ERIC-PCR; Environmental bacteria; Clonal diversity; One Health.

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ASSESSMENT OF THE TOXICOLOGICAL EFFECT ON PERCOLATED WASTE. A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PHYTOCOMPOUND AND GLYPHOSATE RESIDUES

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The present work aimed to evaluate the genotoxic effects of different types of phytosanitary agents. This analysis provides a fundamental warning about safety in agricultural management, covering both "natural" alternatives and residual exposure to synthetic herbicides.

The first survey was conducted in a Phytosanitary Plant Compound (PPC), a biological alternative derived from 13 plants with herbicidal potential. The study validated its efficacy in controlling signalgrass, with the maximum dose of 5% achieving 100% control. However, toxicological evaluation revealed a significant risk. Mutagenicity (Ames Test) and genotoxicity (*Allium cepa* Test) indicated that the most effective concentration (5%) was mutagenic and induced a significant increase in the frequency of micronuclei, a clear indicator of DNA damage. This result is a stark reminder that natural origin does not guarantee safety, and that the high concentration required for field efficacy can pose an acute and direct risk of genetic damage.

In parallel, the second study investigated glyphosate (GLY), the most widely used synthetic herbicide globally, from the perspective of environmental and residual exposure. To analyze the results of the Comet Assay, the protocol was standardized using software ImageJ to objectively quantify cellular damage. The focus was on ultra-low concentrations, in parts per billion (ppb), simulating the levels found in contaminated food and water. The study demonstrated that GLY induces significant DNA damage even at the lowest dose tested (1 ppb). The Damage Frequency (DF), which measures the percentage of cells with comet tails, jumped from 4.44% (negative control - H₂O) to 22.56% at a concentration of 1 ppb. The Damage Index (DI), which measures the severity of the damage, increased progressively, reaching a maximum value of 190.00 at a dose of 200 ppb, reinforcing a strong genotoxic potential. This finding points to a chronic and ubiquitous risk of genotoxicity, not limited to high-dose application, but also resulting from the persistence and accumulation of the compound in the environment.

The critical connection between the two studies lies in the diversity and persistence of genotoxic hazards. PPC demonstrates a risk of DNA damage linked to the effective dose (management risk), while GLY signals a risk of DNA damage linked to residual contamination (chronic exposure risk). The convergence of these data reinforces the urgent need for robust and standardized toxicological assessment (such as quantification with ImageJ) for all pesticides. It is imperative that stringent regulations consider not only efficacy but also the potential for invisible DNA damage, ensuring the protection of human and environmental health.

Keywords: Genotoxicity, Phytosanitary, Glyphosate, Mutagenicity, Environmental Risk.

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ANALYSIS OF THE PERFORMANCE OF NATURAL FILTERS IN MITIGATING GENOTOXICITY INDUCED BY 17 β -ESTRADIOL USING THE COMET ASSAY

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The purpose of this study is to evaluate the efficiency of different filter materials in the remediation of the hormone 17 β -estradiol. The growing presence of this emerging contaminant in water bodies, resulting from the improper disposal of domestic, hospital, and agro-industrial effluents, has been associated with a number of adverse effects, including feminization of fish and reproductive changes, as well as potential risks to human health through the food chain and consumption of contaminated water. To analyze the genotoxic effects induced by 17 β -estradiol, the comet assay was performed. This technique allows the detection of DNA damage at the cellular level, and its ability to quantify the level of genetic damage by measuring DNA migration in the form of a “comet” under electrophoresis makes it ideal for genotoxicity assessments in environmental studies. The development of the work involved the preparation of samples with controlled concentrations of the hormone. Subsequently, these samples were subjected to passage through different filters to simulate remediation processes. After treatment, the *Allium cepa* cells exposed to the samples were isolated and subjected to the comet assay to assess DNA integrity. The analysis of the images obtained was standardized and quantified using ImageJ software, allowing for an objective quantification of the damage. To ensure the validity of the results, controls were used: a negative control, consisting of roots exposed to ultrapure water, and a positive control, where the roots were exposed to an agent known to induce DNA damage, methyl methylsulfonate (MMS). Filters based on banana biomass, *Pleurotus ostreatus*, δ -FeOOH, and their combination were tested. With the values measured, scores were defined to quantify the damage, and these scores were used to calculate the Damage Index (DI) and Damage Frequency (DF%), which demonstrated whether the filters were efficient or not. All treatments showed the ability to mitigate the genetic damage caused by E2, with δ -FeOOH showing the lowest damage rates, followed by *Pleurotus ostreatus* biomass, banana biomass and their combination. The findings highlight the promising use of natural, accessible, and sustainable materials in the remediation of estrogen-contaminated effluents.

Keywords: 17 β -estradiol, genotoxicity, *Allium cepa*, biomass, comet assay.

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TOXIC EFFECTS OF CO-EXPOSURE TO MERCURY AND CADMIUM ON REPRODUCTIVE FUNCTION IN WISTAR RATS

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Introduction: Heavy metals such as mercury (Hg) and cadmium (Cd) are naturally present in our world, however, human activities contribute to their release into the environment, contaminating air, water, and soil (Rzymiski et al., 2015). They represent a risk to human and animal health and are classified as endocrine disruptors. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), exposure causes damage to the female reproductive system (WHO, 2020). The aim of the study was to investigate the toxic effects of co-exposure to mercury and cadmium on reproductive function in Wistar rats. **Material and methods:** They were used female Wistar rats (8–10 weeks of age), randomly divided into two groups (n° 5): a) (CON), exposed to intramuscular saline solution (mg/kg/day, IM), and b) MIX, exposed to Hg (initial dose of 4.6 mg/kg as a loading dose, followed by subsequent doses of 0.07 mg/kg/day, IM) + Cd (drinking water containing CdCl₂ at 100 mg/L⁻¹). The estrous cycle was analyzed daily between 8:00 and 10:00. Tissue morphological analysis was performed using H&E and Picro Sirius Red staining. Hormonal evaluation was conducted using ELISA kits. Data are reported as mean ± SEM. Statistical analysis was performed using Student's t-test, with a statistical significance of p<0.05. All protocols were approved by the UFES Animal Use Ethics Committee (protocol no. 04/2023). **Results:** After exposure, an increase in estrus time and cycle length was observed in the MIX group compared to the CON group (CON: 1.66 ± 0.17; Hg+Cd: 3.16 ± 0.59, p<0.05). Serum levels of estradiol and luteinizing hormone (LH) decreased in the MIX group compared to the CON group (CON: 28.68 ± 3.01; Hg+Cd: 12.98 ± 3.20, p<0.05), (CON: 227.10 ± 7.55; Hg+Cd: 165.40 ± 7.52, p<0.05), respectively. In the ovaries, a decrease in the number of primary follicles was observed in the exposed group (CON: 1.46 ± 0.20; Hg+Cd: 0.67 ± 0.09, p<0.05). The antral follicle count increased in the MIX group compared to the CON group (CON: 0.96 ± 0.09; Hg+Cd: 0.92 ± 0.07, p<0.05). In the MIX group, there was a decrease in the corpus luteum count compared to the CON group (CON: 1.24 ± 0.19; Hg+Cd: 0.81 ± 0.07, p<0.05). The total area of the uterus, endometrium, total myometrium and luminal epithelium were reduced in the MIX group compared to the CON group (CON: 3.44 ± 0.15; Hg+Cd: 2.31 ± 0.11, p<0.05), (CON: 0.50 ± 0.009; Hg+Cd: 0.41 ± 0.02, p<0.05), (CON: 285.0 ± 6.56; Hg+Cd: 258.9 ± 7.71, p<0.05), (CON: 15.37 ± 0.42; Hg+Cd: 16.72 ± 0.38, p<0.05), respectively. Histological analysis stained with Picro Sirius Red revealed an increase in collagen deposition in the ovaries of the MIX group compared to the CON group (CON: 5.90 ± 0.56; Hg+Cd: 15.06 ± 1.48, p<0.05). In the uterus, collagen deposition was decreased in the MIX group compared to the CON group (CON: 0.201 ± 0.007; Hg+Cd: 0.134 ± 0.012, p<0.05). **Conclusion:** These results suggest that co-exposure to these

metals compromises female reproductive function, promoting endocrine dysregulation, hormonal, morphological and tissue changes.

Keywords: Cadmium. Estrous cycle. Mercury. Female reproduction.

Financial support: CAPES, FEST, FAPES, LETC.

ANALYSIS OF WATER TREATMENT USING ARTIFICIAL ZEOLITES ORIGINATING FROM LITHIUM CARBONATE PRODUCTION WASTE

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Introduction. Water treatment research for potability purposes has evolved in recent years, especially through the use of artificial zeolites, which are well-defined materials in terms of size and arrangement, forming channels, such as Aluminum Silicate. A study was conducted to evaluate the potential of residual Al_2SiO_5 generated by the company *Companhia Brasileira de Lítio* in the flocculation and decantation of dispersed clay particles in aqueous solution. **Materials and Methods.** The test was carried out in laboratory 112-A of ICET, Mucuri Campus. In one liter of distilled water, 0.5 cm³ of sieved clay (270 mesh sieve) was applied. Then, 1.0 ml of a 0.5 M sodium hydroxide solution was added, and the materials were mixed and homogenized for a period of five minutes, aiming at the disaggregation and dispersion of the clay colloidal particles. Subsequently, 40 ml of the clay solution were separated into capped test tubes. The collected aluminum silicate was dried in an oven at 70°C for 72 hours, ground, and sieved through a 170 mesh sieve. The material was then divided into beakers and washed with distilled water, 1% hydrochloric acid, and 0.5 M sodium hydroxide, followed by a rinse with distilled water. After that, the materials were again dried, ground, and sieved. A mass of 0.005 grams of silicate, after treatments, was placed in test tubes containing the clay solution. Control tubes without silicate and untreated silicate were also prepared. After application, the tubes were shaken vigorously for 10 seconds and left to rest. At defined periods (30 minutes and 1 hour), the solution was evaluated for turbidity using a manual turbidimeter. **Results:** The results obtained showed that the residual aluminum silicate significantly contributed to the aggregation of dispersed clay particles in water, yielding better results compared to the control treatment without silicate application. The best result was obtained with the treatment using untreated residual aluminum silicate, only sieved. Despite the turbidity reduction, even with the maximum test time (4 hours), turbidity below 50 NTU was not achieved. The silicate responses also varied according to the pH of the medium, with the most efficient flocculation results occurring in basic media (pH > 10). **Conclusion:** Thus, this study indicates that aluminum silicate has potential as a flocculating agent in water treatment, but its efficiency is still limited by the low level of electric charges.

Keywords:

Water treatment, aluminum silicate, waste, lithium, flocculation, decantation, clay solution, zeolites, turbidity, flocculating agent.

LITHIUM BIOSORPTION, AVAILABLE IN MINING TAILINGS, USING PLEUROTUS OSTREATUS IMMOBILIZED IN BENTONITE

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Introduction. According to Ramrakhiani (2016), the use of fungal biomasses for metal biosorption in aqueous media has proven to be highly effective, representing an environmentally friendly, efficient, and relatively low-cost option. In this process, metals are adsorbed onto the biomass surface through physicochemical interactions, where immobilized biomass tends to have a higher adsorption capacity due to the absence of competing protons resulting from the metabolism of living cells. However, the association of immobilized fungal biomasses with nanomaterial particles—particularly the use of the fungus *Pleurotus ostreatus* combined with bentonite nanomaterial—has been shown to be more effective for metal removal. This was observed by Kocaoba & Arisoy (2018) in their study on the biosorption of cadmium and lead in aqueous solutions, where they achieved results close to 95%, with columns characterized by low material consumption and high efficiency. Therefore, the present study is justified by the need to develop a sustainable alternative for the utilization of residual lithium present in mining waste, using a methodology that has proven effective in the biosorption of other metals and that features low operational cost and easy application. The main objective is to investigate the efficiency of a biocomposite column composed of *Pleurotus ostreatus* immobilized in bentonite nanomaterial for the separation of residual lithium available in mining waste.

Materials and Methods. The assembly of the filtering medium was carried out following the methodology described by Kocaoba (2018), in which 200 mg of *Pleurotus ostreatus*, properly immobilized according to Mahan & Holcombe (1992), were mixed with 2 g of bentonite and 2 ml of distilled water, thus forming a paste. This mixture was then placed in an oven at 80°C for 24 hours to promote drying, and the drying process was repeated once more in order to increase efficiency. After assembling the filtering medium, the filtration columns were prepared using columns with a 10 mm diameter, where the amount of filtering material varied according to each experiment. For the analyses, a lithium standard with different concentrations and ultrapure water was used. Between each analysis, the column was regenerated using 0.1 M HCl. After the filtration process was completed, the biosorbed material is being analyzed using inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) in order to determine the amount of lithium biosorbed by the filter. **Results:** Up to the present moment of the event, the study is still in progress, and the ICP-MS analysis results have not yet been obtained to allow the evaluation of the filtration column efficiency using *Pleurotus ostreatus* immobilized in bentonite. **Conclusion:** Although the final results have not yet been obtained, the immobilization process of *Pleurotus ostreatus* in bentonite and the preparation of the filtration columns, as well as the entire filtration process, occurred as expected according to the literature review.

Keywords: Lithium; Biosorption; *Pleurotus Ostreatus*; Bentonite; Mining Tailings.

ALLIUM CEPA BIOASSAY FOR EVALUATING THE TOXICITY OF SLUDGE FROM A WATER TREATMENT PLANT

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A major challenge in water treatment processes is the effective management of sludge generated at water treatment plants (WTP). This sludge, which exhibits a gel-like consistency when at rest and becomes relatively fluid when agitated, typically has a high moisture content, ranging from 85% to 95%, despite its apparent solidity. According to the Brazilian Association of Technical Standards, it is classified as solid waste under the Brazilian Regulatory Standard 10.004. To evaluate sludge toxicity and its potential environmental and biological impacts, the *Allium cepa* bioassay has proven to be a valuable and sensitive tool. By using onion roots to detect toxic effects at the cellular level, this bioassay identifies genetic and morphological alterations that indicate the presence of harmful substances. Its high sensitivity to chemical agents and contaminants commonly found in waste enables a precise assessment of potential risks to living organisms. This study aimed to evaluate the toxicity of sludge generated at the Seminar WTP, located in Mariana, Minas Gerais, using *Allium cepa* bioassays, aiming to investigate the feasibility of its reuse as a raw material in various applications, such as the production of activated carbon. Cytotoxicity was assessed based on the mitotic index of the cells, while genotoxicity was determined by analyzing chromosomal aberrations. The results indicated significant cytotoxic effects compared with the negative control, although no statistically significant levels of genotoxicity were observed. The application of bioassays proved essential for assessing sludge toxicity, as it provides detailed insights into the harmful effects at both cellular and genetic levels. This approach serves as a fundamental tool to ensure that waste treatment and disposal practices are safe and effective, thereby promoting the sustainable use of the material. Further studies, including comprehensive physical and chemical analyses of the sludge, are recommended to deepen the understanding of its characteristics and to evaluate its potential for environmentally safe reuse.

Keywords: Solid Waste, Toxicity, Onion Seeds, Mitotic Index, Chromosomal Aberrations.

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LIFE EXPECTANCY AMONG BRAZILIAN MALE POLICE OFFICERS AND FIREFIGHTERS IN 30 YEARS

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Introduction: Police officers and firefighters face high mortality rates due to extreme working conditions, characterized by physical and psychological stress, exposure to harmful agents, and occupational hazards. These conditions contribute to premature deaths from cardiovascular disease, neoplasms, and external causes such as accidents, homicides, and suicides. Exposure to carcinogenic substances, such as combustion products, increases the incidence of cancer, especially among firefighters. Factors such as long shifts, repetitive trauma, and intense physical exertion increase cardiovascular risk, often resulting in sudden events such as heart attacks and sudden death in both professions. The unique combination of occupational stressors distinguishes these professionals, significantly impacting their life expectancy. **Materials and methods:** A retrospective study was conducted analyzing the death certificates of male military police officers and firefighters in the state of Espírito Santo, southeast of Brazil, between 1988 and 2019, compared with the Brazilian population during the same period. The variables were characterized by descriptive analysis and the association between variables was analyzed using the Abbreviated Life Table method for both populations, by decades (1990 to 1999; 2000 to 2009 and 2010 to 2019) and age groups. Ethics Committee Approval Number: 89364125.5.0000.5060. **Results:** The remaining life expectancy of the analyzed military personnel was consistently lower than that of the general population in all age groups and periods analyzed (1988-1999, 2000-2009 and 2010-2019). The discrepancy is more pronounced at younger ages, such as 20-24, where military personnel had a life expectancy of 35.16 years (1988-1999) compared to 41.38 years for the general population, increasing to 40.08 years versus 44.43 years (2010-2019). With advancing age, the difference narrows but persists. Over the decades, improvements are observed for both groups, although the gap remains, suggesting adverse occupational impacts on military longevity. **Conclusion:** A lower life expectancy was observed among police officers and firefighters compared to the general population. This pattern is found across all age groups, most significantly at younger ages. This result supports the literature that describes the occupational exposure of these professionals as a cause of illness and raises the need for effective, targeted health prevention actions. **Keywords:** Cardiovascular Diseases; Firefighters; Mortality; Police; Occupational Stress.

Funding: No funding was received for this study, except for KNS scholarship (CNPq/FAPES; Grant No. 2025-H5S1W).

TRENDS AND CAUSES OF DEATH AMONG POLICE OFFICERS AND FIREFIGHTERS IN SOUTHEASTERN BRAZIL (1988–2019)

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Introduction: Occupational stress and exposure to hazardous or unhealthy agents are recognized risk factors for disease development. Certain professional groups, due to the specific demands of their work, are particularly vulnerable to these stressors and adverse conditions, which may compromise overall health and contribute to reduced longevity. This study aimed to examine the leading causes of death among Brazilian male military police officers and firefighters over a 30-year period. **Materials e methods:** This retrospective study examined death certificates of male military police officers and firefighters from Espírito Santo, a state located in Southeastern Brazil, covering the period from 1988 to 2019. Data on birth and death dates, cause of death, and skin color were obtained from death certificates. Age at death was calculated, and the underlying cause of death was classified according to ICD-9 and ICD-10 chapters, with support from a pathologist. Variables were characterized by descriptive analysis and the association between variables was analyzed by Qui-square test and Prais-Winsten regression, with significance level <0.05 . Ethics Committee Approval Number: 70725817.1.0000.5060. **Results:** Over three decades, 2198 deaths were observed among officers, with an average death age of 59 ± 18.5 years. On average, 69 deaths occurred annually ($SD=12.2$), with Prais-Winsten regression indicating a significant upward trend of 0.93% per year (95% CI: 0.53–1.32; $p=0.01$). The leading causes of death were circulatory system diseases (32%), external causes (26%), and neoplasms (15%). **Conclusion:** Police officers and firefighters showed premature mortality, with a high burden of circulatory diseases, external causes, and neoplasms, underscoring the importance of preventive measures and continuous health monitoring in these groups.

Keywords: Cardiovascular Diseases; Firefighters; Mortality; Police; Occupational Stress.

Funding: No funding was received for this study, except for KNS scholarship (CNPq/FAPES; Grant No. 2025-H5S1W).

EFFECTS OF EXPOSURE TO TRIBUTYL TIN ON ENDOTHELIUM-DEPENDENT VASCULAR RELAXATION IN MESENTERIC RESISTANCE ARTERIES OF WISTAR RATS

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Introduction: Tributyltin (TBT), an organotin compound once widely used in antifouling paints, is classified as a persistent organic pollutant and endocrine disruptor, leading to its prohibition. TBT exposure affects several organisms, including mammals, with reported cardiovascular impairment. The World Health Organization established an acceptable daily intake of 250 ng/kg/day. However, evidence shows that lower doses (100 ng/kg/day) can still impair vascular reactivity in Wistar rats. The specific effects of low-dose TBT on the endothelium of resistance arteries remain unclear. This study aimed to evaluate the impact of low-dose TBT exposure on endothelium-dependent relaxation in mesenteric resistance arteries, hypothesizing that low doses of TBT may induce vascular dysfunction.

Materials and methods: Female Wistar rats (*Rattus norvegicus*), 12 weeks old and weighing 200–300 g, were divided into two groups and exposed for 15 days: CT – receiving vehicle solution (0.4 % ethanol), and TBT – receiving TBT (100 ng/kg/day), both via orogastric route. All experimental protocols were previously approved (19/2022 - CEUA-UFES). Following exposure, the rats were euthanized during the metestrus/diestrus phase, and third-order mesenteric resistance artery (MRA) were isolated and mounted on a wire myograph for vascular reactivity assessment. Concentration–response curves to acetylcholine (ACh, 1 nM–10 μ M) were obtained in vessels pre-contracted with phenylephrine (PE, 3 μ M), before and after inhibition with L-NAME (300 μ M), indomethacin (INDO, 10 μ M), or clotrimazole (CLOT, 0.75 μ M), either individually or in combination. Vasorelaxation analyses were reported as mean \pm standard error of the mean and analyzed by two-way ANOVA, followed by Sidak's *post hoc* test. Comparisons between groups were performed using Student's t-test (unpaired). The results were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results: No differences were observed in relaxation between CT (AUC: 446 ± 35 a.u., $n = 15$) and TBT (AUC: 466 ± 34 a.u., $n = 12$) and there is no difference between groups, in relation to nitric oxide (NO) contribution, (AUC: CT L-NAME: 311 ± 39 a.u., $n = 6$; TBT L-NAME: 322 ± 51 a.u., $n = 11$). However, in the TBT group, maximal response (R_{max}) was reduced upon NO inhibition (TBT: $93.2 \pm 3.1\%$; TBT L-NAME: $74.3 \pm 5.5\%$), without changes in EC_{50} values (TBT: 7.31 ± 0.1 M; TBT L-NAME: 6.93 ± 0.19 M). In contrast, the CT group exhibited shifts in EC_{50} but not in R_{max} (CT: 7.25 ± 0.09 M; CT L-NAME: 6.63 ± 0.2 M). Moreover, combined inhibition of NO, prostanoid, and epoxyeicosatrienoic acid (EET) pathways produced a more pronounced reduction in R_{max} in the TBT group (TBT: $93.2 \pm 3.1\%$, $n = 13$; TBT L-NAME+INDO+CLOT: $6.7 \pm 2.5\%$, $n = 5$), compared with CT (CT: $90.5 \pm 2.9\%$, $n = 15$; CT L-NAME+INDO+CLOT: $62.5 \pm 6.3\%$, $n = 4$).

Conclusion: Exposure to low doses of TBT alters endothelium-dependent relaxation mechanisms, particularly involving the NO and EET pathways, although it does not

significantly impair vasodilation in mesenteric resistance arteries.

Keywords: Tributyltin; Vascular Relaxation; Endothelium; Mesenteric Resistance Arteries.

Funding: FAPES and FACITEC

LOW-DOSE TRIBUTYLTIN EXPOSURE INDUCES VASCULAR DYSFUNCTION AND OXIDATIVE STRESS IN RESISTANCE MESENTERIC ARTERIES OF WISTAR RATS

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Introduction: Persistent organic pollutants, such as tributyltin (TBT) are industrial by-products with bioaccumulation potential, which remain in ecosystems for long periods. Global restrictions have been implemented due to their environmental impacts and health risks. International agencies (EPA and EFSA) have established acceptable daily intake limits for TBT at 250 and 300 ng/kg/day, respectively. However, recent studies indicate that even below these limits, TBT can cause cardiovascular damage. Based on the hypothesis that low-dose TBT exposure induces morphological and functional changes in resistance mesenteric arteries of Wistar rats, this study aimed to investigate the effects of such exposure on functional and histomorphometric parameters in resistance mesenteric arteries. **Methods:** Female Wistar rats (12 weeks old, 200–300 g, metestrus/diestrus) were divided into control (CT; vehicle with 0.4 % ethanol) or TBT (100 ng/kg/day) groups that were treated via the orogastric route for 15 days, with all protocols approved by CEUA-UFES (19/2022). Concentration–response curves to phenylephrine (PE, 10^{-9} – 10^{-4} M) were obtained in a wire myograph before and after incubation with L-NAME (300 μ M). Morphology was assessed by hematoxilina-eosina and *Picrosirius* red staining. Reactive oxygen species (ROS) were measured using (DHE, 5 μ M) with Tiron (1 mM) as a negative control and Angiotensin II (Ang II, 10 μ M) as a positive control. Data from vascular reactivity were analyzed by two-way ANOVA with Sidak's post-test. AUC, Rmax, EC₅₀ (log [PE] M), and morphometric data were compared by Student's t-test. ROS levels were analyzed by one-way ANOVA with Tukey's post-hoc; $p < 0.05$ was considered significant. Data were expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). **Results:** The PE-contraction curve showed that AUC values were not different between groups (CT: 959 ± 66 a.u.; TBT: 1091 ± 41 a.u.), but it shifted leftward in TBT (EC₅₀ CT: 5.8 ± 0.1 ; TBT: 6.2 ± 0.05), indicating decreased vascular sensitivity. L-NAME incubation caused an EC₅₀ reduction in the CT group (5.82 ± 0.1 ; L-NAME: 6.5 ± 0.17 M), confirming nitric oxide (NO) dependent modulation, whereas TBT exposed showed increased AUC (1091 ± 41 a.u.; L-NAME: 1371 ± 101 a.u.), but EC₅₀ did not change (6.2 ± 0.05 ; L-NAME: 6.0 ± 0.14), suggesting a NO pathway impairment. Baseline ROS levels were elevated in TBT (CT: 9.50 ± 3.49 a.u.; TBT: 25.25 ± 3.05 a.u.), and Ang II raised ROS in both groups, especially in TBT (CT: 25.33 ± 4.03 a.u.; TBT: 42.29 ± 3.21 a.u.), indicating enhanced pro-oxidant responsiveness. Morphometric analysis showed increased collagen deposition in TBT (15.33 ± 1.97 %; CT 10.33 ± 0.91 %), with no changes in lumen, tunica media thickness, cross-sectional area, or thickness/lumen ratio. **Conclusion:** TBT exposure below safety limits causes vascular hypersensitivity to phenylephrine, impairs NO signaling, increases ROS

production, and led to greater collagen deposition. These combined changes indicate that TBT may trigger early vascular dysfunction, which represents a potential cardiovascular risk, even at levels considered safe.

Keywords: Ecotoxicology; Environmental pollution; Health risk; Organostannic compounds; Vascular dysfunction.

Financial Support: CAPES, PIBIC/CNPq, FAPES, PPGFC/UFES, LABERV.

IMPACT OF LOW-DOSE TRIBUTYLTIN EXPOSURE ON ENDOTHELIUM-DEPENDENT CORONARY VASODILATION IN RATS

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Introduction: The impacts of tributyltin (TBT) on marine biota were evidenced by anatomical changes in the gastropod *Nucella lapillus*, characterized by the development of male sexual organs in females (*imposex*). Although banned, recent investigations have reported occurrence of TBT in various ecosystems. Given its capacity for biomagnification and bioaccumulation, potential harm to important physiological systems, including the vascular system. Therefore, the aim of this study was to investigate the effects of TBT exposure on endothelium-dependent coronary vasodilation in rats. We hypothesized that TBT exposure impairs endothelium-dependent vasodilation.

Methodology: Female Wistar rats (12 weeks old, 200–300 g, metestrus/diestrus) were distributed into control (CON; vehicle with 0.4 % ethanol) or TBT (100 ng/kg/day) groups that were exposed via the orogastric route for 15 days with protocols approved by CEUA-UFES (19/2022). The estrous cycle was monitored, and experiments were conducted during metestrus/diestrus. In the coronary vascular bed, using the Langendorff method, baseline coronary perfusion pressure (CPP) was determined and a concentration–response curve to bradykinin (BK; 10^{-10} – 10^{-6} M) was obtained before and after perfusion with L-NAME, indomethacin (INDO), or clotrimazole (CLOT), applied individually or in combination. The septal coronary artery was collected for histological analysis. Data were analyzed by unpaired Student's t-test or two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Bonferroni post-hoc test. Results were expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM) and $p < 0.05$ was considered significant. **Results:** TBT group showed prolongation of metestrus/diestrus (CON: 2.5 ± 0.1 ; TBT: 4.6 ± 0.1 days) accompanied by a reduction in uterine weight (CON: 1.95 ± 0.08 mg·mm⁻¹; TBT: 1.62 ± 0.04 mg·mm⁻¹). Neither baseline CPP (CON: 94.2 ± 7.8 mmHg; TBT: 94.7 ± 5.1 mmHg) nor endothelium-dependent vasodilation differed between groups (CON: 10.4 ± 1.5 %; TBT: 12.5 ± 2.1 %). In the presence of L-NAME, vasodilation was reduced in both groups (CON: 5.7 ± 1.2 %; TBT: 4.0 ± 1.1 %) however, this reduction was greater in the TBT group. Perfusion with INDO (CON: 6.3 ± 1.6 %; TBT: 5.4 ± 1.1 %), CLOT (CON: 1.7 ± 0.4 %; TBT: 1.5 ± 0.5 %), L-NAME + INDO (CON: 7.5 ± 2.0 %; TBT: 5.4 ± 1.6 %) or L-NAME + INDO + CLOT (CON: 1.0 ± 0.4 %; TBT: 0.6 ± 0.2 %) reduced coronary relaxation, with no differences between groups in these protocols. TBT group exhibited a thinner tunica media compared with control group (CON: 29.3 ± 1.7 μ m, $n = 6$; TBT: 22.5 ± 0.8 μ m, $n = 6$). **Conclusion:** Exposure to a low dose of TBT prolongs diestrus/metestrus phase, reduces uterine weight, changes the contribution of the nitric oxide pathway to coronary vasodilation, and reduces tunica media thickness, suggesting endothelial and structural impairment that may contribute to cardiovascular risk.

Keywords: Coronary vascular bed; Ecotoxicology; Environmental pollution; Health risk; Organostannic compounds.

Financial support: FACITEC; FAPES.

GENETIC DETERMINANTS OF SODIUM AND POTASSIUM EXCRETION: FUNCTIONAL AND CARDIOVASCULAR IMPLICATIONS

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Introduction

High sodium intake, particularly in diets rich in ultra-processed foods, is a major risk factor for the premature onset of cardiovascular diseases (CVD). Understanding the factors that influence sodium and potassium consumption and excretion, as well as their relationship with CVD, is crucial for developing effective interventions for CVD prevention. Considering evidence for a genetic basis underlying these traits, the SalKidsGenES project aims to identify genes and genetic variants associated with urinary sodium and potassium excretion and with CVD. The primary objective is to screen for genes and genetic variants with the highest potential to alter the function of transcripts, proteins and pathways related to sodium and potassium balance. Expression quantitative trait loci (eQTL) analyses are essential to evaluate whether genetic variants influence gene expression levels and may modulate physiological responses to sodium and potassium. **Materials and Methods** Data from the Genome-wide association studies (GWAS) Catalog identified three variants linked to urinary sodium and potassium excretion: rs838133-A (FGF21), rs2472297-C (CYP1A1/CYP1A2), and rs11642015-C (FTO). These variants are also associated with cardiovascular traits in the UK Biobank population, the world's largest repository of genomic sequencing data and phenotypes. To explore their potential regulatory roles, in silico analyses were performed using GTEx Portal, HaploReg, RegulomeDB, and GeneCards **Results** No eQTLs were reported for *FGF21* or *CYP1A1*, while *CYP1A2* showed eQTLs in the left ventricle. *FTO* exhibited broader associations, including the aorta, atrium, ventricle, and blood, consistent with its known link to metabolic traits and CVD. The rs838133-A variant, although synonymous, shows enhancer-related epigenetic marks (H3K4me1_Enh, H3K27ac_Enh) in the right ventricle and alters TF motifs such as BDP1, Evi-1, GR, Nkx2, PTF1-beta, and SEF-1. It also presents eQTLs associated with the right atrium (*IZUMO1*, *MAMSTR*) and left ventricle (*FUT2*, *MAMSTR*). The rs2472297-C variant alters the binding motif of SP1 and is associated with eQTLs in the ascending aorta (*PPCDC*, *SCAMP5*, *RPP25*) and venous blood (*MAN2C1*, *SCAMP2*). The intronic variant rs11642015-C is linked to the binding motif of Pax-5. GR, SP1, Evi-1, and Nkx2 are the most likely TF to be involved in CVD, whereas the remaining factors show either no relevant evidence or only indirect associations in the literature. In summary, all SNPs are associated with specific TF and

influence chromatin accessibility, thereby reinforcing their potential functional impact on gene regulation and on processes related to sodium/potassium excretion and CVD. **Conclusion** These findings support the hypothesis that genetic variants associated with sodium and potassium excretion may exert their effects through gene regulation in cardiac tissues and metabolism, influencing chromatin accessibility and TF binding. The results contribute to understanding the molecular mechanisms linking electrolyte homeostasis to CVD, identifying *FTO* as a major candidate gene for a functional role in this process. Nevertheless, further studies are required to elucidate and validate the precise functional impact of these genes and variants.

Keywords: Sodium, potassium, cardiovascular risk, excretion, variants

Funding: FAPES

THEMATIC AXIS III

Pathways to Health Equity

INCLUSIVE GENOMIC

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Introduction: The completion of the Human Genome Project marked the transition to the so-called “*Genomic Era*”, a period characterized by the emergence of Next-Generation Sequencing (NGS). The advent of these technologies enabled the rapid and detailed identification of DNA variants, the alterations in the human genome. As a result, Genomics has been consolidated as one of the omics sciences dedicated to the comprehensive study of the genome, which is the complete set of the genes of an organism. When integrated with other omics, it broadens the understanding of genetic alterations associated with diseases, rare or common, and strengthens advances toward Precision Medicine. However, most genomic studies, such as Genome Wide Association Study (GWAS), are largely based on populations of European descent from the Global North, representing about 80% of the samples. Populations from developing countries, particularly admixed groups such as Brazil, remained invisible and underrepresented in the last decades. To reinforce the importance of genomic studies in multiethnic populations, especially those with lower socioeconomic income, a narrative review on inclusive genomics and its repercussions was conducted, aiming to identify and disseminate recent initiatives to mitigate this lack of representativeness and its negative impacts on equity. **Materials and Methods:** A narrative review, based on articles retrieved from the Medline/PubMed database, addressing European predominance in genomic repositories, exclusion of admixed populations, challenges, implications of low representativeness, and the benefits of inclusion for precision medicine. **Results:** Data were identified from the GWAS Catalog (founded in 2008), which compiles large-scale genomic studies, including the UK Biobank, which sequenced half a million British genomes. Additional data come from the *All of Us* program in the United States, launched in 2015, with the goal of sequencing 1 million genomes. These studies, with a predominance of European and North American individuals, are driving early diagnoses, the development of polygenic risk scores, and personalized therapies. Nevertheless, there are still gaps in the genomic representation of other populations in these studies. In this context, different initiatives have emerged, such as INMEGEN (20,000 Mexican genomes), the Genome Japan Project (100,000 Japanese genomes), and H3Africa (with a goal of 3 million African genomes). In Brazil, different national initiatives stand out, such as the pioneering sequencing of the SABE cohort, which identified 2 million novel variants and generated ABraOM (2017), the *Genomas Brasil* project (2020), *Genomas Raros* (2020), *Genoma SUS* (2024), with the goal of sequencing 25,000 genomes; and the *DNA do Brasil* project by the company gen-t (2019). Other important initiatives include REFARGEN, which develops pharmacogenomics research focusing on Brazilian diversity to identify therapeutic targets and adapt clinical protocols to the country’s genetic reality, and RENOMICA, specific to study the genomics applied to cardiovascular diseases. **Conclusion:** The expansion of sequencing projects in Brazil, as well as in other

admixed populations, is essential for mapping genetic variability and contributing to personalized medicine and public health, since the study of these populations has been particularly valuable for the identification of novel and causal variants. However, overlapping projects, concentration in the Rio-São Paulo axis, a regional approach instead of state ones, and the lack of strategic unified coordination represent significant challenges. The effective inclusion of all Brazilian regions, state and ethnic groups is a pathway for equity, crucial to ensuring a truly representative and effective precision medicine.

Keywords: Genomic; Precision Medicine; Underrepresentation; Admixture

Funding: FAPES

CHARACTERIZATION OF THE PROFILE OF WOMEN ATTENDING THE WOMEN'S HEALTH OUTPATIENT CLINIC OF A UNIVERSITY HOSPITAL

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Introduction: Gynecological conditions can compromise both the well-being and reproductive capacity of women. Among the most commonly reported symptoms, pelvic pain stands out as the most frequent and the one that most affects women's quality of life, being the main reason for seeking medical care. Understanding the most prevalent sociodemographic and clinical factors in a given population is essential for planning appropriate strategies to manage and mitigate these symptoms. The objective of this study was to characterize the profile of women attending the women's health outpatient clinic of a university hospital, testing the hypothesis that it is possible to describe the main sociodemographic and clinical characteristics of these women. **Materials and Methods:** This is a cross-sectional, descriptive study with a quantitative approach. The sample consisted of 242 women, aged between 18 and 55 years, who attended the women's health outpatient clinic of the Cassiano Antônio Moraes University Hospital (HUCAM) between February 8, 2024, and July 23, 2025. Data analysis was performed using SPSS software, version 27. The study was approved by the Research Ethics Committee (CEP HUCAM/UFES), under opinion No. 5.616.235 and CAAE No. 60880122.8.0000.5071. **Results:** Among the 242 women, most were aged between 41 and 45 years (41.6 ± 8.4), predominantly married (63.6%), with completed high school education (48.8%), family income between R\$ 2,005 and R\$ 8,640 (50.4%), and engaged in paid work (69.8%). Regarding clinical characteristics, 43 participants reported no symptoms, while 67 presented five or more gynecological symptoms. A total of 79 women (32.6%) had been experiencing gynecological symptoms for at least three years. Pelvic pain was reported by 144 participants (59.5%), and 95 (39.3%) reported regular use of analgesics. A confirmed diagnosis of endometriosis was present in 68 patients (28.09%), with pelvic magnetic resonance imaging (69.1%) and transvaginal ultrasound (25.0%) being the most frequently used diagnostic tests. The impact on personal and social life was significant: 118 women (48.8%) reported negative effects on social activities, 94 (38.8%) required time off work, 92 (38.0%) experienced sleep disturbances, and 86 (35.5%) reported impaired affective relationships. Physical examination revealed pain on palpation in 106 participants (43.8%), pain on bimanual examination in 90 (37.2%), and palpable masses in 18 (7.4%) women. The laboratory marker CA-125 had a mean value of $21.21 (\pm 32.14)$. The anthropometric profile indicated overweight, with a mean BMI of $28.5 \text{ kg/m}^2 (\pm 6.4)$, and only 106 (43.8%) women reported regular physical activity. **Conclusion:** The sociodemographic and clinical profile of the women studied reveals specific characteristics that may contribute to the early identification and clinical management of gynecological diseases. These findings reinforce the importance of a multidisciplinary and integrated assessment of social and clinical factors in women's healthcare, suggesting

that health education and early diagnosis strategies should be directed toward the most vulnerable groups.

Keywords: Pelvic Pain. Clinical Diagnosis. Pathological Conditions, Signs and Symptoms.

Funding: This study was supported by the Espírito Santo Research and Innovation Support Foundation (FAPES-ES), Notice No. 10/2024, PROCAP Master's 2025.

SOCIAL MEDIA AND PSYCHOSTIMULANTS USE AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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Introduction. The overexposure to technical images, as occurs on social media, has been leading to a ‘supersaturation of senses’, resulting in a state of dispersion and difficulties in maintaining concentration, with signs and symptoms similar to Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (Türcke, 2010; Xu et al., 2024; Ding et al., 2025). Many students have been using psychostimulants as an attempt to recover their distracted senses (Affonso et al., 2016; Cândido et al., 2019; Laet et al., 2022). Furthermore, the problematic use of social media has been compromising the students' health and teaching-learning process (Bueno, 2020; Fermann et al., 2021; Cerqueira et al., 2023). In this context, the objective of this study is to investigate the problematic use of social media and psychostimulants among university students in Espírito Santo. **Methods.** This study adopts an observational, analytic, cross-sectional quantitative design and has been conducted with undergraduate students from public higher education institutions in Espírito Santo, aged ≥ 18 years old. Data have been collected through a standardized, anonymous, self-administered questionnaire made available via Google Forms, assessing social media use based on the ‘Internet Addiction Test’ (Young, 1998), adapted for Brazil (Khoury et al., 2017; Brito et al., 2021), the use of psychostimulants, as well as sociodemographic and academic informations. The project was approved by the Research Ethics Committee/Plataforma Brasil (CAAE n. 80461624.3.0000.5060). For analysis, the chi-square test of independence ($p < 0.05$) was used to examine associations between sociodemographic variables, social media addiction, and psychostimulant use. **Results.** In a sample of 363 students, 55.9% exhibited problematic use of social media (33.9% moderate and 22.0% severe). Of the total students, 22.3% reported using psychostimulants, and among these, 33.3% did so without a prescription. Among those who self-medicated and experienced adverse reactions (tachycardia, anxiety, sleep disturbances, tremors, and loss of appetite), 61% did not discontinue use. The chi-square test of independence showed an association between self-diagnosis on social media and the use of these drugs ($X^2(1) = 6.742$; $p = 0.009$), and between self-diagnosis and self-medication ($X^2(1) = 5.503$; $p = 0.019$). Overall, 80% of these self-diagnoses were either not confirmed or were refuted after professional evaluation. There was also an association between self-diagnosis and problematic use of social media ($X^2(1) = 10.553$; $p = 0.001$). The test further indicated an association between academic failure ($X^2(1) = 11.821$; $p < 0.001$) and psychostimulant use. **Conclusion.** The study results suggest that there may be an indirect relationship between

problematic use of social media, psychostimulant use, and poor academic performance, with potential impacts on students' mental and physical health, highlighting it as a public health concern. However, further investigations are needed to evaluate the predictors of psychostimulant use among students.

Keywords: Social media; addiction; psychostimulants; self medication; teaching and learning.

Funding: Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Espírito Santo - FAPES (862/2023 - edital 28/2022) and Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico - CNPq

MICROBIOLOGICAL WATER QUALITY ASSESSMENT IN A RURAL SCHOOL IN CARIACICA (BRAZIL): AN EXTENSIONIST APPROACH UNDER THE ONE HEALTH CONCEPT

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Introduction: Water quality for human consumption and recreational use is a central concern for public health, as contaminants and pathogens can cause diseases such as cholera, dysentery, hepatitis, and typhoid fever. In 2022, the World Health Organization estimated that 1.7 billion people relied on drinking water sources contaminated with feces, resulting in up to 485,000 annual deaths, frequently associated with the presence of *Escherichia coli*. Detecting fecal coliforms in school and community environments is therefore relevant not only to identify immediate health risks but also as an educational tool. This project integrated teaching, extension, and research, aligned with the Brazilian Ministry of Education Resolution n° 7/2018, which established extension activities as a mandatory component of undergraduate curricula. The aim was to apply the One Health approach through the microbiological analysis of water quality in a rural school in Cariacica (ES), focusing on coliforms and *E. coli* detection, and to share results with the school community in an accessible and educational way. **Methods:** Eight water samples were collected at the Escola do Campo e Estação de Ciências em Tempo Integral Margarete Cruz Pereira and its surroundings: (i) tilapia fishpond; (ii) tucunaré fishpond; (iii) well supplying the school canteen; (iv) well supplying the classrooms; (v) water used for vegetable garden irrigation; (vi) stream near the school; (vii) stream near a water spout; and (viii) stream at the entrance of the Roda D'Água community. Samples were analyzed using the Most Probable Number (MPN) method for total and thermotolerant coliforms, followed by biochemical confirmation of *E. coli*. Results were presented to students in two age-adapted sessions: one for younger children (1st to 6th grade) and another for older students (7th to 9th grade). Educational activities included interactive explanations on fecal contamination, hygiene, and waterborne disease prevention. **Results:** All five water samples collected within the school area (fishponds, wells, irrigation) tested negative for fecal coliforms. In contrast, all stream samples tested positive: (i) near the school, 3 coliforms/100 mL; (ii) intermediate point, 43 coliforms/100 mL; and (iii) near the community entrance, 43 coliforms/100 mL. In all positive samples, *E. coli* was confirmed. During the feedback sessions, students reported using the stream for recreational bathing, highlighting the risk of direct exposure to contaminated water. Discussions revealed strong student engagement, with questions about waste disposal, sewage management, and protection against infections and parasitic diseases. Visual observation indicated that domestic sewage was being directly discharged into the stream, likely explaining the contamination. **Conclusion:** This project demonstrated the importance of integrating university and school communities, promoting both the generation of scientific data and critical awareness among students regarding water

quality, hygiene practices, and environmental preservation. The extension activity reinforced One Health principles by articulating science, education, and health promotion in a socially vulnerable rural territory.

Keywords: Water quality. *Escherichia coli*. Fecal coliforms. One Health. Health education.

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RECLASSIFICATION OF VARIANTS OF UNCERTAIN SIGNIFICANCE (VUS) IN RARE DISEASES: THE BRVUSES EXPERIENCE IN ESPÍRITO SANTO AND A CASE REPORT WITH A VARIANT IN THE LMNA GENE

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Keywords: reclassification; ACMG; BRVUSES; genetic diagnosis; laminopathies.

Introduction: Advances in genomic sequencing have expanded the identification of genetic variants, improving diagnostic accuracy for several diseases. The variants may be synonymous, missense, nonsense, frameshift, or intronic. According to the ACMG (American College of Medical Genetics and Genomics), variants are classified as pathogenic (P), likely pathogenic (LP), of uncertain significance (VUS), likely benign (LB), or benign (B). Clinical interpretation depends on the type of alteration, biochemical features, population frequency, prior association with similar phenotypes, computational or AI-based predictions, functional assays, and family segregation analysis. **Materials and Methods:** Observational study based on a systematic literature review, institutional experience, and case report (CAAE 89223825.7.0000.5071). **Results:** VUS remain one of the major challenges in clinical utility of genomics. A large-scale analysis involving 1.6 million individuals revealed that 41% of genetic tests reported VUS, mostly missense variants. In 2020, 16% of medical recommendations changed after variant reclassification, and 36.2% of patients had at least one reclassified variant. Although sequencing has improved diagnostic yield, 50% of rare disease cases remain without a definitive diagnosis, underscoring the need for systematic reanalysis of variants, particularly VUS. Another key limitation is the fact of 80% or more of international genomic databases are constituted by global north samples, which affects diagnostic precision in underrepresented groups such as the Brazilian population. National initiatives such as ABraOM, DNA do Brasil, and Genomas SUS aim to address this issue. In Espírito Santo, the BRVusES (Bank for Revaluation of Variants of Uncertain Significance in Espírito Santo) was established to document and longitudinally monitor VUS in patients attended at HUCAM University Hospital, enabling reclassification based on genotype-phenotype correlation. As an example, we report a 10-year-old patient with suspect of Emery-Dreifuss Muscular Dystrophy, presenting delay of motor development, generalized weakness, myopathic facies, and skeletal and cardiac abnormalities. Genetic testing identified a missense VUS in the LMNA gene (c.1354G>T, p.Val452Phe), encoding lamin A/C. Mutations in LMNA are implicated in approximately 6% of global cases of dilated cardiomyopathy, characterized by ventricular dysfunction and a high risk of heart failure. Although initially classified as a VUS, growing evidence supports reclassification to LP, including its occurrence in a critical protein domain, presence of multiple pathogenic missense variants in LMNA, deleterious computational predictions, and low population frequency. **Conclusion:** This case highlights the importance of

integrating clinical, molecular, and familial data for accurate interpretation of variants in laminopathies and other rare disorders. Continuous reanalysis of VUS through structured databases such as BRVusES is a pioneer initiative and essential for expanding diagnostic capacity, improving clinical management, and reducing uncertainty in patient follow-up. Moreover, this strategy contributes to reducing health inequities by promoting equitable access to precision healthcare for underrepresented populations.

Funding: Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa e Inovação do Espírito Santo

SIMVASTATIN NANOEMULSION: AN ORAL LIQUID FORMULATION TO IMPROVE ACCEPTABILITY AND ADHERENCE TO LIPID-LOWERING TREATMENT

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Introduction: Hyperlipidemia, a highly prevalent disorder in the Brazilian population, is a major etiological factor for cardiovascular diseases, which are among the leading causes of increased morbidity and mortality rates. Oral lipid-lowering agents are commercially available only in solid dosage forms, which may hinder treatment acceptability and adherence among patients with swallowing difficulties, such as the elderly, dysphagic patients, those using feeding tubes, and/or pediatric patients. The inadequacy of solid dosage forms becomes an even greater barrier to therapeutic continuity, especially in the treatment of chronic diseases, highlighting the importance of developing tools to make treatment more accessible to these populations. By addressing therapeutic gaps not covered by the pharmaceutical industry, compounding pharmacies can contribute to meeting this demand. This study, therefore, aimed to develop, characterize, and evaluate the stability of an oral nanoemulsion of simvastatin, a novel and innovative formulation. **Methods:** Simvastatin nanoemulsions (5 mg/mL), composed of Medium-Chain Triglycerides as solubilizer and a mixture of Span® 80 and Tween® 80 as emulsifiers, were produced using a high-energy homogenization method. The simvastatin nanoemulsions were evaluated for physicochemical parameters over 90 days of storage at room temperature (25 to 30°C) and at refrigerated temperatures (2 to 8°C). In addition, a High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) analytical method was adapted for the quantification of simvastatin in the nanoemulsions. Statistical analysis was performed using two-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), followed by Tukey's test. **Results:** Oil-in-water (O/W) nanoemulsions with a liquid and homogeneous appearance were obtained. In terms of palatability, the emulsions exhibited a sweet and mentholated flavor due to the selected flavoring agent. The formulations' observed characteristics indicate a vehicle favorable to dose uniformity and ease of administration. Throughout the evaluation period, the physical stability of the emulsion system was maintained, with no physical signs of degradation or precipitation. The nanoemulsions remained stable in terms of appearance, physicochemical parameters, and simvastatin content for 14 days when stored at room temperature and for 90 days under refrigeration. **Conclusion:** This information provides important technical and scientific support for the pharmaceutical production sector for beyond-use date definition. Thus, the results indicate the viability of the developed formulation as a pharmaceutical alternative to meet specific needs not covered by the pharmaceutical industry. In this way, the oral simvastatin nanoemulsion can provide access to safe and effective pharmacotherapy, increase adherence to lipid-lowering treatment, and consequently reduce associated cardiovascular risk.

Keywords: Hyperlipidemia; Oral liquid formulations; Pharmaceutical compounding; Non-sterile preparations; Pharmacotherapy.

Financial support: Espírito Santo Research and Innovation Foundation (FAPES, Brazil)

THEMATIC AXIS IV

Integrating Physiology, Toxicology
and Therapeutics in Cardiorespiratory disease

EXPERIMENTAL CONDITIONS SHAPE BEHAVIORAL AND AUTONOMIC OUTCOMES OF ACUTE CHLORPYRIFOS EXPOSURE IN RATS

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Introduction: Organophosphates (OPs) are a class toxicant widely used worldwide. Evidence suggests that different exposure patterns to OP compounds induce cardiovascular, respiratory, behavioral, cognitive, and motor impairment, as well as oxidative/nitrosative and inflammatory responses. In previous studies, we observed that repeated intermittent intoxication at sub-toxic doses of the OP chlorpyrifos (CPF) led to impaired autonomic response in the contextual fear conditioning (CFC) test without affecting the behavioral response, while a single dose of CPF intoxication caused impaired behavioral response in the CFC. However, we did not evaluate whether acute CPF poisoning could affect the autonomic response in the CFC. Therefore, we investigated the behavioral, autonomic, and biochemical effects of acute exposure to CPF in rats subjected to the CFC. **Methods:** For this purpose, adult Wistar rats were subjected to the CFC test (Committee for the Ethical Use of Animals in Scientific Research n°04/2022). The CFC was divided into three sessions named conditioning, extinction, and extinction recall. In the conditioning session, each animal was habituated for 2 minutes inside the CFC box and then subjected to three foot shocks (0.7 mA/3 s at a randomized interval of 30-60 s). After the last shock, the animal remained inside the box for an additional 1 minute, totaling 5 minutes. In the extinction session, each rat was placed in the box for a period of 21 minutes without shock delivery to evaluate fear expression and for extinction training. In the extinction recall session, again without shock delivery, each rat was re-exposed to the box for 5 minutes to evaluate fear extinction. Exposure to CPF (20 mg/kg, i.p.) always occurred after conditioning. Autonomic (mean arterial pressure, MAP, and heart rate, HR) and behavioral (freezing) parameters were recorded in the extinction and extinction recall sessions. Two different protocols were performed. In Protocol 1, femoral artery cannulation surgery under ketamine/xylazine (80/10 mg/kg) anesthesia was performed 24 h after conditioning and the effect of CPF on the CFC was evaluated 48 h after intoxication. In Protocol 2, cannulation surgery was performed 24 h before conditioning and the effect of CPF on the CFC was evaluated 24 h after intoxication. At the end of the experiments, the animals were euthanized to collect brainstem and hippocampus samples for measurement of acetylcholinesterase (AChE) activity. **Results:** In protocol 1, in which rats underwent surgery 24 h after conditioning and were re-exposed to the context 48 h after intoxication, acute CPF poisoning at a dose of 20 mg/kg changed the pressor and tachycardic responses of intoxicated animals but did not affect the freezing behavioral response. Conversely, in protocol 2, acute CPF intoxication impaired extinction and increased fear expression 24 h after intoxication without affecting MAP and HR in animals previously subjected to femoral artery

cannulation surgery. In both protocols, CPF inhibited AChE in the hippocampus and brainstem 48 h and 72 h after intoxication. **Conclusion:** Acute CPF poisoning in rats impairs behavioral and cardiovascular responses in CFC test, and the order of the protocol procedures involving surgery plus anesthesia may influence the outcomes.

Keywords: Chlorpyrifos; Organophosphate; Contextual fear conditioning; Behavior; Cardiovascular.

Financial support: Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa e Inovação do Espírito Santo (FAPES, Grant Codes: 2022- 78KWB; 749/2024), CAPES (Grant codes 01); CNPq/FAPES 2025-H5S1W; CNPq/MCTI/FNDCT N° 44/2024. GGN, LJC and VSM, were recipients of Capes Foundation Scholarship (Grant Code 01).

SLEEP IN MENOPAUSAL WOMEN: RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN METABOLISM AND SLEEP DISORDERS

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Introduction: During menopause, several physiological changes occur that affect not only reproductive functions but also aspects such as mood, cognition, behavior, memory, and sleep. Sleep disorders, especially obstructive sleep apnea (OSA), are associated with physiological imbalances that increase the risk of chronic diseases, such as cardiovascular disease. In menopausal women, these risks can be intensified. Therefore, this study aimed to assess the sleep quality of menopausal women using oximetry and actigraphy, correlating clinical parameters with the presence of OSA, in order to investigate whether women with cardiometabolic disorders in this period are more likely to develop OSA.

Material and methods: This is a cross-sectional, descriptive study, registered under CEP n°. 6100927.250115.180645, and conducted in the gynecology department of HUCAM/UFES-Maruípe. Women aged 45 to 65 years, not using hormone therapy and with vasomotor symptoms and/or cardiometabolic alterations, were included. Each participant underwent a medical history and sleep assessment using type IV polysomnography, recording oximetry, oxygen desaturation index (ODI), and nocturnal heart rate (HR) for diagnostic impression of OSA. The examination was performed with a wireless oximeter linked to a smartphone application, categorizing into absence of OSA, mild sleep apnea (ODI 5 to 15 ev/h), moderate sleep apnea (ODI 5 to 30 ev/h), and severe sleep apnea (ODI \geq 30 ev/h). Statistical analysis was performed using R software (version 4.5.1) with RStudio environment (version 2025.09.1). The normality of the variables was tested using the Shapiro-Wilk test. As the assumptions for normal distribution were not met, Spearman's correlation (ρ) was used to verify the relationship between body mass index (BMI) and ODI. The significance level adopted was $p < 0.05$, with a 95% CI. **Results:** 44 women participated, with an average age of 55 ± 5 years. The cardiometabolic assessment revealed an average BMI of 29.69 ± 6.40 kg/m², average SBP was 129 ± 17 mmHg and average DBP was 79 ± 9 mmHg. Regarding sleep variables, an average ODI of 7.15 ± 8.39 ev/h, average SpO₂ of $96 \pm 1.94\%$, average nocturnal HR of 65 ± 8 bpm and average sleep time of 375.70 ± 77.5 minutes were observed. 15 cases of mild OSA, 3 moderate and 1 severe were identified. There was no significant correlation between MAP and ODI, nor between BMI and MAP ($\rho = 0.031$; $p = 0.841$; $\rho = 0.288$; $p = 0.057$). However, a moderate positive correlation was observed between BMI and ODI ($\rho = 0.56$; $p < 0.001$). **Conclusion:** Although the variables PA-ODI and BMI-PA did not show a significant association, a correlation was observed between BMI and ODI, suggesting that common physiological changes during menopause, such as weight gain, are somehow associated with increased ODI. This may influence the development of chronic diseases and worsen the quality of life of these women. These findings reinforce

the importance of cardiometabolic and sleep health monitoring in women during this period, aiming to prevent chronic complications and improve quality of life.

Keywords : Sleep; menopause; OSA; cardiometabolic risk;

Financial support: UFES, CAPES, FAPES, LOCE, EPIGENE, HUCAM.

ELLAGIC ACID SUPPLEMENTATION PRESERVES MYOCARDIAL FUNCTION IN MERCURY-EXPOSED RATS

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Introduction: Mercury is a toxic metal to which the population may be exposed both in occupational settings and because of environmental disasters. Evidence indicates that chronic mercury exposure can significantly impair cardiac function. In this context, the search for therapeutic alternatives using bioactive compounds, such as ellagic acid (EA), has received growing attention due to its protective effects on the cardiovascular system. This polyphenol is present in fruits, vegetables, and nuts, and acts as a phytochelator and protector against the toxicity of metals, metalloids, and metallic ions. Therefore, the present study investigated whether oral supplementation with EA could attenuate the effects of mercury (Hg) exposure on the mechanics of rat cardiac muscle. **Material and Methods:** Male Wistar rats (8 weeks old) were randomly assigned to 3 groups: Ct (n=6, intramuscular NaCl 0.9% and gavage with NaOH 0.1M), Hg (n=5, HgCl₂ 4.6 µg/kg loading dose and 0.07 µg/kg/day and gavage with NaOH 0.1M), and Hg+EA (n=4, HgCl₂ + EA 30 mg/kg/day via gavage) for 30 days. At the end of the treatment, the animals were anesthetized with ketamine and xylazine i.p., the heart was excised, and the papillary muscle was isolated and mounted in an organ bath aerated with carbogenic mixture, electrically stimulated at 12 V with a frequency of 0.5 Hz. Developed force (g/mg of muscle mass) was assessed at optimal stretch (L_{max}) and under increasing concentrations of CaCl₂ (0.62; 1.25; 2.75; and 3.25 mM). The protocols were approved by CEUA/UFES (19/2024). **Results:** Exposure to HgCl₂ reduced papillary muscle contractile force, whereas cotreatment with EA prevented this reduction (Ct: 0.292 ± 0.035 vs Hg: 0.194 ± 0.016 g/mg; p=0.02, Hg vs Hg+EA: 0.34 ± 0.024 g/mg; p=0.004, one-way ANOVA). The contractile response to increasing calcium concentrations (Ct [CaCl₂]: 1.25 mM: 0.309 ± 0.025; 2.5 mM: 0.413 ± 0.041; 3.75 mM: 0.413 ± 0.035 g/mg) was also reduced in the Hg group ([CaCl₂]: 1.25 mM: 0.122 ± 0.049; 2.5 mM: 0.181 ± 0.056; 3.75 mM: 0.185 ± 0.055 g/mg; p=0.01 vs Ct) and preserved in the Hg+EA group ([CaCl₂]: 1.25 mM: 0.231 ± 0.092; 2.5 mM: 0.278 ± 0.088; 3.75 mM: 0.363 ± 0.092 g/mg; p=0.08 vs Ct), starting at 1.25 mM CaCl₂. **Conclusion:** Oral supplementation with ellagic acid exerted a protective role on the contractile capacity and myocardial calcium responsiveness of rats chronically exposed to mercury.

Keywords: Contractility, Papillary muscle, Supplementation

Financial support: Fapes and CNPq.

ELLAGIC ACID MITIGATES IRON OVERLOAD-INDUCED VASCULOPATHY BY MODULATING THE COX-2 PATHWAY AND PROMOTING AN ANTI-INFLAMMATORY MACROPHAGE PHENOTYPE.

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Introduction: Iron overload (IO) is a well-established cause of systemic damage, including the cardiovascular system. Recently, it has been strongly associated with the development of vasculopathy. Given that ellagic acid (EA) has antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, we hypothesized it could mitigate the vascular inflammation associated with IO-induced vasculopathy. Therefore, this study aimed to investigate whether EA reduces the inflammatory process in a rodent model of chronic IO. **Materials and Methods:** Wistar rats (~200g) were randomly assigned to three groups: controls (Ct, vehicle), iron overload (Fe, 100 mg/kg/day, i.p.), and IO treated with EA (FeEA). After a 4-week treatment period, vascular reactivity was evaluated in isolated aortic rings by constructing cumulative concentration–response curves to phenylephrine with and without cyclooxygenase (COX) pathway inhibitors. Additionally, RT-PCR was performed on aortic tissue to assess gene expression. All data were analyzed using two-way ANOVA with Fisher's post-hoc test, and a P-value <0.05 was considered significant. All animal procedures were approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee on Animal Use (CEUA-UFES 18/2023). **Results:** The Fe group exhibited a significant increase in vasoconstriction to phenylephrine; however, this effect was partially attenuated by EA treatment (Ct: 71.1±7.7; Fe: 121.4±3.8; FeEA: 106.5±6.0). Incubation with the non-selective COX inhibitor indomethacin reduced the vascular response in the Fe group but had no effect on the Ct and FeEA groups (Ct: 66.2±7.0; Ct/INDO: 60.5±6.1; Fe: 119.9±3.8; Fe/INDO: 96.1±7.4; FeEA: 109.4±5.97; FeEA/INDO: 110.2±4). Similarly, the selective COX-2 inhibitor NS-398 also reduced vasoconstriction of Fe aortas, while paradoxically increased this response in the FeEA group (Ct: 69.7±7.9; Ct NS: 73.59±7.4; Fe: 99.8±4.8; Fe NS: 79.38±6; FeEA: 68.54±6.1; FeEA NS: 79.91±9). No changes were observed following incubation with the TP receptor antagonist SQ 29,548, but the EP1 receptor antagonist SC 19,220 reduced vascular reactivity in the Fe group with no effect in the FeEA group (Ct: 71.2±6.2; Ct SC: 71.54±7.4; Fe: 97.9±4.2; Fe SC: 81.9±5.2; FeEA: 74.35±7.7; FeEA SC: 76.2±5.7). Furthermore, EA treatment increased prostacyclin levels in the FeEA group. At the molecular level, The Fe group showed increased mRNA expression of COX-2 and macrophage activation markers, consistent with a pro-inflammatory M1 phenotype polarization. In contrast, the FeEA group exhibited increased expression of genes indicative of an anti-inflammatory M2 macrophage phenotype. **Conclusion:** Ellagic acid treatment attenuated the hyper-vasoconstrictive response induced by chronic IO. This protective effect was associated with the modulation of the COX-2 pathway, increase in prostacyclin levels, and a favorable shift in macrophage polarization toward an anti-inflammatory M2 phenotype. These findings suggest that ellagic acid could serve as a valuable therapeutic agent for mitigating IO-induced vasculopathy.

Keywords: Iron overload; Vasculopathy; Ellagic acid.

Funding: CAPES; CNPq; FAPES.

ELLAGIC ACID MODULATES OXIDATIVE STRESS–MEDIATED VASCULAR DYSFUNCTION IN MERCURY-EXPOSED RATS

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Introduction: Exposure to mercury chloride (HgCl₂), a highly toxic environmental pollutant, occurs mainly through contaminated fish, dental amalgam vapors, and occupational mining. Such exposure has been associated with oxidative stress, endothelial dysfunction, and increased cardiovascular risk. Natural bioactive compounds have shown promise in mitigating these deleterious effects. Ellagic acid (EA), a polyphenol found in fruits and seeds, exhibits antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties with potential to attenuate HgCl₂-induced damage. Therefore, this study evaluated the effects of EA on vascular reactivity alterations induced by HgCl₂ in rat thoracic aorta rings, using phenylephrine (PE)-induced contractile responses and pharmacological interventions to elucidate the underlying physiological mechanisms.

Material and Methods: Male Wistar rats (8 weeks old) were randomly assigned to four groups: Control (CT); Mercury (HG, HgCl₂ loading dose 4.6 µg/kg followed by 0.07 µg/kg/day, intramuscular injection); Ellagic acid (EA, 30 mg/kg/day by gavage); and Mercury + Ellagic acid (HGEA, HgCl₂ + EA). Vehicles were administered to groups not receiving HgCl₂ or EA (0.9%NaCl i.m. or NaOH plus carboxymethylcellulose by gavage, respectively). After 30 days of treatment, animals were anesthetized with ketamine/xylazine (i.p.). The thoracic aorta was isolated, perivascular adipose tissue removed, cut into rings and mounted in organ baths to assess changes in arterial wall tension induced by cumulative concentrations of the α₁-adrenergic agonist phenylephrine (N=13–16). All procedures were approved by CEUA/UFES (Protocol No.19/2024). Data are expressed as mean ± SEM and were analyzed by two-way ANOVA followed by Tukey or Fisher's post-test (p<0.05).

Results: The HG group exhibited an augmented vasoconstrictor response to phenylephrine compared with control, while EA treatment prevented this effect and maintained values similar to control (E_{max}: CT: 81.0±1.6%; HG: 104.7±3.6%; HGEA: 78.5±2.3%). The EA group did not differ from control in any tested condition (p>0.05). Indomethacin reduced the vasoconstriction response only in the HG group (E_{max}: CT: 83.5±2.8%; HG: 56.6±3.6%; HGEA: 85.8±2.7%), suggesting that EA treatment prevented the involvement of cyclooxygenase-derived products in mercury-induced augmented vasoconstriction. Catalase incubation did not change reactivity vascular to phenylephrine in HG (98.3±5.1%), but markedly increased in HGEA (109.3±4.4%), indicating that EA attenuated contractility at least in part via modulation of hydrogen peroxide. Tempol incubation reduced vasoconstriction only in HG (E_{max} CT: 86.3±3.1%; HG: 69.7±3.1%; HGEA: 74.6±4.0%), pointing to superoxide anion as a mediator of mercury-induced hypercontractility, which was prevented by EA treatment. L-NAME increased vasoconstriction in all groups (CT: 157.3±4.6%; HG: 166.4±4.1%; HGEA: 164.8±5.3%), with no significant differences among them. In endothelium-denuded rings

(E⁻), vasoconstriction was markedly elevated in all groups. Analysis of the percentage difference in area under the curve (dAUC%) revealed a reduction in HG (CT: 417.7 ± 59.1; HG: 279.7 ± 64.9; HGEA: 457.3 ± 67.9), consistent with endothelial dysfunction that was prevented by EA treatment.

Conclusion: HgCl₂ induced vascular dysfunction in rat aortic rings, characterized by increased contractility mediated by oxidative stress, cyclooxygenase-derived factors and endothelial impairment. EA prevented these alterations, modulating contractility in part via hydrogen peroxide and preserving endothelial function, thereby reinforcing its potential as a protective agent against the cardiovascular effects of mercury exposure.

Keywords: Mercury; Ellagic acid; Vascular Reactivity; Oxidative Stress; Endothelial dysfunction.

Financial support: FAPES, CAPES, CNPq.

MITOCHONDRIAL CELL-FREE DNA AS A POSSIBLE BIOMARKER IN PATIENTS WITH SICKLE CELL ANEMIA ASSOCIATED WITH IRON OVERLOAD

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Introduction: Chronic iron overload, a frequent complication of regular transfusions in patients with sickle cell anemia, promotes oxidative stress and ferroptotic cell death. This process is characterized by plasma membrane rupture and loss of mitochondrial integrity, which could lead to the release of DNA fragments into the circulation (cell-free DNA, cfDNA). The quantification of these molecules—particularly those from mitochondrial origin (mt-cfDNA)—is emerging as a promising diagnostic approach, with the potential to reflect cellular injury and disease progression in a minimally invasive manner. **Objective:** This study aimed to evaluate the levels of circulating cfDNA from both nuclear (n-cfDNA) and mitochondrial (mt-cfDNA) origins in patients with sickle cell anemia and iron overload (IO), compared with individuals without these conditions. **Methods:** This cross-sectional study was conducted between April 2023 and June 2024 at the Hematology and Hemotherapy Center of Espírito Santo (HEMOES, Vitória, Brazil) (CAAE: 26210619.3.0000.5060). Eligible participants included those with diagnosed sickle cell anemia and a documented history of IO, defined by (1) a serum ferritin level >1000 ng/mL and a transferrin saturation index >45%, or (2) a history of at least two transfusions in the previous 6 months. The control group comprised healthy blood donors without hematologic disorders or alterations in iron status. Blood was collected after signing the informed consent form, for laboratory and cf-DNA analysis. DNA was extracted and purified using the *Qiagen* kit and cfDNA was quantified by real-time quantitative polymerase chain reaction (rtPCR), using primers for non-coding sequences specific for nuclear and mitochondrial genomes. Additional clinical and laboratory data were retrieved from medical records. Statistical analysis included tests for normality, followed by appropriate comparisons with significance defined as $p < 0.05$. **Results:** A total of 36 patients with sickle cell anemia with IO and 82 controls were included. Regarding iron parameters, the sickle cell group presented a median ferritin of 2717 ± 4105 ng/mL (95% CI: 1386–4047), serum iron 168 ± 84 µg/dL (95% CI: 140–195), and transferrin saturation index $56.9 \pm 23\%$ (95% CI: 49–64); and healthy individuals had ferritin 150 ± 128 ng/mL (95% CI: 126–175), serum iron 108 ± 41 µg/dL (95% CI: 100–116), and transferrin saturation $34.5 \pm 12\%$ (95% CI: 32–36). Laboratory tests of individuals with sickle cell anemia are compatible with the criteria adopted for IO. Patients with sickle cell anemia and IO exhibited significantly higher levels of mt-cfDNA compared to controls ($p = 0.0177$), whereas n-cfDNA showed no difference between groups ($p = 0.356$). **Conclusion:** To our knowledge, this is the first study to demonstrate

that iron overload in patients with sickle cell anemia is associated with elevated circulating mt-cfDNA. This increase may reflect, at least in part, a significant degree of ferroptosis-driven mitochondrial damage. These preliminary findings should support further investigations on the potential correlations between mt-cfDNA and clinically relevant factors such as age, transfusion history, comorbidities (e.g., hypertension, insulin resistance), and typical outcomes (e.g., including vaso-occlusive crises and hospitalizations).

Keywords: Iron; DNA fragmentation; mitochondria; oxidative stress.

Funding: FAPES and CAPES.

COMPARISON BETWEEN THE BRAIN ACTIVITIES OF THE ENZYMES ACETYLCHOLINESTERASE AND BUTYRYLCHOLINESTERASE IN NORMOTENSIVE AND HYPERTENSIVE RATS

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Introduction: Systemic arterial hypertension (SAH) is a chronic, silent, slowly progressive disease that is a significant risk factor for cardiovascular disease (CVD). The pathophysiology of this disease involves genetic, environmental, neural, chemical, hormonal, vascular, and inflammatory factors that trigger increased blood pressure (BP). Among these factors, autonomic nervous system (ANS) imbalance plays a primary role, with hyperstimulation of the sympathetic nervous system (SNS) and hypostimulation of the parasympathetic nervous system (PNS). Acetylcholine (ACh), the main neurotransmitter of the ANS, modulates this system through specific cholinergic pathways regulated by cholinesterases (ChEs): acetylcholinesterase (AChE) and butyrylcholinesterase (BChE). Changes in the activity of these enzymes have been related to hypertension, so the objective of this study was to evaluate and compare the brain enzymatic activity of ChEs in hypertensive and normotensive rats. **Material and methods:** ChE activity was evaluated by the Ellman method in the trunk and hippocampus of 10-12-week-old adult male spontaneously hypertensive rats (SHR; n=11); Wistar Kyoto rats (WKY; n=10); and Wistar rats (W; n=10). For statistical analysis of AChE and BChE activity differences between strains, a one-way ANOVA was performed, with the enzyme activity as the dependent variable, and Tukey's post-hoc test was performed when there was statistical significance. The data were analyzed using GraphPad Prism software and represented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD), with the significance level considered $p \leq 0.05$. This work was approved by the Animal Use Ethics Committee (CEUA Approval Numbers 05/2023). **Results:** Comparison of AChE enzyme activity in the trunk between the WKY, W, and SHR strains revealed no statistically significant difference ($F(2,28) = 1.424$; $p > 0.05$). In contrast, activity in the hippocampus differed significantly among the strains ($F(2,28) = 7.957$; $p < 0.01$). WKY rats showed significantly higher AChE activity in the hippocampus compared to both W rats and SHR ($p < 0.01$). **Conclusion:** The reduced AChE activity observed in the hippocampus suggests a compensatory mechanism for cognitive deficits and autonomic dysfunction. These findings reinforce the involvement of the cholinergic system in hypertension and highlight ChEs as potential therapeutic targets, paving the way for future investigations aimed at developing therapeutic strategies focused on these enzymes, contributing to improving disease control and enhancing quality of life of the affected population.

Keywords: Hypertension; Cerebral Acetylcholinesterase; Cerebral Butyrylcholinesterase; Spontaneously Hypertensive Rats.

Financial support: Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa e Inovação do Espírito Santo (FAPES, Grant Codes: 2022- 78KWB; 749/2024), CAPES (Grant codes 01); CNPq/FAPES 2025-H5S1W; CNPq/MCTI/FNDCT N° 44/2024.

BIOMECHANICAL ASSESSMENT OF DECELLULARIZED PORCINE AORTIC TISSUES: IMPLICATIONS FOR VALVE REPLACEMENT

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Introduction: Heart valve diseases impose a major clinical burden, since the limited regenerative capacity of native valves often necessitates transplantation as the only viable therapeutic option. However, allograft rejection remains a significant complication. Tissue bioengineering, particularly decellularization, offers a promising strategy by substantially reducing immunogenicity. Despite the decrease in rejection episodes, complications associated with the poor biomechanical performance of decellularized matrices are still reported. Thus, this study aimed to investigate the effects of porcine ascending aorta and aortic valve leaflet decellularization on their mechanical properties, which may underlie such complications. **Methods:** Segments of the ascending aorta and aortic valve leaflets were obtained from male pigs following ethical approval (CEUA-UFES, #05/2021). Tissues were distributed into two groups: Native (NAT) or Decellularized (DEC). In decellularization, cells are removed from the tissue using detergents (SDS/Triton) and an enzymatic process with Benzonase to degrade and eliminate residual nucleic acids, but preserving the extracellular matrix. Samples were cut into 4 mm × 2 mm segments and mounted in an organ bath filled with phosphate-buffered solution at room temperature. The setup involved a micromanipulator coupled with a force transducer. Leaflets were positioned in both circumferential and radial orientations to account for the natural fiber arrangement. Three mechanical performance tests were conducted: 1) Gradual stretch curve (0.3 mm steps until 2.7 mm) to evaluate gradual tensile strength; 2) Sudden submaximal stretching (2 mm) to evaluate tension decay during 30 minutes (viscoelasticity); and 3) Final length after removal from the organ bath, to evaluate permanent deformation (fracture deformation). Data were analyzed using unpaired Student's t-test, two-way ANOVA, followed by Fisher's post hoc test ($p < 0.05$). **Results:** Aortas from the DEC group showed a slight impairment in the gradual tensile test (NAT: 15.12 ± 0.46 vs. DEC: 13.41 ± 1.3 g/mm). However, the time-dependent tension decay under submaximal stretching (NAT: -5.19 ± 0.65 vs. DEC: -4.37 ± 0.72 %), and fracture deformation (NAT: 4.32 ± 0.07 vs. DEC: 4.03 ± 0.02 mm) remained unchanged. In contrast, valve leaflets from the DEC group, regardless of orientation, preserved both the stretch curve (circumferential NAT: 11.40 ± 1.08 vs. DEC: 10.61 ± 3.7 g/mm; radial NAT: 10.97 ± 1.7 vs. DEC: 12.62 ± 2.7 g/mm) and time-dependent tension decay (circumferential NAT: -28.53 ± 8.4 vs. DEC: -23.29 ± 12 %; radial NAT: -24.97 ± 5.1 vs. DEC: -24.82 ± 17 %). Notably, the DEC leaflets exhibited extended final lengths (circumferential NAT: 5.74 ± 0.30 vs. DEC: 7.53 ± 0.6 ; radial NAT: 6.26 ± 0.29 vs. DES: 7.35 ± 0.2), suggesting some degree of permanent deformation. **Conclusion:** Decellularization leads to discrete

changes in specific mechanical properties of the porcine ascending aorta and aortic valve leaflets, which may be associated with elastin loss during the cell removal process, thus affecting the tissue's elasticity and distension capacity. Future studies are crucial to investigate strategies, such as matrix stabilization techniques and re-cellularization, to mitigate these consequences and effectively recover the mechanical characteristics of native tissues for clinical applications.

Keywords: Tissue-engineered heart valve; decellularization; impaired valve compliance; mechanical properties.

Funding: FAPES, RENORBIO.

EFFECTS OF PERIODONTITIS ON BAROREFLEX FUNCTION OF HYPERTENSIVE RATS

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Introduction: Systemic arterial hypertension is a condition that affects a large part of the world's population and is a risk factor for cardiovascular events. Periodontal disease, like hypertension, is a highly prevalent disease, being the sixth most common human disease. Both conditions have been linked to complications from cardiovascular outcomes, with extreme relevance and impact on public health. Baroreceptors located in the aortic arch and carotid sinus are responsible for reflex control of blood pressure. Although it has already been clarified that their function is affected in patients with hypertension, with lower sensitivity to blood pressure changes, it is still necessary to elucidate whether periodontitis, when added to hypertension, has effects on baroreflex control. **Materials and Methods:** The study was conducted on male (2-month-old) Spontaneously Hypertensive Rats (SHR) divided into two experimental groups: SHR control animals, which did not undergo any clinical intervention, and SHR periodontitis animals, which underwent periodontitis induction by inserting a ligature between their two lower molars (CEUA-UFES number 22/2024). After 4 weeks, the ligature was removed, and periodontitis was confirmed by the presence of bacterial plaque and bleeding during its removal. The femoral vein and artery were catheterized, and the cannulas were exteriorized on the animal's back. After recovering (24-hour), the animals were connected to hemodynamic measurement equipment (BIOPAC), to systolic (SAP), diastolic (DAP) and mean (MAP) blood pressure, as well as heart rate (HR) quantification. Baroreflex control of blood pressure was evaluated in conscious animals by measuring reflex tachycardia and bradycardia in response to changes in blood pressure following phenylephrine (0.2-12.8 µg/Kg) and sodium nitroprusside (0.4-25.6 µg/Kg) injections. Results are expressed as mean ± SEM. *p<0.05. **Results:** SAP (199.1 ± 17.10 and 196.0 ± 17.10 mmHg), DAP (135.9 ± 11.40 and 143.3 ± 11.40 mmHg), MAP (162.6 ± 12.16 and 168.3 ± 12.16 mmHg), and HR (341.3 ± 12.22 and 325.0 ± 12.22 bpm) were not statistically different between the control and periodontitis groups. Dose response curves phenylephrine and sodium nitroprusside-induced changes in HR were also similar between groups. Baroreflex sensitivity, as quantified by $\Delta FC/\Delta PAM$, from both phenylephrine injections (-0.2400 ± 0.07603 and -0.2633 ± 0.07603 , $p>0.05$) and sodium nitroprusside injections (-2.0120 ± 0.4302 and -1.511 ± 0.4302) were not statistically different between the groups. **Conclusion:** The presented results show that periodontitis, when associated with hypertension, did not affect the baroreflex control of blood pressure in SHR animals. Despite the absence of statistical differences, the obtained data in this

study provides important evidence on the repercussion of periodontitis on the hemodynamics and baroreflex responses, indicating the need to expand comparative studies between more experimental groups.

Keywords: Arterial hypertension. Periodontitis. Baroreflex.

Financial Support: CNPq e FAPES.

CARDIAC MITOCHONDRIAL DYSFUNCTION MEDIATED BY RAAS: MECHANISMS AND THERAPEUTIC PERSPECTIVES

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ABSTRACT: Chronic activation of renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS) promotes oxidative stress and mitochondrial dysfunction in the heart, contributing to hypertrophy, apoptosis, and progression of cardiovascular disease (CVD). Emerging therapies, including mitochondrial antioxidants, SGLT2 inhibitors, metformin, statins, and mitochondrial transplantation, have shown cardioprotective potential, though robust clinical validation remains necessary to confirm their therapeutic potential.

INTRODUCTION: Mitochondria play a central role to cardiac physiology by regulating energy metabolism, redox signaling, apoptosis, and inflammatory pathways. Mitochondrial dysfunction is associated with both acute and chronic conditions, such as myocardial infarction and heart failure, which together represent leading causes of global morbidity and mortality among middle-aged and older adults. Chronic activation of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS) enhances reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation and disrupts mitochondrial integrity, exacerbating oxidative stress. This study investigated the interplay between RAAS activation and cardiac mitochondrial dysfunction, under the hypothesis that sustained RAAS activity contributes to mitochondrial dysfunction and accelerates the progression of cardiovascular disease (CVD).

METHODOLOGY: This integrative review analyzed studies on RAAS dysregulation and its relationship with mitochondrial dysfunction, ROS, and CVD, as well as emerging therapeutic strategies. Literature searches were conducted in PubMed, Cochrane Library, Embase, Scopus, and Web of Science (2019–2025) using the Boolean operator AND with the descriptors: “renin angiotensin system”, “cardiovascular physiological phenomena”, “myocardial infarction”, and “oxidative stress”. A total of 2,331 publications were identified, of which 97 were preselected. After exclusions due to thematic inadequacy, 39 articles met the eligibility criteria and were included in the review. These were analyzed qualitatively and quantitatively and organized into thematic categories, as illustrated in Figure 1. **RESULTS:** The RAAS is involved in essential physiological processes that maintain blood flow homeostasis. However, its chronic activation induces cardiac hypertrophy and oxidative stress. In mitochondria, angiotensin II, the main effector of the system, promotes organelle dysfunction and excessive ROS production. Mitochondria express angiotensin II receptors with distinct functions: activation of type 2 receptor (AT2R) enhances nitric oxide production, reduces oxygen consumption and ROS generation, and confers protective effects under stress, whereas overstimulation of type 1 receptor (AT1R) promotes mitochondrial permeability transition pore opening, loss of membrane potential, and apoptosis. Experimental models of hypertension and diabetes

showed increased AT1R expression before clinical disease manifestation. At nuclear level, AT2R induces antioxidant and biogenesis-regulating factors, while AT1R stimulates pro-inflammatory and pro-fibrotic genes, accelerating CVD progression. Novel therapeutic approaches targeting mitochondrial dysfunction have been proposed, including transplantation of healthy mitochondria, mitochondrial peptides and antioxidants such as SS-31, MitoQ, and Mito-Tempo. In addition, established agents, such as metformin, SGLT2 inhibitors, and high-dose simvastatin, have been investigated for their impact on mitochondrial preservation, highlighting a promising field of pharmacological research focused on the intersection of mitochondrial metabolism and cardiovascular pathophysiology. **CONCLUSION:** Mitochondrial dysfunction, exacerbated by chronic RAAS activation, plays a pivotal role in CVD progression by driving redox imbalance, ROS accumulation, and impairment of key processes such as oxidative phosphorylation, biogenesis, and mitochondrial dynamics. Therapeutic strategies including antioxidants, SGLT2 inhibitors, metformin, natural compounds, and mitochondrial transplantation show promise but still require confirmation in large, well-designed clinical trials. Thus, mitochondrial protection represents a critical target for the development of next-generation cardioprotective therapies.

Figure1

Source: Own authorship.

Keywords: Renin angiotensin system, Mitochondria, myocardial infarction, oxidative Stress

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METABOLIC AND ADIPOSE TISSUE EFFECTS OF A REFINED CARBOHYDRATE RICH DIET IN FEMALE WISTAR RATS

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Introduction

The consumption of refined carbohydrates, characterized by high levels of simple sugars, has been associated with the early development of metabolic disturbances and adipose tissue dysfunction, factors linked to systemic inflammation and increased cardiovascular risk. This study aimed to evaluate the metabolic effects and visceral adipose tissue responses to a refined carbohydrate rich diet in female Wistar rats.

Materials and Methods

An experimental study was conducted using 8 week old female Wistar rats (~250 g) obtained from the UFES central animal facility (CEUA-UFES n° 16/2022). Animals were maintained under controlled conditions and randomly assigned to two groups: control (CT), fed standard chow, and high-carb. (HC), fed a diet enriched with refined carbohydrates (45% condensed milk, 10% sucrose, and 45% standard chow) for 15 days. On day 12, an intraperitoneal glucose tolerance test (ipGTT) was performed. On day 15, fasting blood glucose was measured, followed by euthanasia for collection of blood from the abdominal aorta. Serum was obtained by centrifugation and used to quantify total cholesterol, HDL, and triglycerides using commercial colorimetric kits. Ovarian, perirenal, mesenteric, and retroperitoneal adipose tissues were collected to assess fat deposition. Data were analyzed using unpaired Student's t-test and/or two-way ANOVA.

Results

The HC diet did not alter fasting blood glucose (CT: 103.89 ± 13.12 mg/dL; HC: 99.96 ± 11.75 mg/dL; n = 28). However, the ipGTT, which is more sensitive than fasting glucose, showed elevated glucose levels at 15 and 30 minutes in the HC group (15 min-CT: 201.28 ± 9.82 mg/dL; HC: 278.57 ± 10.15 mg/dL; 30 min-CT: 168.28 ± 9.79 mg/dL; HC: 224.14 ± 8.37 mg/dL; n = 7). Total cholesterol was unchanged (CT: 122.50 ± 12.87 mg/dL; HC: 121.91 ± 26.25 mg/dL; n = 9), but plasma triglycerides increased (CT: 90.10 ± 4.62 mg/dL; HC: 112.23 ± 6.54 mg/dL; n = 9) and HDL decreased (CT: 51.16 ± 3.41 mg/dL; HC: 41.10 ± 2.98 mg/dL; n = 9) in the HC group. Analysis of visceral fat depots revealed increased ovarian fat (CT: 3.11 ± 0.29 g; HC: 4.26 ± 0.40 g; n = 14), whereas mesenteric (CT: 1.46 ± 0.07 g; HC: 1.81 ± 0.16 g; n = 14), retroperitoneal (CT: 1.66 ± 0.12 g; HC:

1.90 ± 0.20 g; n = 14), and perirenal fat (CT: 0.73 ± 0.11 g; HC: 0.96 ± 0.10 g; n = 14) showed no significant differences between groups.

Conclusion

Exposure to the HC diet was associated with glucose intolerance and dyslipidemia, characterized by increased triglycerides, reduced HDL, and ovarian fat accumulation. Although fasting glucose remained unchanged, early metabolic alterations were observed, suggesting initial pro-inflammatory responses. These findings indicate that even short-term consumption of refined carbohydrates may disrupt metabolic balance and promote early alterations in visceral adipose tissue.

Keywords: Refined carbohydrates; Dyslipidemia; Inflammation.

Funding: Foundation for Research and Innovation Support of Espírito Santo (FAPES) and Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel (CAPES).

THE CONSUMPTION OF A DIET RICH IN REFINED CARBOHYDRATES FOR 15 DAYS REDUCES THE CONTRACTILE FORCE OF PAPILLARY MUSCLES

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Introduction

Excessive consumption of refined carbohydrates is associated with increased systemic inflammation, oxidative stress, and metabolic dysfunctions that negatively affect the cardiovascular system. Evidence suggests that diets high in refined carbohydrates may disrupt calcium homeostasis and excitation–contraction coupling, thereby impairing cardiac muscle contractility. The aim of this study was to evaluate whether a diet rich in refined carbohydrates compromises cardiac contractility in female Wistar rats.

Materials and Methods

This experimental study was conducted with eight week old female Wistar rats (average initial weight: 250 g) obtained from the UFES Central Animal Facility. The animals were randomly assigned to two experimental groups: Control (CT), fed a standard diet, and High Carb (HC), fed a diet rich in refined carbohydrates composed of 45% condensed milk, 10% sucrose, and 45% standard chow for 15 days. Body weight change (Δ), daily intake of chow, water, and energy, as well as feed efficiency (g/Kcal), were evaluated. Parameters assessed in left ventricular (LV) papillary muscles included contraction force (g/mg), maximal positive and negative derivatives (dF/dt^+ and dF/dt^-), post-pause potentiation (PPP), and post-rest contraction (PRC). Data were expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM) and analyzed using unpaired Student's *t*-test and two-way ANOVA, with $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant. CEUA–UFES no. 16/2022.

Results

At the end of the treatment, both CT and HC groups showed similar body weight variation, with no significant differences in body weight Δ (CT: 24.21 ± 1.62 g; HC: 24.89 ± 1.59 g; $n = 28$). Papillary muscle weight did not differ between groups (CT: 6.61 ± 0.54 mg; $n = 17$; HC: 5.59 ± 0.43 mg; $n = 20$). The HC group exhibited a reduction in daily chow intake (CT: 17.54 ± 0.43 g; HC: 16.18 ± 0.44 g; $n = 28$) and lower water consumption (CT: 25.93 ± 0.89 mL; HC: 21.2 ± 0.59 mL; $n = 28$), with no differences in total energy intake (CT: 70.17 ± 1.75 Kcal; HC: 70.69 ± 1.9 Kcal; $n = 28$) or feed efficiency (CT: 0.34 ± 0.01 g/Kcal; HC: 0.33 ± 0.01 g/Kcal; $n = 28$). In the functional

study, the HC group showed a significant reduction in contraction force (CT: 0.30 ± 0.12 g/mg; $n = 11$; HC: 0.24 ± 0.07 g/mg; $n = 16$), as well as decreased dF/dt^+ (CT: 3.30 ± 1.00 g/mg; $n = 10$; HC: 2.5 ± 0.84 g/mg; $n = 16$). Moreover, PPP was reduced after 60 seconds of rest (CT: 207.63 ± 29.98 ; $n = 13$; HC: 175.53 ± 31.96 ; $n = 16$), and PRC was also lower in the HC group (CT: 35.5 ± 20.30 ; $n = 11$; HC: 22.58 ± 10.45 ; $n = 16$).

Conclusion

Animals in the HC group showed reduced food intake and decreased contractile strength of LV papillary muscles, indicating myocardial dysfunction independent of body weight and energy intake. The reductions in force, dF/dt^+ , PPP, and PRC suggest impairment in excitation–contraction coupling and intracellular calcium regulation, pointing to early deterioration of cardiac performance. These findings reinforce that excessive intake of refined carbohydrates compromises cardiac muscle contractile function, representing a significant risk factor for the development and progression of cardiovascular diseases.

Keywords: Refined carbohydrates; Myocardial contractility; Excitation-contraction coupling.

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ACUTE INJURY MARKERS IN AN EXPERIMENTAL MODEL OF IRON OVERLOAD

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Introduction: Iron overload can lead to severe damage in multiple organs, with toxicity primarily resulting from oxidative stress. The acute form is hazardous since it can induce organ failure within a short period. The early detection of damage in patients at risk of iron overload allows more effective clinical management, preventing severe complications. In this study, we hypothesized that monitoring serum markers of target organ injury may be useful and correlate with iron deposit and damage in an animal model of acute iron intoxication. **Material and Methods:** Two-month-old male Wistar rats, weighing 250-300 g, were divided into a control group (Ct) injected with saline, and three groups injected with different high doses of iron-dextran (Fe: 250, 500, and 1000 mg/kg, i.p.). All protocols had ethical approval (CEUA-UFES #51/2019). After 24 hours, the animals were euthanized and blood and tissues (heart, liver, and kidneys) were collected. Blood analyses (serum) included markers of oxidative stress (MDA and AOPP), systemic iron profile (iron, ferritin, and transferrin), cardiac injury (CK-MB, Troponin I, and LDH), hepatic injury (alkaline phosphatase, AST, and ALT), and renal/glomerular function (creatinine). Tissue iron quantification was performed using Inductively Coupled Plasma-Optical Emission Spectrometry (ICP-OES). Statistical analysis was performed using the Kruskal-Wallis with Dunn's post-test, and the Spearman test for correlations (* $p < 0.05$ vs. Ct). **Results:** As expected, all Fe groups showed significant iron accumulation in the analyzed organs, as well as an elevation in the serum iron status. Furthermore, the acute intoxication was accompanied by increased serum levels of not only markers of systemic oxidative stress MDA (CT: 0.422 ± 0.019 ; Fe250: $0.823 \pm 0.094^*$; Fe500: 0.975 ± 0.11 ; Fe1000: $1.28 \pm 0.12^* \mu\text{M}$) and AOPP (CT: 0.84 ± 0.27 ; Fe250: $15.5 \pm 2.8^*$; Fe500: $17.6 \pm 2.4^*$; Fe1000: $26.8 \pm 1.5^* \mu\text{M}$), but also an elevation in LDH (CT: 199 ± 33 ; Fe500: $373 \pm 56^*$; Fe1000: $501 \pm 106^* \text{U/L}$), troponin I (Ct: 0.6 ± 0.2 ; Fe1000: $1.5 \pm 0.2^* \text{pg/mL}$), AST (Ct: 65.7 ± 1.8 ; Fe500: $104.2 \pm 7.6^*$; Fe1000: $132 \pm 20^* \text{U/L}$), and creatinine (Ct: 0.26 ± 0.03 ; Fe250: $0.36 \pm 0.02^*$; Fe1000: $0.38 \pm 0.01 \text{mg/dL}^*$). Moreover, the serum iron level positively correlated with MDA and AOPP, and the iron deposited in the heart and liver positively correlated with their respective injury/dysfunction markers: Cardiac Fe vs. LDH ($r = 0.99$, $P = 0.009$), and Hepatic Fe vs. AST ($r = 0.98$, $P < 0.0001$), but not Renal Fe vs. Creatinine ($r = 0.59$, $P = 0.1089$). **Conclusion:** Acute iron overload, even within a 24-hour period, is capable of inducing significant injury mediated by oxidative stress, probably due to the accumulation of this element in different tissues. This accumulation positively correlated with the elevation of organ damage biomarkers, suggesting that monitoring such serum markers may be an important tool in acute iron intoxication management.

Keywords: Iron Overload, Iron Intoxication, Oxidative Stress, Myocardial Damage, Biomarkers.

Financiamento: UFES, CNPq e a Capes

TESTOSTERONE AND ALDOSTERONE: LONG-TERM MODULATION OF VASCULAR REACTIVITY IN ORCHIECTOMIZED WISTAR RATS TREATED WITH SPIRONOLACTONE.

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Introduction: Testosterone, has been shown to exhibit endothelium-dependent vasodilation in acute scenarios. We test the hypothesis that testosterone plays a major role in the long-term modulation of vascular reactivity by an aldosterone-dependent pathway. **Methods:** 12-week-old Wistar rats were segregated into Control (SHAM, N=8) and Orchiectomy (OQT, N=9) groups and treated for 3 months with spironolactone (SPI) (SHAM+SPI, N=10 and OQT+SPI, N=9, 80 mg/kg, gavage), aldosterone receptor antagonist. (CEUA-UFES 17/2020). Vascular reactivity was examined in isolated thoracic aorta rings during concentration-response curves to phenylephrine (Phe) (10^{-11} to 10^{-3} M) in the presence and absence of L-NAME (LN) (NOS inhibitor, 100 μ M), and with endothelium-denuded rings (E-). Results were expressed as mean \pm SEM. **Results:** After 3 months, the groups OQT show less body weight gain compared to the SHAM. This discrepancy was abolished with SPI treatment. (SHAM:231 \pm 11; OQT:158.4 \pm 13*; OQT+SPI:180.5 \pm 20.60*; SHAM+SPI: 215.3 \pm 26.1 g *p<0.05). There was no difference in the maximum response (Rmax) to Phe between the SHAM and OQT groups. However, OQT+SPI group demonstrated a decreased Rmax to Phe compared to the SHAM (SHAM:109.4 \pm 9.5%; OQT:120.5 \pm 10%; SHAM+SPI: 120.4 \pm 7.56 % N=10 vs OQT+SPI: 93.3 \pm 10.2 % N=10; *p<0.05). The reactivity to Phe increased in the presence of LN and in E-, with no difference between the groups. **Conclusion:** Our data suggests that testosterone has a role in angiotensin II-mediated NO production, since blocking NO production with LN resulted in a decrease in Rmax in the OQT group compared to its control. It highlights the potential of testosterone in the contractile response mediated by the angiotensin AT1 receptor.

Keywords: Testosterone; Angiotensin II; Vascular Reactivity; Aldosterone, Male sexuals hormones; Vascular endothelium.

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REGULATION OF VASCULAR REACTIVITY DEPENDENT ON THE PKD1 SIGNALING PATHWAY AND OXIDATIVE STRESS IN SPONTANEOUSLY HYPERTENSIVE RATS

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High blood pressure is a major cause of cardiovascular diseases. In the hypertensive rat model (SHR), vascular dysfunction is linked to oxidative inactivation of nitric oxide (NO), resulting from increased production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) dependent on NADPH oxidase (NOX). NOX redox signaling involves regulatory mechanisms mediated by intra- and extracellular pathways. Recently, attention has been directed to protein kinase D1 (PKD1), part of the Ca²⁺-calmodulin-dependent kinase family, which has been associated with vascular smooth muscle contraction and modulation of vascular reactivity. This study hypothesized that PKD1 participates in vascular tone regulation in SHR via NOX-dependent oxidative stress. Isolated aortic rings from Wistar and SHR rats were used to evaluate α 1 receptor- and angiotensin II (ATII)-mediated vascular reactivity. Concentration-response curves to phenylephrine (10⁻¹⁰–10⁻⁴ M) and ATII (10⁻¹⁰–10⁻⁵ M) were obtained cumulatively in the presence or absence of CID (3.2 μ M, selective PKD1 inhibitor) and Apokinin (30 μ M, NOX inhibitor). Oxidative stress was assessed by thiobarbituric acid reactive species (TBARS) to measure lipid peroxidation, and dihydroethidium (DHE) fluorescence. Systolic blood pressure (SBP, mmHg) was recorded by tail plethysmography 48 h before experiments. Data are presented as mean \pm SEM and analyzed by Student's t-test, ANOVA, and Tukey's post-hoc test. SHR exhibited lower body mass (Wistar: 313 \pm 5.5 g vs SHR: 260 \pm 8.5 g, *p<0.01) and higher SBP (Wistar: 130.0 \pm 1.7 vs SHR: 197.3 \pm 2.5 mmHg, *p<0.01), with no differences in heart rate. In Wistar rats, PKD1 inhibition with CID did not alter phenylephrine reactivity (R_{max}: 114.4 \pm 7.54 vs 96.11 \pm 13.7 % KCl). However, in SHR, CID reduced aortic reactivity to phenylephrine (R_{max}: 129.9 \pm 8.28 vs 83.74 \pm 9.3 % KCl, *p<0.01). For ATII, CID reduced vasoconstrictor responses only in Wistar rats (R_{max}: 52.5 \pm 3.7 vs 38.8 \pm 6.4 % KCl, *p<0.01). No differences were observed between CID and CID+Apokinin groups in either strain. Oxidative stress analysis showed no significant differences between groups with or without CID after ATII incubation. However, co-incubation with CID and Apokinin reduced malondialdehyde (MDA) levels in SHR. These findings support the hypothesis that PKD1 contributes to aortic ring reactivity in both strains but in distinct contexts: in SHR, PKD1 mainly modulates phenylephrine-mediated contraction, whereas in Wistar rats, it influences ATII responses. The hypothesis that oxidative stress mediates CID responses was rejected, as Apokinin did not alter CID effects. Nevertheless, the observed interaction between CID and Apokinin in reducing oxidative markers in SHR suggests a partial role of ROS in vascular regulation. In conclusion, PKD1 signaling is crucial for vascular contraction in SHR under phenylephrine stimulation and in Wistar rats under ATII stimulation, independent of

NOX-derived oxidative stress. These results provide insights into vascular regulation mechanisms and may inform new therapeutic strategies for hypertension management.

Keywords: PKD1; Vascular Reactivity; SHR; NADPH Oxidase; Aorta; Phenylephrine; Angiotensin II.

Funding: CAPES, CNPq e FAPES

INVESTIGATION OF CARDIOPROTECTIVE STRATEGIES BY THERAPEUTIC AND PHARMACOLOGICAL AGENTS IN CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES USING CELL CULTURE: AN UPDATED REVIEW

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Introduction: Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are the leading cause of mortality worldwide, accounting for approximately one-third of all deaths. Conditions such as coronary artery disease, hypertension, stroke, and heart failure are associated with high morbidity and mortality rates, as well as significant healthcare costs. Despite therapeutic advances, there remains a continuous need for more effective and safer strategies. *In vitro* studies, such as cell culture models, are crucial in the development of cardiovascular therapies and compound validation, enabling detailed analysis of molecular and cellular mechanisms in a controlled environment prior to *in vivo* studies and clinical trials.

Methodology: A systematic review was conducted in the PubMed database using the descriptors “cell culture,” “cardiovascular disease,” and “cardioprotection.” Of the 384 articles initially retrieved, 28 met the inclusion criteria: original studies published between 2015 and 2025, available in Portuguese or English, with free full-text access, and involving direct use of cardiovascular cell culture models. Duplicates, review articles, and studies without direct application of cell culture were excluded. The selected studies were qualitatively analyzed regarding models, methodologies, tested compounds, and underlying mechanisms.

Results: *In vitro* models using cardiomyocytes (H9c2, primary rat and human), endothelial cells (HUVEC, MV-EC), smooth muscle cells, and fibroblasts were widely employed to simulate hypoxia/reoxygenation injury, oxidative stress, chemical ischemia, and doxorubicin-induced cardiotoxicity. Viability assays (MTT, CCK-8), flow cytometry, and TUNEL were used to assess apoptosis, necrosis, and enzyme release such as LDH. Oxidative stress assays quantified reactive oxygen species (ROS), enzymatic activity (SOD, catalase), and oxidative markers (MDA, TAC). Several bioactive compounds demonstrated cardioprotective effects. Methylophiopogonanone A reduced apoptosis by activating the PI3K/Akt/eNOS pathway. Resveratrol restored mitochondrial function under oxidative stress, while the herbal formulation Qiliqiangxin modulated apoptosis-regulating proteins and inhibited mitochondrial fission. Salvianolic acid B protected against ischemic injury by suppressing excessive autophagy via the miR-30a/Beclin-1 pathway. Drugs such as rapamycin and dexmedetomidine regulated apoptosis and mitochondrial metabolism, while antioxidant compounds like isosteviol, baicalein, Δ 9-tetrahydrocannabinol, and R-(-)-carvone reduced ROS levels and enhanced antioxidant enzyme activity. Other studies showed that sevoflurane preconditioning inhibited autophagy-mediated cell death, and adipose-derived stem cells pretreated with herbal formulations reduced apoptosis and cardiac hypertrophy induced by chemotherapeutics. Additionally, the use

of doxorubicin prodrugs improved absorption kinetics in cardiomyoblasts, suggesting new approaches for more specific and less toxic therapies. Strategies based on co-cultures and cultured cardiac slices also yielded promising results, bringing *in vitro* models closer to physiological conditions and allowing more detailed analysis of cellular responses.

Conclusion: *In vitro* studies are essential tools for the development of cardiovascular therapies, enabling the understanding of cellular mechanisms and rapid, effective testing of compounds. Although translation of these results to *in vivo* models has limitations, these systems provide valuable data to guide future research. With the advancement of technologies such as 3D cultures and organoids, the translational applicability of these findings is expected to increase, strengthening the development of innovative cardioprotective strategies.

Keywords: *in vitro* models; natural bioactive compounds; synthetic drugs; cardiotoxicity prevention

ACUTE CHLORPYRIFOS-OXON EXPOSURE DISRUPTS BEZOLD–JARISCH REFLEX AND CARDIORESPIRATORY INTEGRATION IN WISTAR AND HYPERTENSIVE RATS

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Cardiorespiratory complications are the leading cause of hospitalization and are potentially fatal in organophosphate (OP) poisoning. Experimental studies show that OP-induced mortality is greater in spontaneously hypertensive rats (SHR) than in normotensive animals. We previously demonstrated, *in situ*, that chlorpyrifos (CPF), a commonly used OP, impairs baro- and chemo- reflexes in a strain-specific manner. *In vivo*, we have already demonstrated that the Bezold-Jarisch reflex (BJR) is also dysfunctional following CPF exposure. However, the acute effects of OP on BJR response during the early phase of poisoning, especially in the presence of comorbidities such as hypertension, remain unclear. Using the working heart-brainstem preparation, we simultaneously recorded heart rate, phrenic nerve activity, and thoracic sympathetic nerve activity in both Wistar and pre-hypertensive SHR (4-5 week old; CEUA number 17/2022). After a 15-minute baseline, the BJR was evoked by an arterial bolus of phenylbiguanide (120 µg/Kg). Preparations were then administered with either Chlorpyrifos-oxon (CPO; 15 mg/Kg), the active form of CPF, or DMSO (vehicle), and reflex was reassessed. Brainstems and atrial tissues were collected for cholinesterase (ChE), butyryl (BChE) and acetylcholinesterase (AChE), activity assays (µmol/h/mg of protein). Data (mean ± SD) were analysed using two-way ANOVA and generalized mixed models. Groups (n = 10 each): Wistar DMSO (WD), Wistar CPO (WC), SHR DMSO (SD), SHR CPO (SC). CPO led to a dysfunction of BJR, increasing bradycardic responses relative to the DMSO group (Wistar = Δ -59.6; p<0.05; SHR = Δ -63.2; p<0.01; bpm). Perfusion pressure (PP) significantly decreased in both groups after CPO (WC = Δ 2.71; p<0.01; SC = Δ 3.07; p<0.01; mmHg), whereas respiratory responses were reversed, with CPO shifting the typical BJR bradypnea into tachypnea (WD = Δ 5.56; p<0.01; WC = Δ -4.79; p<0.05; SD = Δ 1.42; p>0.05; SC = Δ -5.28; p<0.01; cpm). Expiratory time (ET) and sympathetic inhibition showed a strain-dependent effect with a larger prolongation of ET in Wistar (WC = Δ 2.22 vs SC = Δ 0.91; s) and a blunted sympatho-inhibitory response in SHR (WC = Δ -0.13; p>0.05; SC = Δ -0.42; p<0.01; µvolts). At baseline levels (under DMSO), SHR already presented a more intense bradycardia (Δ = -96.7 ± 45.2), whereas Wistar showed a slight decrease in PP (Δ = -5.7 ± 2.01) and stronger bradypnea (Δ = -15.24 ± 7.58). Brainstem ChE activity was inhibited in both strains after CPO (WD 5.23 ± 0.76; WC 0.27 ± 0.13; SD 5.83 ± 0.49; SC 0.39 ± 0.17). Both atrial BChE (WD 1.71 ±

0.38; WC 0.65 ± 0.32 ; SD 1.202 ± 0.48 ; SC 0.59 ± 0.24) and AChE (WD 0.52 ± 0.19 ; WC 0.09 ± 0.03 ; SD 0.47 ± 0.23 ; SC 0.09 ± 0.07) activity were reduced by CPO, and pre-hypertensive animals showed a lower baseline atrial BChE activity. Our findings show that acute OP exposure also impairs BRJ and cardiorespiratory integration, with differential effects between hypertensive and normotensive phenotypes. These results underscore the importance of understanding strain-specific vulnerabilities to OP toxicity, as different clinical approaches may be required.

Keywords: Organophosphate poisoning, Chlorpyrifos, Bezold Jarisch Reflex and Hypertension.

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SHORT- AND LONG-TERM PERIODONTITIS IN APOE KNOCKOUT MICE: IMPACT ON ALVEOLAR BONE LOSS AND SYSTEMIC OXIDATIVE STRESS

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Introduction: The relationship between periodontitis and various systemic diseases has been extensively investigated in recent decades. Among these conditions, cardiovascular diseases (CVD's) stand out, which can be aggravated by the presence of periodontal inflammation. Hypercholesterolemia is recognized as one of the main modifiable risk factors for the development of CVD's, in addition representing a possible link between chronic periodontal inflammation and atherosclerosis. Oxidative stress is one of the main pathophysiological mechanisms associated with periodontitis, a condition characterized by increased production of reactive oxygen species (ROS). At the same time, individuals with hypercholesterolemia are more susceptible to LDL-Cholesterol oxidation when there is an increase in ROS production and consequently higher risk of developing atherosclerosis. Considering that the periodontal inflammatory process can trigger systemic repercussions, it is relevant to investigate whether these effects persist after removal of the causative agent, especially in individuals with predisposing conditions such as hypercholesterolemia. Thus, this study aims to evaluate alveolar bone loss, plasma levels of (ROS), and oxidative stress in an experimental mouse model of hypercholesterolemia (ApoE knockout) subjected experimental periodontitis, 7 and 28 days after removal of the causative agent. **Materials and Methods:** ApoE knockout mice were subjected to periodontitis induction by ligation of the right first molar for four weeks. After ligature removal, animals were divided into two groups: ApoEP7 (euthanized 7 days later, n=5) and ApoEP28 (euthanized 28 days later, n=5). A control group without periodontitis was also included (ApoEC, n=5). Bone loss in the mandible was quantified by scanning electron microscopy. Systemic oxidative stress was assessed by plasma lipid peroxidation (TBARS). The ROS superoxide anion and hydrogen peroxide were analyzed by flow cytometry in blood cells using DHE and DCF as markers **Results:** We observed significant ($p<0.05$) bone loss in the ApoEP7 ($771.6\pm 32.30 \mu\text{m}$) and ApoEP28 ($797.0\pm 44.88 \mu\text{m}$) groups compared to ApoEC ($553.9\pm 22.70 \mu\text{m}$). We also observed a significant increase ($p<0.05$) in systemic lipid peroxidation in the ApoEP7 ($0.02118\pm 0.003607 \mu\text{mol/mg}$) and ApoEP28 ($0.03313\pm 0.004602 \mu\text{mol/mg}$) groups compared to ApoEC ($0.006925\pm 0.0007040 \mu\text{mol/mg}$). There was also a significant increase ($p<0.05$) in hydrogen peroxide levels in the ApoE7 ($989.5\pm 35.5 \text{ a.u}$) and ApoE28 ($1804\pm 3.5 \text{ a.u}$) groups compared to the ApoEC group ($555.6\pm 69.75 \text{ a.u}$), and in superoxide anion levels, in the ApoE7 group ($147.3\pm 12.41 \text{ a.u}$) and ApoE28 (135.7 ± 2.60

a.u.) when compared to ApoEC (97.68 ± 3.87 a.u). **Conclusion:** Our findings demonstrate that even after resolution of periodontitis induction, with ligature removal and local debridement, animals continued to exhibit marked bone loss, increased ROS, and oxidative stress. These results suggest that the deleterious systemic effects of periodontitis extend beyond the active phase of the disease, indicating ongoing cellular damage in a chronic context, especially in hypercholesterolemic animals.

Keywords: Hypercholesterolemia. Periodontitis. Reactive oxygen species.

Financial Support: FAPES. CNPq. CAPES

PROGESTERONE PREVENTS CORONARY ENDOTHELIAL DYSFUNCTION INDUCED BY OVARECTOMY

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Introduction: Progesterone (P4) is a steroid hormone produced mainly by the ovaries, that exerts multiple actions in the body. P4 can act directly on the vascular smooth muscle and endothelial cells through specific receptors, contributing to vascular homeostasis. Nevertheless, the mechanisms involved in the coronary bed are not yet been fully elucidated. This study investigated the effects of P4 on endothelial function in the coronary bed of ovariectomized rats, based on the hypothesis that progesterone treatment prevents endothelial dysfunction induced by hormonal deficiency. **Material and Methods:** Protocols were approved by CEUA/UFES (63/2017). Female Wistar rats (8-week-old, body weight: 182 ± 14 g) were divided into: Sham, Ovariectomized (OVX), and Ovariectomized treated with progesterone (OVX P4) (2 mg/kg/day). Vascular reactivity was assessed by a modified Langendorff technique. After stabilization (40 min), baseline coronary perfusion pressure (CPP) was established and a bradykinin curve (BK, 0.1–1000 nM) was performed, followed by inhibitions with L-NAME (100 μ M), indomethacin (INDO, 2.8 μ M), L-NAME + INDO, or L-NAME + INDO + clotrimazole (0.75 μ M). The intensity of eNOS, Akt, and gp91phox protein expression was quantified by Western blot (WB). Oxygen reactive species and hydrogen peroxide production were measured by fluorescence analysis. Data were expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM), normality was confirmed by the Shapiro–Wilk test and analyzed by one- or two-way ANOVA followed by Tukey’s *post hoc* test ($p < 0.05$). **Results:** The OVX group had a lower baseline CPP compared to the others and P4 treatment was able to prevent this effect (Sham, 88 ± 3 ; OVX, 70 ± 8 ; OVX P4, 96 ± 8 mmHg, $n=20$). After BK administration, we observed that endothelium-dependent vasodilation was impaired in the OVX group and potentiated in the OVX P4 group (Sham, 14.7 ± 1 ; OVX, 7.3 ± 1 ; OVX P4, 23.9 ± 3 %; $n=8$). In the L-NAME curve, there was a greater increase in relaxation in the OVX P4 group (23.9 ± 2.8 to 35.2 ± 2.6 %), indicating that this pathway appears to act by negatively modulating relaxation in these animals. After inhibition of the prostanoid pathway with indomethacin, the relaxant response to BK was similar to that observed in the basal curve (Sham, 11.3 ± 1.5 %; OVX, 4.0 ± 0.7 %; OVX P4, 26.8 ± 0.4 %). These results suggest that the prostanoid pathway does not participate in BK-

induced vasodilation. The response after combined inhibition of NO and prostanoids was similar to that found with individual inhibition of NO (Sham, $19.4 \pm 2\%$; OVX, $8.5 \pm 1.1\%$; OVX P4, $33.2 \pm 3\%$). Finally, after combined inhibition of NO, prostanoids, and epoxyeicosatrienoic acids, we observed that the vasodilatory response was abolished in all groups, showing participation of EDH. Fluorescence and WB results showed that treatment prevented the alterations in oxidative parameters induced by ovariectomy. **Conclusion:** P4 exerts a beneficial effect on the coronary bed, preventing endothelial dysfunction resulting from hormonal deficiency.

Keywords: Hormonal replacement; Sex hormones; Cardioprotection.

Funding: CAPES, FAPES.

EFFECTS OF COPPER OVERLOAD ON THE REDOX STATUS OF MESENTERIC PERIVASCULAR ADIPOSE TISSUE IN WISTAR RATS

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Introduction: Copper is an essential trace metal. Despite its physiological importance, excessive copper can be harmful, inducing oxidative stress and cellular damage, which may be associated with cardiovascular alterations. Perivascular adipose tissue (PVAT) is a critical regulator of vascular tone. However, under conditions of oxidative stress, the endocrine, metabolic, and anticontractile functions of PVAT may be altered, compromising vascular balance. The impact of copper overload on mesenteric PVAT remains unexplored.

Methods: Eight-week-old male rats were divided into two groups: Control (saline solution, CT, i.p.) or Copper (25.72 µg/kg/day Cu, i.p. for 30 days). The rats were anesthetized with a combination of ketamine (60 mg/kg, i.p.) and xylazine (6 mg/kg, i.p.). After euthanasia, mesenteric PVAT was collected to quantify reactive oxygen species (ROS) and nitric oxide (NO), evaluate the expression of the eNOS gene and protein expression of antioxidant enzymes. The study was approved by the Ethics Committee on Animal Use (CEUA-UFES n. 01/2023). Data were expressed as mean ± standard error of the average. Significant differences will be represented by * for P < 0.05 using Student's t-test.

Results: We observed an increase in ROS production (CT=1.24±0.13; CU= 4.55±1.24***, n= 5-6, u.a.%area), NOX 4 protein expression (CT=0.98±0.2; CU= 1.4±0.41*, n= 6) and a decrease in SOD-1 protein expression (CT=1.00±0.27; CU=0.61±0.10*, n=5-6, 2 replicates). No differences were found in catalase protein expression (CT=1.00±0.04; CU=1.20±0.11, n=6, 2 replicates), bioavailability of NO (CT=2.27±0.44; CU= 2.55±0.44, n= 5, u.a.%area) and eNOS mRNA levels (CT=0.94±0.21; CU= 0.91±0.12, n= 6-7).

Conclusion: Exposure to twice the recommended dose of copper altered key redox pathways in mesenteric PVAT, suggesting its potential role as an inducer of oxidative stress.

Keywords: copper; perivascular adipose tissue; status redox;

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EFFECTS OF A DIET RICH IN REFINED CARBOHYDRATES ON VASCULAR REACTIVITY IN MALE AND FEMALE RATS: SEX DIFFERENCES

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Introduction: The global increase in refined carbohydrate consumption and its association with cardiovascular diseases led to this study, which investigated whether a diet rich in carbohydrates compromises vascular reactivity in rat aortas, with a comparison between sexes. The aim was to identify differences in vascular response between males and females, considering sex-related biological variations. **Methods:** Six-week-old male and female Wistar rats, weighing approximately 250g, were obtained from the animal facility of the Federal University of Espírito Santo, with protocol approval from the University's Ethics Committee for Animal Use (CEUA – UFES – 16/2022). After two weeks of acclimatization, the animals were randomly divided into two experimental groups: the Control group (CT) and the High-Carbohydrate Diet group (HCD). The CT group received standard chow for 15 days, while the HCD group was fed a diet composed of 45% condensed milk, 10% refined sugar, and 45% standard chow. After treatment, the animals were sacrificed, and their thoracic aortas were removed for vascular reactivity and gene expression experiments. Vascular reactivity was measured as force tension in grams-force exerted by the rings, with 1 g representing baseline tension. The results were analyzed by t-test and two-way ANOVA, with significance set at $p < 0.05$. **Results:** The high-carbohydrate diet (HCD) did not significantly alter weight gain in male rats compared to the control group (CT). Weight gain was 50 ± 3.1 g in the CT group ($n = 8$) and 50 ± 2.7 g in the HCD group ($n = 8$). Similarly, female rats did not show significant differences in weight gain. The average weight of females in the CT group was 50.5 ± 11.47 g ($n = 8$), and in the HCD group it was 51.7 ± 6.0 g ($n = 8$). Regarding vascular reactivity, male rats in the HCD group showed a significant reduction in vascular response compared to the CT group. In the CT group, vascular reactivity was 97.0 ± 7.7 g ($n = 9$), while in the HCD group it was 57.9 ± 9.0 g ($n = 10$). The same pattern was observed in females: the HCD group exhibited reduced vascular reactivity compared to the CT group. Female rats in the CT group showed a reactivity of 90 ± 19.8 g ($n = 13$), while in the HCD group it was 62.8 ± 22.6 g ($n = 14$). **Conclusion:** The results indicate that the high-carbohydrate diet (HCD) did not cause significant changes in weight gain in male and female rats compared to the control group (CT). However, vascular reactivity was significantly reduced in animals of both sexes that received the HCD diet. This reduction was observed in both males and females, suggesting that the diet may affect vascular responses regardless of sex, without influencing weight gain.

Keywords: Diet; Carbohydrates; Sexual differences. **Funding:** FAPES - Foundation for Research and Innovation Support of Espírito Santo.

THEMATIC AXIS V

Drugs and Exposures: Xenobiotics and Health Effects

MEMANTINE FAILS TO PREVENT AND EXACERBATES SOME TOXICITY SIGNS AFTER ACUTE CHLORPYRIFOS POISONING

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Introduction: Human poisoning by organophosphates (OP) represents a public health problem, due to their widespread application in agriculture and their use as chemical weapons, and in suicide attempts. Current treatment relies on atropine (ATR) administration, yet the high mortality highlights the need for alternative therapies. Due to its neuroprotective properties, one of the drugs that has been studied as an antidote is memantine (MEM). Therefore, this study aimed to evaluate whether memantine, alone or combined with ATR, could reduce the toxicity of chlorpyrifos (CPF), a highly used OP. **Materials and Methods:** Adult male Wistar rats (300-350g) were obtained from the Federal University of Espírito Santo (UFES) breeding colony. The animals were injected with saline or CPF and after one hour, they received MEM and/or ATR according to their group. Signs of acute toxicity were monitored from CPF injection up to 4 hours at intervals of 10 min, 30 min, 45 min, 1 h, 1 h 20 min, 1 h 40 min, 2 h, 3 h, and 4 h. Signs recorded included salivation, lacrimation, exophthalmos, coordination, general activity, and motor activity. Signs were rated on a scale: 0 = absent, 1 = light, 2 = moderate and 3 = intense. After 24 hours, blood samples were collected, and CPF poisoning was confirmed by measuring erythrocyte acetylcholinesterase (AChE) and plasmatic butyrylcholinesterase (BChE) activities using the Ellman's method. Data were analysed using the SPSS statistics software (version 20.0; IBM, New York, NY, USA) for Windows, with Generalized Estimating Equations (GEE) and significance was set at $P < 0.05$. All protocols were approved by the UFES Ethics Committee on Animal Use (CEUA; certificate nº 17/2022). **Results:** MEM-treated rats showed a greater severity of exophthalmos (OR = 6.847; $p < 0.05$), loss of coordination (OR = 7.021; $p < 0.05$) and lacrimation (OR = 62.798; $p < 0.05$) when compared to CPF-treated rats. CPF-induced salivation and exophthalmos were prevented by ATR treatment (OR = 0.032; $p < 0.05$; OR = 1,774E-10; $p < 0.000$, respectively). Toxicity signs of general and motor activities were infrequent across all groups, limiting statistical comparison. CPF poisoning greatly inhibited AChE and BChE activities. ChE inhibition was unchanged either by MEM and/or ATR treatment. **Conclusion:** Acute administration of memantine exacerbated some signs of CPF toxicity and was unable to restore enzyme activity. Whether memantine will also fail to exert protective effects against cardiorespiratory damage induced by CPF remains to be investigated.

Keywords: Memantine; Organophosphates; Excitotoxicity; Atropine; Antidotes.

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EFFECTS OF ACUTE CHLORPYRIFOS POISONING ON SIGNS OF ACUTE TOXICITY AND CHOLINESTERASE ACTIVITY IN ADULT NORMOTENSIVE FEMALES RATS

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Introduction: Organophosphates, such as chlorpyrifos (CPF), are widely used in Brazil and act directly on the inhibition of cholinesterases, triggering acute poisonings with autonomic and behavioral manifestations. Although OP poisonings are more frequently reported in men, evidence suggests that, in the context of suicide attempts, this prevalence shifts toward women. Moreover, few experimental studies also show that female rats exhibit greater susceptibility to OP poisoning. However, most preclinical studies are still conducted in males, leaving gaps regarding the effects in females. Thus, the objective of this study was to evaluate the susceptibility of adult female rats to acute CPF poisoning. **Material and methods:** Adult Wistar female rats (12–16 weeks) were used, kept under controlled conditions, distributed into groups according to the intraperitoneal administration of CPF (10, 20, or 30 mg/kg) or saline (Control). Signs of acute toxicity were monitored for up to 4 hours after CPF administration. After 24 hours, samples were collected for analysis of enzymatic activity of acetylcholinesterase (AChE), in blood (mU/ μ mol Hb) and brainstem (μ mol/h/mg protein) as well as butyrylcholinesterase (BChE) in plasma (μ mol/h/mg protein) according to Ellman's method. Data were analyzed by one-way ANOVA and ordinal categorical model, with significance set at $p < 0.05$, using GraphPad Prism and SPSS. The protocol was approved by CEUA/UFES (n° 04/2024). **Results:** Acute administration of chlorpyrifos (CPF; 10, 20, and 30 mg/kg, i.p.) in adult female Wistar rats induced signs of cholinergic toxicity, such as salivation, lacrimation, exophthalmos, changes in coordination and general activity, in a dose-dependent manner. For motor activity, there were only discrete changes at the highest doses of CPF. A significant reduction was observed in brain AChE activity ($p < 0.05$), erythrocyte AChE ($p < 0.05$) and plasmatic BChE at all doses tested ($p < 0.01$). These findings confirm the classic cholinergic syndrome described for OFs, in agreement with previous studies in males, and showing that females present relevant susceptibility at the same doses. **Conclusion:** Acute chlorpyrifos poisoning in adult female rats resulted in classic signs of cholinergic syndrome and significant, dose-dependent inhibition of cholinesterases. These findings confirm the compound's neurotoxic profile and highlight

the importance of considering sex in toxicological studies, contributing to a broader understanding of the health risks associated with organophosphate use.

Keywords: Organophosphate. Chlorpyrifos. Acute toxicity. Female. Cholinesterases.

Financial support: Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa e Inovação do Espírito Santo (FAPES, Grant Codes: 2022- 78KWB; 749/2024), CNPq/FAPES 2025-H5S1W; CNPq/MCTI/FNDCT N° 44/2024. KBS was a recipient of CNPq/FAPES scholarship. VSM; GGN; LJC; BFS; TJB was a recipient of a CAPES scholarship (grant codes 01).

EFFECTS OF CO-EXPOSURE TO TRIBUTYLTIN AND A HIGH-REFINED CARBOHYDRATE DIET ON HEPATIC AND PANCREATIC HISTOMORPHOLOGY IN PREGNANT RATS

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Introduction: A high-refined carbohydrate diet (HCD) and the environmental contaminant tributyltin (TBT) are associated with the development of obesity and reproductive dysfunctions. Previous studies have demonstrated that isolated exposure to either HCD or TBT leads to ovarian abnormalities and disturbances in glucose metabolism, accompanied by hepatic and pancreatic impairments. However, although these factors commonly co-occur in real life, little is understood about how their co-exposure affects carbohydrate and lipid metabolism during pregnancy. Therefore, this study aimed to analyze the disturbances caused by subacute co-exposure to TBT and HCD in hepatic and pancreatic metabolism of pregnant rats. **Materials and Methods:** Adult female Wistar rats (8 weeks old, n=10/group) were obtained from the Central Animal Facility/UFES, and the study was approved by CEUA/UFES (01/2021). Animals were exposed for 15 days: CON (0.4% ethanol gavage + standard diet), TBT (100 ng/kg/day gavage + standard diet), HCD (4.4 kcal/g diet), and HCD-TBT (co-exposure). Body weight was monitored twice a week. Pregnancy was confirmed by vaginal plug (G0.5). On gestational day 19, rats were euthanized and organs collected. Analyses included liver and pancreas mast cells (Toluidine blue), histology (H&E), collagen deposition (Picrosirius), lipid profile, and serum markers of cellular abnormalities. Data were analyzed by Tukey's test ($p < 0.05$) and expressed as mean \pm SEM. **Results:** Increased food intake was observed in the HCD-TBT group vs CON (CON: 196.8 ± 2.5 ; HCD-TBT: 247.2 ± 9.9), and also during pregnancy in the TBT group vs CON (CON: 226.7 ± 2.7 ; TBT: 241.9 ± 7.3). Differences in body weight gain before and during pregnancy were detected among groups. Serum cholesterol levels were higher in the HCD group vs CON (CON: 124.7 ± 3.4 ; HCD: 127.6 ± 1.7). Histological analysis revealed increased pancreatic islet number in the HCD-TBT group vs CON (CON: 9971 ± 715 ; HCD-TBT: 17068 ± 1092), increased hepatic granuloma formation in HCD-TBT vs CON (CON: 0.00007 ± 0.00001 ; HCD-TBT: 0.0002 ± 0.00003), increased mast cell number in the pancreas of the HCD-TBT group vs CON (CON: 0.2 ± 0.02 ; HCD-TBT: 0.5 ± 0.07), and in the liver of the TBT group vs CON ($p = 0.07$). Collagen density was increased in the liver of HCD-TBT vs CON (CON: 0.04 ± 0.001 ; HCD-TBT: 0.1 ± 0.004) and in the pancreas (CON: 0.003 ± 0.0004 ; HCD-TBT: 0.009 ± 0.0004). Hepatic lipase (U/L) increased in the HCD-TBT group vs CON (CON: 42.5 ± 11.5 ; HCD-TBT: 145.5 ± 13.4), and oxaloacetic transaminase (AST) levels increased in TBT vs CON (CON: 588 ± 119 ; TBT: 1126 ± 90). **Conclusion:** These findings demonstrate that preconception exposure to TBT and HCD led to alterations in body weight, tissue inflammation, oxidative stress, and changes in blood markers during pregnancy.

Keywords: *high-carbohydrate diet; tributyltin; liver; pancreas; pregnant.*

Funding: CNPq (307224/2021-0) and FAPES (Announcements No. 19/2022 and No. 03/2021).

CHRONIC INTERMITTENT CHLORPYRIFOS EXPOSURE LEADS TO HISTOMORPHOLOGICAL KIDNEY CHANGES AND CHOLINESTERASE INHIBITION IN RATS

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Introduction: Pre-clinical experimental studies have demonstrated histopathological alterations and renal dysfunction after subchronic and chronic continuous exposure to organophosphate (OP) compounds, such as chlorpyrifos (CPF), a widely used pesticide. However, the renal effects of intermittent exposure to this compound, a pattern of exposure that resembles the exposure commonly experienced by rural workers, remain under-investigated. In this context, the present study evaluated the effects of intermittent exposure to CPF on histomorphological parameters in male Wistar rats. **Material and methods:** Male Wistar rats (12 weeks; 200-300g) were used (CEUA/UFES n° 05/2025). Rats received either NaCl 0,9% (Control group - SAL) or CPF (7 or 10 mg/kg), three times per week for 4 weeks. At the end of the treatment period, rats were decapitated and blood and kidney samples were taken. The left kidney was processed for histological analysis to assess morphological alterations (Hematoxylin and eosin - HE) and possible collagen deposition (*Picrosirius Red*), while the right kidney alongside with blood samples were reserved for biochemical analysis of activity of acetylcholinesterase (AChE) and butyrylcholinesterase (BuChE) in renal tissue as well as erythrocyte AChE and plasmatic BuChE. Statistical analyses were performed using GraphPad Prism software (v. 8.0.2). The significance level was set at $p < 0.05$. Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM), and histomorphological alterations were reported in both descriptive and semi-quantitative way. Nonparametric data were analyzed using the Kruskal–Wallis test, while parametric data were analyzed by one-way ANOVA followed, when appropriate, by Dunnett’s post hoc test. **Results:** Histological analysis of renal tissue stained with HE coloring revealed preserved architecture in the Control Group without traces of degenerative alterations. In contrast, in CPF-treated groups significant

tissue damage was observed, such as Bowman's capsule space reduction, mild tubular narrowing, and mononuclear cell infiltration, in dose-dependent manner. Quantitative analysis of type I renal collagen deposition revealed a higher percentage in CPF-treated groups compared to Control (%Area: SAL, 1.94% [n=6]; CPF7, 3.60% [n=6]; CPF10, 2.53% [n=6]). Inhibition of cholinesterase activity after CPF treatment was observed for erythrocyte AChE ($p < 0.01$), plasmatic BuChE ($p < 0.01$), and renal AChE ($p < 0.05$), except for renal BuChE ($p > 0.05$). **Conclusion:** The results indicate that chronic intermittent exposure to CPF promotes histological damage to renal tissue, along with inhibition of erythrocyte and renal AChE and plasmatic BuChE. Moreover, these findings are expected to contribute to a better understanding of CPF effects in the context of chronic intermittent exposure.

Keywords: Organophosphate. Kidney. Chlorpyrifos. Intermittent.

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EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTS OF INTERMITTENT EXPOSURE TO THE INSECTICIDE CHLORPYRIFOS ON HEPATIC HISTOMORPHOLOGICAL ALTERATIONS

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Introduction: Chlorpyrifos (CPF) is one of the most widely used organophosphate (OP) compounds worldwide. Experimental studies suggest that chronic continuous exposure leads to toxin accumulation in the liver, resulting in pathological alterations. Therefore, this project aimed to evaluate the hepatic histomorphological effects of intermittent CPF exposure in adult male Wistar rats. **Materials and Methods:** All protocols were approved by the Ethics Committee on Animal Use, UFES (CEUA-UFES, 05/2023). Adult male Wistar rats (12 weeks, 200–300 g) received CPF (7 or 10 mg/kg) or saline intraperitoneally, three times per week for four weeks. Body weight was monitored. Blood and liver samples were collected post-euthanasia to quantify erythrocyte acetylcholinesterase (AChE), plasmatic butyrylcholinesterase (BuChE), and hepatic AChE and BuChE. Liver fragments were processed for histomorphological analysis, and relative liver mass was calculated as liver weight (g) / tibia length (cm). Data analysis and graph construction were performed using GraphPad Prism version 8.0.2 for Windows (GraphPad Software®, San Diego, California, USA). Histomorphological data were analyzed descriptively and semi-quantitatively. Numerical data are presented as mean ± standard error of the mean (SEM), with significance set at $p < 0.05$. Data normality was verified and parametric data were analyzed by one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's post-hoc test when appropriate, and non-parametric data were analyzed using the Kruskal-Wallis test. **Results:** CPF exposure significantly reduced erythrocyte AChE (mU/ μ mol Hb) in both treated groups versus controls ($p < 0.01$). Plasma BuChE (μ mol/min/L) and hepatic AChE (μ mol/h/mg protein) and BuChE (μ mol/min/mg protein) were also significantly inhibited by CPF at the doses of 7 and 10 mg/kg ($p < 0.01$). Body weight gain decreased significantly in the 10 mg/kg group ($p < 0.01$), while relative liver

mass remained unchanged. Livers of control rats displayed preserved architecture with uniform hepatocyte cords and sinusoids. CPF-treated groups (7 and 10 mg/kg) showed sinusoidal dilation, hepatocyte cord disorganization, focal mononuclear infiltrates, and increased binucleated hepatocytes in the 10 mg/kg group ($p < 0.01$). **Conclusion:** Intermittent CPF exposure markedly inhibited AChE and BuChE in blood and liver, confirming their sensitivity as OP toxicity biomarkers. Reduced body weight suggests systemic effects on food intake, whereas unchanged relative liver mass indicates no gross hypertrophy or atrophy. Histomorphological changes, including sinusoidal dilation, hepatocyte cord disorganization, and focal mononuclear infiltrates, suggest vascular congestion and inflammatory responses, demonstrating CPF's hepatotoxic potential under intermittent exposure. These findings reinforce CPF exposure risk to liver morphology even under non-continuous exposure scenarios.

Keywords: Organophosphate. Chlorpyrifos. Intermittent intoxication. Hepatic.

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INTERMITTENT SUBCHRONIC EXPOSURE TO CHLORPYRIFOS ALTERS WATER INTAKE AND UREA LEVELS WITHOUT MAJOR IMPAIRMENT OF RENAL FUNCTION IN ADULT FEMALE WISTAR RATS

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Introduction: Chlorpyrifos (CPF), a widely used organophosphate (OF), produces a highly toxic and lipophilic metabolite, capable of diffusing into different tissues, including the kidneys, which may compromise its function. The analysis of the biochemical profile through biomarkers in plasma and urine helps in the evaluation of the impact of the CPF on the health of this organ. In addition, studies in the literature have already demonstrated sex-specific differences in metabolization and physiological responses to xenobiotic intoxication but there are few studies in females, particularly after CPF exposure, reinforcing the importance of this work. Therefore, the present study aimed to evaluate the effects of subchronic exposure to CPF on renal markers in female rats. **Material and methods:** Adult female Wistar rats aged between 8 and 12 weeks, weighing between 200-300g (CEUA n° 04/2024) were used. The animals were divided into three groups: CPF-7 (7mg/kg of CPF; n=8), CPF-10 (10mg/kg of CPF; n=8) and control group (saline, NaCl, 0.9%; n=8). The animals received intraperitoneal (i.p.) injections, three times a week, on alternate days, for 28 days. At the end of exposure, the rats were housed individually in metabolic cages, allowing the control of water intake and urine collection (ml/24h). The plasma samples were derived from whole blood collected after euthanasia. The renal markers were analyzed by the method as indicated in the product package insert. Biochemical markers quantified were creatinine (mg/dl; mg/24h), urea (mg/dl), sodium and potassium (mmol/L or mEq/24h), microalbuminuria (mg/24h). From these measurements it was possible to estimate creatinine clearance (CICr; mL/min), blood urea nitrogen (BUN; mg/ml) and BUN/creatinine ratio (mg/dl). Comparisons between groups were performed using one-way ANOVA, followed by Dunnet's post-hoc test. Data were expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM) and the level of significance was set at $p < 0.05$. **Results:** Our results showed that there was a difference in water intake between the CPF-7 group and the control group (28,89 x 20,25, $p < 0.01$, ml/24h), with lower consumption in the intoxicated group. Urea levels in the CPF-7 group were higher than in the control group (40.13 x 59.86, $p < 0.05$, mg/dl) and lower than in the CPF-10 group (59,86 x 40,50, $p < 0.05$, mg/dl). There was no statistical difference in the other parameters evaluated. **Conclusion:** In summary, intermittent subchronic exposure to low doses of CPF did not result in marked changes

in biochemical markers of renal function in female rats. However, further studies are needed, as sex-related factors may lead to distinct renal outcomes under similar exposure conditions, and hormonal influences could further modulate the susceptibility to intoxication.

Keywords: Chlorpyrifos; Females; Intermittent; Renal Function; Biochemical parameters.

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CHRONIC INTERMITTENT EXPOSURE TO CHLORPYRIFOS REDUCES KIDNEY FUNCTION IN MALE WISTAR RATS

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Introduction: Preclinical studies have shown that intermittent exposure to chlorpyrifos (CPF), a widely used organophosphate (OP) insecticide, impaired cardiovascular reflexes and induced cardiac hypertrophy associated with increased oxidative stress in male rats. However, the effects of this same exposure pattern on renal function remain unknown. Therefore, this study seeks to provide evidence of the effects of intermittent exposure on renal function in male rats. **Materials and Methods:** Wistar male rats at 12 weeks of age weighing approximately 300 g were injected intraperitoneally for 4 weeks, intermittently, with saline (SAL) or CPF at doses of 7 mg/kg (CPF7) and 10 mg/kg (CPF10). The animals were placed in a metabolic cage for 3 days during the last week of treatment to obtain the values of food intake (mg/24h), volume of water intake and urine excreted (ml/24h). After the treatment period, the animals were euthanized by decapitation and kidney samples (N=8) were collected for acetylcholinesterase (AChE) determination and blood samples (N=6-8) for evaluation of creatinine, urea, sodium (Na⁺) and potassium (K⁺) by enzymatic kinetic method, according to the manufacturer's instructions. In addition, 24-hour urine samples (N=6-8) for evaluation of creatinine, Na⁺, K⁺ and microalbuminuria by digital flame photometer. Blood urea nitrogen (BUN) levels, BUN/creatinine ratio and creatinine clearance (Cl_{cr}) were subsequently calculated. Data was analyzed by One-way ANOVA followed by Dunnet's *post hoc* test. All data are presented as means ± standard error of mean and level of significance was set as p<0.05 (Project Ethical Committee Approval n° 05/2023). **Results:** Intoxication with CPF significantly reduced AChE activity in relation to the control group (0.03±0.005 x 0.05±0.005, umol/h/mg protein). CPF10 increased the levels of urea (74.5±5.9 x 43±1.4, mg/dl), BUN (34.8±2.7 x 20.1±0.6, mg/dl), creatinine (2.3±0.1 x 1.7±0.1, mg/dl), Na⁺ (145.3±0.7 x 141.5±0.8, mEq/L) and K⁺ (5±0.2 x 4.3±0.1, mEq/L) in the blood and reduced Cl_{cr} (7.7±0.7 x 10.8±1.1, ml/min) and urinary Na⁺ (126.4±10.8 x 178.1±7.9, mEq/24h), in relation to the SAL. BUN/creatinine ratio was elevated only in CPF7 (17.7±0.7 x 12.4±0.8, mg/dl). **Conclusion:** Intermittent subchronic CPF exposure impaired renal function in male rats, suggesting potential risks for populations occupationally exposed in an intermittent manner.

Keywords: Chlorpyrifos; Kidney; Intermittent; Male; Wistar.

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PROTECTIVE POTENTIAL OF SELENIUM IN MITIGATING MERCURY-INDUCED TOXICOGENETIC ALTERATIONS

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Introduction: Mercury (Hg) is a highly toxic metal that poses significant risks to human and environmental health due to its ability to bioaccumulate and biomagnify through food webs, making fish consumption an important source of exposure. Once absorbed, Hg can induce various deleterious effects, including oxidative stress that may lead to genetic and cellular damage. In contrast, selenium (Se) is an essential metalloid that plays a vital role in maintaining cellular homeostasis and antioxidant defense, particularly as a component of selenoenzymes such as glutathione peroxidase. Several studies have demonstrated that Se can exert a protective effect against Hg toxicity when the molar ratio of Se:Hg exceeds 1, suggesting a potential antagonistic interaction between these elements. In this context, the present study aimed to evaluate whether Se can mitigate the toxicogenetic effects of Hg in juvenile Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). We hypothesized that Se supplementation would reduce the genotoxic and mutagenic alterations induced by Hg exposure. **Methods:** This study was approved by the Animal Use Ethics Committee (CEUA–UFES; Protocol No. 018/2020). Juvenile *O. niloticus* (5 - 15 g) were exposed for 96 hours to the following concentrations: Se (10, 50, and 250 µg/L), Hg (0.2, 2.0, and 20 µg/L), and combined Se + Hg (10 + 0.2, 50 + 2.0, and 250 + 20 µg/L). At the end of the exposure period, fish were anesthetized with benzocaine (100 mg/L), and blood samples were collected via caudal puncture. Smears were prepared on glass slides, stained, and analyzed microscopically. Erythrocytes were examined for nuclear abnormalities, which were classified as genotoxic (binucleated, blebbed, lobed, or notched nuclei) or mutagenic (presence of micronuclei). Data were analyzed using the non-parametric Mann–Whitney test ($p < 0.0001$) with BioEstat 5.0 software. Results were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation of the number of altered cells per treatment. **Results:** Exposure to Hg significantly increased the incidence of genotoxic alterations at all tested concentrations, whereas Se exposure alone did not induce such effects. However, Se exposure led to a higher frequency of mutagenic alterations. Similarly, Hg exposure increased the frequency of mutagenic changes, except at the highest concentration tested. Notably, the combined exposure to Se + Hg resulted in a marked reduction in both genotoxic and mutagenic alterations compared to exposures to Hg or Se alone. **Conclusion:** The reduction in genotoxic and mutagenic alterations under combined Se + Hg exposure suggests that Se may exert a protective effect by enhancing antioxidant enzyme activity and reducing Hg-induced oxidative stress. Given that Hg toxicity is largely mediated by oxidative damage, the presence of Se likely decreased the formation of reactive oxygen species, thereby mitigating Hg's toxicogenetic effects. Further investigations assessing oxidative stress biomarkers and the activity of Se-dependent antioxidant enzymes are

warranted to elucidate the molecular mechanisms underlying the protective interaction between Se and Hg.

Keywords: Hg; Micronuclei; Nuclear Alterations; Se; Toxicity.

TOXIC EFFECTS OF TRIBUTYL TIN AND CADMIUM CO-EXPOSURE ON THE REPRODUCTIVE AXIS IN WISTAR RATS

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Abstract:

Daily exposure to chemicals in water and food poses risks to human health. Cadmium (Cd) and tributyltin (TBT) are known for their harmful effects on the endocrine system, as well as on female reproductive health, acting as endocrine-disrupting chemicals. However, the effects of co-exposure (Cd+TBT) to these substances remain poorly understood. This study aimed to investigate the impact of co-exposure on the reproductive axis of Wistar rats (8–10 weeks). Rats were divided into two groups: control (CON, n=9) at doses of saline and treated with TBT+Cd (MIX, n=10), at doses of 100 ng/kg/day and 100 mg/L. The estrous cycle was monitored for 15 days. After treatment, tissues were histologically analyzed using H&E and Alcian Blue, and hormone levels were measured by ELISA kits. The study was approved by CEUA-UFES (04/2023). Data were expressed as mean \pm SEM. Exposure to MIX resulted in increased uterine weight (CON: 0.39 ± 0.029 ; MIX: 0.48 ± 0.020 , $p < 0.05$) and reduced ovarian weight (CON: 0.13 ± 0.006 ; MIX: 0.11 ± 0.007 , $p < 0.05$). Estrous cycle duration was shorter (CON: 7.16 ± 0.59 ; MIX: 5.65 ± 0.28 , $p < 0.05$), with reduced proestrus phase (CON: 2.23 ± 0.36 ; MIX: 0.93 ± 0.06 , $p < 0.05$). Estrogen and testosterone levels decreased (E2: CON: 29 ± 3.16 ; MIX: 19 ± 2.86 ; T: CON: 0.60 ± 0.04 ; MIX: 0.33 ± 0.02 , $p < 0.05$). The ovarian reserve was reduced (CON: 0.31 ± 0.04 ; MIX: 0.11 ± 0.02 , $p < 0.05$), along with fewer corpora lutea (CON: 0.29 ± 0.07 ; MIX: 0.11 ± 0.03 , $p < 0.05$). Uterine analysis showed increased myometrium and luminal epithelium thickness (CON: 1.36 ± 0.07 ; MIX: 1.74 ± 0.06 ; CON: 15.6 ± 1.1 ; MIX: 20.8 ± 1.4 , $p < 0.05$), and reduced endometrial area (CON: 0.57 ± 0.04 ; MIX: 0.49 ± 0.007 , $p < 0.05$). Mast cell increase indicated ovarian inflammation (CON: 0.40 ± 0.19 ; MIX: 1.29 ± 0.23 , $p < 0.05$) and uterus (CON: 0.0009 ± 0.0002 ; MIX: 2.32 ± 0.40 , $p < 0.05$). Serum Cd showed positive correlations with estrogen ($r=0.8$) and progesterone receptors ($r=0.8$), and a negative correlation with testosterone ($r=-0.8$), although without statistical significance. Serum Sn correlated moderately with FSH ($r=0.7$) and the proestrus phase ($r=0.7$), also without significance. In contrast, Cd showed a significant

negative correlation with the thickness of the external myometrium ($r=-0.9$; $p=0.04$) and with $ER\alpha$ expression in the endometrium ($r=-1$; $p=0.04$) Serum Sn did not show statistically relevant correlations with the evaluated uterine parameters.. These findings demonstrate that co-exposure to MIX has detrimental effects on reproductive structure and function in female rats. These findings demonstrate that co-exposure to MIX has detrimental effects on reproductive structure and function in female rats.

Keywords: Cadmium, endocrine disruptor, heavy metals, female reproduction, tributyltin.

Founding: FAPES, CNPq.

SEX-SPECIFIC EFFECTS OF ACUTE CHLORPYRIFOS POISONING IN YOUNG NORMOTENSIVE AND PRE- HYPERTENSIVE RATS

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Introduction: Brazil is one of the leading countries in terms of pesticide sales and consumption, including organophosphorus compounds (OPs). The increasing rate of use of these substances is associated with a rise in cases of acute poisoning among children and adults. Chlorpyrifos (CPF), a highly toxic pesticide, is one of the most widely used OPs. Its primary mechanism of action involves the inhibition of acetylcholinesterase (AChE) and butyrylcholinesterase (BChE). These enzymes hydrolyze acetylcholine (ACh), and their inhibition leads to the accumulation of this neurotransmitter, triggering acute cholinergic syndrome. Study demonstrated that hypertension is a risk factor for worse outcomes in OP poisoning. It remains to be determined whether a genetic predisposition to hypertension might also increase susceptibility. Moreover, due to the limited number of preclinical studies conducted in females, little is known about sex-specific differences in OP toxicity. **Materials and Methods:** 28-day-old male and female rats, ~100 g, from Wistar, spontaneously hypertensive (SHR) and Wistar Kyoto (WKY) strains were treated with CPF 30 mg/kg or 3% DMSO. Acute toxicity signs, such as salivation, lacrimation, motor coordination, exploratory activity and motor dysfunction, were monitored up to 4 hours post-exposure and 24 hours after treatment, plasma BChE and erythrocyte AChE activities were measured. Acute toxicity data were analyzed using simple ordinal logistic regression. The effects of CPF on enzymatic activities were analyzed by three-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). Comparisons of enzyme inhibition and basal cholinesterase were analyzed using two-way ANOVA. The significance level was set at $p < 0.05$. ANOVA analyses were followed by Tukey's post hoc test, when appropriate, and all data were checked for outliers and subjected to normality tests. Ethics approval numbers for animal use were registered by the Ethics Committee on Animal Use of Federal University of Espírito Santo under numbers 17/2022 and 04/2024. **Results:** CPF induced more frequent and severe signs of toxicity in pre-hypertensive rats compared to normotensive rats and in males compared to females. CPF exposure inhibited BChE activity across all sexes and strains, except in SHR males, which didn't show statistically significant BChE inhibition following CPF exposure. Wistar animals exhibited higher basal BChE activity than SHR animals for each respective sex. CPF exposure inhibited AChE activity in males of all strains but didn't affect AChE activity in Wistar and SHR females. Across all strains, males exhibited higher basal AChE activity than females. **Conclusion:** The findings from this study suggest that a genetic predisposition to hypertension may represent a risk factor for the exacerbation of OP poisoning outcomes and that males are more susceptible to CPF-induced toxicity than females.

Keywords: Organophosphates; Chlorpyrifos; Toxicity; Hypertension; Sex differences.

Funding: Federal University of Espírito Santo; Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa e Inovação do Espírito Santo (FAPES, Grant Codes: 2022- 78KWB; 749/2024), CNPq/FAPES 2025-H5S1W; CNPq/MCTI/FNDCT N° 44/2024. VFC was a recipient of UFES scholarship (PIBIC UFES); KBS was a recipient of FAPES scholarship; BFS, VSM were recipients of CAPES scholarship (Grant codes 01).

USE OF OVER-THE-COUNTER PSYCHO-STIMULANTS BY MEDICAL STUDENTS: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

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Introduction: Medical students are exposed to significant challenges, such as an extensive workload, high performance expectations, and the necessity to balance theory, practice, personal life, extracurricular activities, and exposure to human pain and suffering from the onset of their university training. This environment contributes to high levels of stress, physical and mental fatigue, and anxiety. Therefore, in an effort to maintain productivity and cope with academic demands, many students use over-the-counter psycho-stimulants (OTC-PS), such as caffeine and energy drinks, to increase alertness, reduce sleepiness, and extend study time. However, this practice raises concerns about the impacts on physical and mental health and the quality of medical training, which should emphasize holistic care, including for the students themselves. This study aims to analyze the patterns of use, frequency, risks, and adverse effects associated with the consumption of OTC-PS by medical students from a higher education institution in Minas Gerais state. **Methods:** This observational, descriptive cross-sectional study collected data between May and October 2024, using an anonymous, self-administered online questionnaire at a higher education institution. The research instrument contained questions about the consumption habits of OTC-PS, and all medical students were invited to participate. The study was approved by the Research Ethics Committee (Certificate of presentation for ethical appreciation 65661522.1.0000.5157). **Results:** Of the 236 participants, 222 (94.1%) reported using OTC-PS, and 134 (56.8%) stated they consumed these substances daily. Furthermore, 77 (32.6%) reported continuously increasing their consumption after starting the course, while 70 (29.7%) increased use specifically during examination periods. The high prevalence observed among medical students may be strongly associated with the intense workload, marked by long study periods and practical activities, often accompanied by sleep deprivation and physical and mental exhaustion. The constant pressure for results and the neglect of self-care seem to contribute to the search for quick fixes, such as OTC-PS, which are easily acquired due to their wide availability and lack of medical prescription. This scenario highlights the urgent need to discuss student well-being and the normalization of this use, which occurs primarily during critical periods of the academic calendar. A notable finding was the high frequency of adverse effects among OTC-PS users, with the most common being insomnia, agitation, and tachycardia. Additionally, the fact that half of the participants reported withdrawal symptoms upon discontinuing use, such as headache, drowsiness, and mood swings, suggests the possibility of a continuous use cycle and functional dependence, where students become reliant on these substances to cope with the demands of medical training. **Conclusion:** The frequent use of OTC-PS among medical students highlights physical and mental exhaustion as well as structural failures in medical education, which is characterized by high demand and little support for student well-being. The normalization of consumption and the low perception of risk reinforce the urgency of institutional strategies that promote mental health, self-care, welcoming environments,

and active listening, thus fostering a more humanized education where the student is also a target of care.

Keywords: Central nervous system stimulants, caffeine, medical education.

Financial support: Univale.

NEUTROPENIA IN BREAST CANCER: EFFECTS OF CHEMOTHERAPY AND INFLUENCE OF LIFESTYLE-RELATED RISK FACTORS

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Introduction: Breast cancer (BC) is a disease involving the interaction of genetic, environmental, and lifestyle factors that contribute to both the onset and progression of the cancer. One of the most commonly used treatments for women with BC is chemotherapy, which directly targets cells with rapid division characteristics, such as hematopoietic tissue. Among the possible side effects of chemotherapy, neutropenia stands out, characterized by a sharp decrease in neutrophils and classified as mild (1,000 to 1,500/ μ L), moderate (500 to 999/ μ L), or severe (below 500/ μ L), potentially leading to death. Therefore, the present study aims to investigate the relationship between risk factors such as alcohol consumption, smoking, and cancer staging, as well as neutrophil levels before and after treatment. **Materials and Methods:** The study was conducted at the Capixaba Oncology Center (CECON) between 2016 and 2018, evaluating 152 women. Part of the study was retrospective, collecting clinical-epidemiological data, blood pressure, presence of comorbidities, and neutrophil values during treatment from patient records of those diagnosed with breast cancer who received highly cytotoxic chemotherapeutic regimens, including combinations such as AC-T (doxorubicin, cyclophosphamide, and paclitaxel), TC (docetaxel and cyclophosphamide), 5FU (protocols using 5-fluorouracil), and PLATINS (protocols using carboplatin or cisplatin). This study was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the Federal University of Espírito Santo (CEP-UFES) – Approval Number: 2.186.172/2017. The obtained data were expressed as absolute and relative frequencies, presented through boxplots, and the paired Wilcoxon test was used to compare continuous variables pre- and post-intervention. The clinical cutoff adopted to identify neutropenia was 1,500 cells per mm^3 . Associations between the presence of neutropenia and categorical variables such as hypertension, alcohol consumption, and smoking were analyzed using Pearson's Chi-Square test. When the expected frequency was below 5, Fisher's exact test was used. For all analyses, a significance level of $p < 0.05$ and a 95% confidence interval were considered. **Results:** Among the women undergoing chemotherapy, 10.5% presented neutropenia during follow-up. The occurrence of neutropenia showed no statistically significant association with hypertension ($p = 0.834$), alcohol consumption ($p = 0.212$), or smoking ($p = 0.676$), indicating that these factors did not significantly influence neutrophil reduction. Analysis of physiological and hematological variables revealed no significant differences in body mass index (BMI) ($p = 0.621$), weight ($p = 0.555$), or diastolic blood pressure (DBP) ($p = 0.0838$) between pre- and post-treatment. In contrast, systolic blood pressure (SBP) showed a significant reduction after chemotherapy ($p = 0.000194$), suggesting a possible hemodynamic effect of the treatment. Regarding

hematological parameters, a significant decrease in total neutrophil count ($p = 0.0253$) was observed after treatment. **Conclusion:** These findings indicate that, although chemotherapy induced hematological changes compatible with neutropenia, factors such as alcohol consumption, smoking, and hypertension were not associated with its occurrence. These results reinforce the need for continuous hematological monitoring during treatment to minimize risks and ensure the therapeutic safety of patients.

Keywords: Breast cancer, chemotherapy, neutropenia, risk factors

EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTS OF BERBERINE ON COGNITIVE AND ANXIETY-LIKE BEHAVIORS AND ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF ETHANOL-INDUCED CONDITIONED PLACE PREFERENCE IN MICE

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Introduction: SUD is defined as a result of drug abuse, and its diagnosis is based on a pathological pattern of behaviors related to the use of the substance of abuse. Currently available treatments have limitations regarding efficacy, adherence, and tolerability, which generates the need to seek new therapeutic approaches. In this context, berberine emerges as a potential drug to be investigated in basic research applied to the study of SUD, since it interferes with neural pathways related to the reward mechanism linked to the use of psychotropic substances. Therefore, we sought to evaluate the effects of berberine on cognitive and anxiety-like behaviors and on the rewarding effects of ethanol.

Material and methods: *Experiment 1 (Plus-Maze Discriminative Avoidance Task – PMDAT):* In this experiment, 40 adults male C57BL6J animals were distributed into the following groups (n=8/group): SAL; ETH; BER2; BER10 and BER20. This protocol consisted of two phases: training (day 1) and testing (day 2). Saline, ethanol 1.8 g/kg and berberine at doses of 2, 10 and 20 mg/kg were administered intraperitoneally (ip) before training. In the training session, learning and anxiety-like behavior were assessed, while memory was analyzed on the test day. *Experiment 2 (Conditional Place Preference – CPP):* In this protocol, 33 adult male C57BL6J animals were distributed into the following experimental groups (n = 10-12/group): SAL-BER; ETH-VEH and ETH-BER. The experimental protocol consisted of 6 stages, namely: (1) Habituation (days 1-2); (2) Pre-conditioning test (day 3); (3) Conditioning (days 4-12); (4) Post-conditioning test (day 13); (5) Treatment (days 14-22); and (6) Post-treatment test (day 24). In the conditioning phase, the animals were treated with saline or ethanol 1.8 g/kg, via ip, while in the treatment phase, the animals received ip administrations of vehicle or berberine 10 mg/kg (CEUA/UFES no. 20/2024). **Results:** Experiment 1 (PMDAT): Ethanol, but not berberine, induced a learning deficit in the task [$F_{(4,35)}= 6.215$; $p=0.0007$], expressed by a longer exploration time of the aversive closed arm during the training session. During the test session, only the ETH group [$t_{(7)}=1.849$; $p=0.1070$] presented memory deficit, while the other groups presented avoidance behavior of the aversive compartment. In the test, the ETH and BER10 groups presented anxiolytic effect [$F_{(4,35)}=8.473$; $p<0.0001$; SAL x ETH ($p=0.0003$), SAL x BER10 ($p=0.0329$)], expressed by a longer exploration time of the open arms of the apparatus. Experiment 2 (CPP): Ethanol exposure in the ETH-VEH and ETH-BER groups was able to induce CPP expression in the post-conditioning test [$F_{(2,30)}=7.540$; $p=0.002$; SAL-BER x ETH-VEH ($p=0.002$) and SAL-BER x ETH-BER ($p=0.011$)], while berberine treatment was able to attenuate CPP during

the post-treatment test [$F_{(2,30)}=3.577$; $p=0.040$; SAL-BER x ETH-VEH ($p=0.041$); SAL-BER x ETH-BER ($p=0.119$)]. **Conclusion:** Berberine did not induce changes in learning or memory, but produced an anxiolytic effect when administered at a dose of 10 mg/kg. This same dose was able to attenuate the rewarding effects of ethanol in the ethanol-induced CPP model in mice.

Keywords: Ethanol; Berberine; Plus-Maze Discriminative Avoidance Task; Conditioned Place Preference; Alcohol Use Disorder.

Funding: Espírito Santo Research and Innovation Support Foundation (Fapes) and State Department of Education – Sedu/ES (n° 111/2025).

ISOFLURANE DOES NOT CHANGE PLASMATIC BUTYRYLCHOLINESTERASE ACTIVITY IN WISTAR RATS

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Introduction: Volatile anesthetics, such as isoflurane, are widely used in preclinical and clinical procedures. Although they ensure safety and comfort during procedures, they are not risk-free and have been associated with cardiovascular and respiratory alterations as well as cognitive impairment, effects partially attributed to autonomic imbalance. Evidence suggests that volatile anesthetics can influence the cholinergic system, but their role in modulating cholinesterase activity in a sex-specific manner remains unclear. Cholinesterases are responsible for acetylcholine hydrolysis. Butyrylcholinesterase (BuChE) is a cholinesterase present in blood plasma, and it is especially recognized as a biomarker of intoxication and inflammatory processes. **Materials and Methods:** The influence of isoflurane on plasmatic BuChE activity was investigated in 10-12 weeks Wistar rats under three experimental protocols (Ethical Committee Approval n°04/2024). Each protocol included male (n = 8) and female (n = 8) rats. Protocol 1: blood samples were collected before anesthesia (tail puncture), during femoral artery catheterization under isoflurane anesthesia (induction 4%, maintenance 2.5%), and 24 and 48 h after surgery. Protocol 2: Animals were anesthetized (induction 4%, maintenance 2.5%) and euthanized 48 h later for blood collection. Protocol 3: naïve animals were euthanized for blood sampling. Heparinized blood samples were centrifuged at 8.400 rpm/4° C for 10 min for plasma separation, and BuChE activity was determined by colorimetric assay. Data were analyzed by one-way ANOVA for repeated measures, followed by the Tukey post hoc test, with statistical significance set at p<0.05. **Results:** Plasmatic BuChE activity was significantly higher in females. In Protocol 1, no differences were observed between preoperative and postoperative (48 h) measurements in either sex. Across protocols, males BuChE activity was not affected by isoflurane. In females, BuChE activity was not different between protocols 2 and 3, but was significantly lower in Protocol 1 compared with Protocol 2 (p<0.05). **Conclusion:** Isoflurane did not interfere with plasmatic BuChE in both sexes. Given its widespread use in both clinical and preclinical settings, these findings may be promising, as they suggest an absence of direct

effects of isoflurane on this enzyme. Stress induced during tail puncture and surgery seems to have a more relevant impact on BuChE-activity than isoflurane. Once cholinesterases are distinctly distributed throughout the whole organism, the effects of isoflurane on other cholinesterases present in different tissues must be confirmed.

Keywords: Volatile Anesthetics; Isoflurane; Cholinergic System; Sex-Specific.

Financial Support: Federal University of Espírito Santo; Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa e Inovação do Espírito Santo (FAPES, Grant Codes: 2022 – 78KWB; 749/2024), CNPq/FAPES 2025-H5S1W; CNPq/MCTI/FNDCT N° 44/2024. PBSA; BML; KBS. were recipients of FAPES scholarship (Grant Codes). BFS; GGN; LJC and VSM were recipients of CAPES scholarship (Grant Code 01). AB was recipient of UFES scholarship (PIBIC UFES).

IN SILICO AND IN VITRO EVIDENCE OF KETAMINE AND XYLAZINE INTERACTION WITH CHOLINESTERASES

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Introduction: General anesthetics are widely used in pre-clinical studies and clinical practices. Ketamine and Xylazine (K/X) are anesthetics commonly used in veterinary procedures, even though these compounds can cause disturbance in homeostasis and autonomic balance, which are closely associated with changes in cardiovascular, respiratory, cognitive, and inflammatory regulation. Different mechanisms have been proposed for understanding how K/X may interfere with autonomic system, but their role in the cholinergic system and in cholinesterases activity remains unclear. Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) and Butyrylcholinesterase (BuChE) are cholinesterases responsible for acetylcholine (ACh) hydrolysis, and they are distinctly distributed in organisms. While AChE is strictly related to ACh hydrolysis, BuChE hydrolyzes multiple substrates, including ACh, and both enzymes have been recognized as biomarkers in organophosphate intoxication. This study aimed to evaluate the potential binding of K/X to AChE and BuChE using molecular docking and to confirm these interactions through *in vitro* assays. **Materials and Methods:** The enzymes were prospected from PDB (AChE: 7XN1; BuChE: 4BDS), both complexed with tacrine, which was removed and pH adjusted to 7.4 using APBS-PDB2PQR website program. Ketamine isomers (R/S) and Xylazine were obtained from PubChem and subsequently optimized and protonated to pH 7.4 using Avogadro 1.90.0. For both enzymes, docking coordinates were the same as the original complex, defining a 10 Å radius around the binding site. Validation was conducted through redocking of tacrine, and only results with RMSD ≤ 2 Å were accepted. Discovery Studio (BioVia, 2024) was used for bidimensional and tridimensional visualization. *In vitro* assays were performed to confirm *in silico* results using blood samples of control male Wistar rats (CEUA Protocolo Approval n° 17/2023). Both cholinesterase activity from plasma (BuChE) and erythrocyte (AChE) was analysed by the colorimetric method. Serial dilutions of Ketamine or Xylazine were tested, and enzyme activity was compared to control assays without anesthetics. Statistical analyses were carried out in GraphPad Prism 8.0.2, and ANOVA for repeated measures was used, followed by Tukey's test when appropriate. Statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$. **Results:** Fitness score were as follows: R-Ketamine, 58.50 for AChE and 49.62 for BuChE; S-Ketamine, 58.50 for AChE and 47.2 for BuChE; Xylazine, 59.71 for AChE and 49.79 for BuChE. *In vitro*, AChE inhibition was observed with Ketamine and xylazine at concentrations of 0.0263 μM and 0.35 μM , respectively ($p < 0.01$). BuChE inhibition was observed from 0.0263 μM for ketamine and 0.035 μM for xylazine ($p=0.05$). **Conclusion:** The *in silico* results demonstrated that both anesthetics interact with AChE and BuChE,

which was corroborated by *in vitro* assays. These findings suggest that K/X can interfere with cholinesterase activity and may potentially affect the systemic cholinergic tone.

Keywords: General Anesthetics; Ketamine; Xylazine; Cholinergic System; Docking.

Financial Support: Federal University of Espírito Santo; Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa e Inovação do Espírito Santo (FAPES, Grant Codes: 2022 – 78KWB; 749/2024), CNPq/FAPES 2025-H5S1W; CNPq/MCTI/FNDCT N° 44/2024. PBSA; BML; KBS. were recipients of FAPES scholarship (Grant Codes). BFS; GGN; LJC and VSM were recipients of CAPES scholarship (Grant Code 01).

EFFECTS OF ZINC SUPPLEMENTATION ON THE PREVENTION OF VASCULAR DAMAGE INDUCED BY SUBCHRONIC CADMIUM EXPOSURE IN RATS

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Introduction

Cadmium (Cd) is a heavy metal and environmental pollutant has been associated with several cardiovascular disorders, including hypertension, atherosclerosis, peripheral arterial disease, and heart failure. The vascular injury caused by Cd exposure is primarily attributed to the induction of oxidative stress and endothelial dysfunction. Zinc (Zn), in turn, is an essential trace element with well-established antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. It can compete with Cd for binding sites on enzymes and cellular transporters, thereby mitigating Cd-induced cellular toxicity. In this context, the present study investigated the effects of Zn supplementation on CdCl₂-induced alterations in vascular reactivity in rat thoracic aortic rings, employing phenylephrine (Phe)-induced contractile responses and pharmacological interventions to elucidate the underlying physiological mechanisms.

Material and Methods

Male Wistar rats (8 weeks old) were randomly assigned to four groups: Control (Ct); Cadmium (Cd, CdCl₂ 100 ppm via drinking water); Zinc (Zn, 5 mg/kg/day i.p.); and Cd + Zinc (CdZn, CdCl₂ + Zn). Vehicle was administered to the groups that did not receive Zinc (0.9% NaCl i.p.). After 30 days of treatment, the animals were anesthetized with ketamine/xylazine (i.p.). The thoracic aorta was isolated, perivascular adipose tissue was removed, cut into rings, and mounted in organ baths to evaluate changes in arterial wall tension induced by cumulative concentrations of the α_1 -adrenergic agonist phenylephrine (N=15-25). All procedures were approved by CEUA/UFES (no. 01/2024). Data were expressed as mean \pm SEM and were analyzed by two-way ANOVA followed by Tukey or Fisher post-test ($p < 0.05$).

Results

The Cd group exhibited an increased vasoconstrictor response to phenylephrine compared to the control, while Zn treatment prevented this effect (E_{max}: Ct: 97.6 \pm 2.7; Cd: 124 \pm 3.1; Zn: 95 \pm 2.2; CdZn: 99 \pm 1.8). The Zn group did not differ from the control under any condition tested ($p > 0.05$).

Incubation with Tiron reduced the vasoconstrictor response only in the Cd group (E_{max} Ct: 87 \pm 3.0; Cd: 84 \pm 2.6; CdZn: 87 \pm 3.1), pointing to superoxide anion as a mediator of Cd-induced hypercontractility, which was prevented by Zn treatment. Incubation with catalase did not alter vascular reactivity to phenylephrine in any of the groups studied (E_{max} Ct: 116 \pm 3.9; Cd: 110 \pm 2.6; CdZn: 103 \pm 3.7). Incubation with L-NAME increased vasoconstriction in all groups (E_{max} Ct: 169 \pm 2.8; Cd: 159 \pm 3.7; CdZn: 160 \pm 3.2), with no important differences between them. Endothelium removal also enhanced the vasoconstrictor response to phenylephrine in all groups. Analysis of the percentage

difference in the area under the curve ($\Delta\text{AUC}\%$) revealed a reduction in endothelial modulation in the Cd group (Ct: 142 ± 27 ; Cd: 58 ± 14 ; CdZn: 122 ± 12), consistent with endothelial dysfunction that was prevented by Zn treatment.

Conclusion

Zinc supplementation prevented the vascular hyperreactivity and endothelial dysfunction induced by chronic cadmium exposure in rats. These findings suggest that zinc exerts a vasoprotective effect, likely by reducing oxidative stress—particularly superoxide anion production—and preserving endothelial modulation.

Keywords: Cadmium; Zinc; Vascular Reactivity; Oxidative Stress; Endothelial dysfunction.

Financial support: FAPES, CAPES, CNPq.

THEMATIC AXIS VI

Bioactive Potential of Nature:
Sustainable Pathways for Health and Innovation

EVALUATION OF THE INHIBITORY POTENTIAL OF α -AMYLASE AND α -GLUCOSIDASE BY THE LEAF EXTRACT OF *EUGENIA ASTRINGENS* (MYRTACEAE)

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Introduction: Type 2 diabetes mellitus is characterized by postprandial hyperglycemia, which results from the rapid digestion and absorption of carbohydrates. The enzymes α -amylase and α -glucosidase play a key role in this process, making them key therapeutic targets for glycemic control. Although synthetic drugs such as acarbose, miglitol, and voglibose are effective, their adverse effects justify the search for natural alternatives. Species of the genus *Eugenia* (Myrtaceae), known to be rich in phenolic compounds, flavonoids, and terpenes, have demonstrated inhibitory potential against these enzymes. The aim of this study was to evaluate the ability of *Eugenia astringens* to inhibit enzymes involved in carbohydrate metabolism, as well as to investigate the chemical composition of this species. **Materials and Methods:** Methanolic extract from *E. astringens* leaves (EMF) was prepared and subjected to in vitro spectrophotometric assays to assess its inhibitory potential against α -amylase and α -glucosidase. Chemical characterization was performed using Electrospray Fourier Transform Ion Cyclotron Resonance Mass Spectrometry (ESI(-/+)) FT-ICR MS). **Results:** In the α -amylase assay, EMF at a concentration of 1 mg/mL exhibited $87.57 \pm 0.83\%$ inhibition (acarbose standard: $98.62 \pm 1.06\%$). Regarding α -glucosidase inhibition, EMF showed $98.69 \pm 0.47\%$ inhibition at 250 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, with an IC_{50} of 34.28 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (deoxynojirimycin standard IC_{50} : 28.83 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). The compounds gallic acid, methyl gallate, quercetin, quercitrin, myricetin, luteolin, betulinic acid, corosolic acid, maslinic acid, and glycyrrhethinic acid were identified in *E. astringens*, which may be associated with its inhibitory activity against α -amylase and α -glucosidase. **Conclusion:** The leaf extract of *E. astringens* demonstrated significant inhibitory activity against α -amylase and α -glucosidase. Therefore, this species represents a promising source of bioactive compounds for the treatment of type 2 diabetes, particularly given its traditional use in glycemic control.

Keywords: *Eugenia astringens*, α -amylase, α -glucosidase, diabetes, glycemic control.

Funding: UFES, UNB, CAPES.

THE NON-CONVENTIONAL FOOD PLANT (PANC) *XANTHOSOMA SAGITTIFOLIUM* (L.) SCHOTT (TAIOBA) AS A SOURCE OF LECTINS WITH ANTITUMOR POTENTIAL

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The Non-Conventional Food Plant (PANC) *Xanthosoma sagittifolium* (L.) Schott (taioba) is a monocotyledon of the Araceae family and *Xanthosoma* genus. Its leaves exhibit notable nutritional properties, containing a satisfactory amount of total fiber and a protein content comparable to that of the PANC Ora-pro-nóbis. Additionally, it is a rich source of iron, calcium, magnesium, vitamin C, and phenolic compounds. Extracts obtained from both leaves and roots have also demonstrated significant antiproliferative, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial potential. Given these attributes, taioba is an interesting target for proteomic and metabolomic studies to identify the molecules present in its leaves (and roots) and associate them with biologically relevant activities of biotechnological interest. In this context, the present study aims to purify and characterize lectins found in taioba leaves, as these proteins, due to their specific and reversible carbohydrate-binding capacity, are associated with the described biological activities. The purification process was monitored through hemagglutination assays and SDS-PAGE, revealing bands with a molecular mass ranging between 12–14 kDa, corresponding to the monomeric unit of lectins. Hemagglutinating fractions were obtained through sequential saline precipitation ($(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ at 15% and 35%) from the protein extract of leaves and roots. The 15% precipitated fraction from the leaf extract was selected for further purification using size-exclusion chromatography in an HPLC system, yielding two partially purified hemagglutinating fractions. The protein profile of these fractions displayed bands corresponding to the monomeric unit and its multiples, suggesting the formation of supramolecular arrangements, a common characteristic of lectins. These fractions were further analyzed by mass spectrometry (data not yet available). It was demonstrated that the fractions obtained after saline precipitation of the leaf extract (P15F and P35F) exhibited hemagglutination activity with specificity for mannose, without distinguishing ABO blood types. The hemagglutination activity of P15F was more effective at an optimal pH between 7.5 and 7.9 and a temperature of 37°C, showing dependence on magnesium ions. Using a resazurin-based cell viability assay, the hemagglutinating fractions – obtained from size-exclusion chromatography – exhibited dose-dependent cytotoxicity (~0.1 µg to 53 µg) against rat glioma (C6), human colon carcinoma (RKO), and human primary ovarian malignant adenocarcinoma (TOV-21G) cell lines, except for the human glioblastoma cell line (U373), reducing viability by up to 78%. Thus, in this study, two hemagglutinating fractions with cytotoxic potential were partially purified, representing the first steps toward their full biochemical and functional characterization, as well as the exploration of taioba's biotechnological potential.

Keywords: Xanthosoma sagittifolium (L.) Schott, PANC, lectins, antitumor activity.

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CHEMICAL ANALYSIS AND ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITIES OF LEAF AND FLOWER CRUDE EXTRACTS OF *HELENIMUM AMARUM*

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Introduction: Plants are extensively studied for their potential to treat diseases that lack an effective cure, such as cancer, considering the biological properties of their constituents and the variation of these compounds in different plant organs. The aim of this study was to determine the total contents of phenolic compounds, flavonoids, and tannins in ethanolic extracts from the leaves and flowers of *Helenium amarum*; to investigate their chemical profile through Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR); and to evaluate their antioxidant activities by DPPH and ABTS assays. **Materials and Methods:** Specimens of *H. amarum* acquired from the market in Vitória (Brazil) were used to prepare crude ethanolic extracts by exhaustive maceration of leaves and flowers. The extracts were analyzed for total phenolic compounds, flavonoids, and tannins through colorimetric assays with absorbance measured in an ELISA reader, and FTIR spectroscopy ($650\text{--}4000\text{cm}^{-1}$) and DPPH and ABTS assays for antioxidants activities. **Results:** The leaf extract showed a higher flavonoid content ($144.34\pm 3.95\ \mu\text{g/mL.Egg rutin}$) compared with the flower extract ($103.20\pm 4.06\ \mu\text{g/mL.Egg rutin}$). Total phenolic contents were very similar between organs: $48.209\pm 0.035\ \mu\text{g/mL.Egg gallic acid}$ in leaves and $48.051\pm 0.014\ \mu\text{g/mL.Egg gallic acid}$ in flowers. Tannin levels were also comparable, with $6.06\pm 0.003\ \mu\text{g/mL.Egg tannic acid}$ in leaves and $5.989\pm 0.001\ \mu\text{g/mL.Egg tannic acid}$ in flowers. FTIR analysis of the flower extract revealed an average spectrum with two intense peaks around 3000cm^{-1} (40–65% transmittance), suggesting strong absorption of alkanes and O–H/NH groups. This indicates higher concentrations of terpenes, flavonoids, and alkaloids in flowers. Lower absorption near 1700cm^{-1} suggested fewer carbonyl groups, while reduced transmittance between $500\text{--}1000\text{cm}^{-1}$ (85%) indicated minimal contribution of functional groups. In contrast, the leaf extract exhibited hydroxyl or amine groups ($3000\text{--}3500\text{cm}^{-1}$) with moderate absorption (~80% transmittance), aliphatic chains ($2900\text{--}3000\text{cm}^{-1}$), and signals associated with carbonyls or aromatic systems ($1500\text{--}2000\text{cm}^{-1}$). Strong C–O absorptions ($1000\text{--}1200\text{cm}^{-1}$) suggested presence of phenolic compounds, flavonoids, carboxylic acids or esters, aliphatic chains, and oxygenated compounds. Both extracts demonstrated high inhibition percentages in the ABTS method, even at the lowest tested concentrations (31.25 and $15.625\ \mu\text{g.mL}^{-1}$), indicating strong antioxidant potential. However, in the DPPH assay, both extracts showed weak inhibition, even at higher concentrations, suggesting selectivity toward specific mechanisms of radical scavenging. **Conclusion:** *H. amarum*

leaves contain a higher flavonoid content than flowers, along with slightly higher amounts of phenolic compounds and tannins. Leaves also presented greater concentrations of carbonyl and oxygenated compounds, such as flavonoids, esters, carboxylic acids, and phenols. Flowers showed a predominance of aliphatic compounds, terpenes, and a stronger contribution of alcohols or phenols. These findings are consistent with the known distribution of metabolites, since flowers typically accumulate volatile terpenes, while leaves store phenolic compounds and flavonoids. Overall, both extracts demonstrated strong activity in the ABTS assay, suggesting the presence of lipophilic and hydrophilic compounds. This activity may be influenced by sesquiterpene lactones, recognized as the main group of compounds in this species.

Keywords: phytochemistry, Asteraceae, antioxidants, sesquiterpene lactones.

Financial Support: Fapes – Research Support Foundation of Espírito Santo.

PRODUCTION OF BIOTECHNOLOGICALLY RELEVANT ENZYMES BY BACTERIA ISOLATED FROM A MANGROVE IN ESPÍRITO SANTO.

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Introduction

Mangroves are ecosystems of great ecological relevance, characterized by high biological diversity and the presence of microorganisms with biotechnological potential (Baskaran et al, 2023). Considering the scarcity of studies focused on the microbiota of mangroves in Espírito Santo, this study aimed to evaluate the functional biodiversity of bacteria isolated from these environments, with emphasis on the screening of enzymatic activities of biotechnological interest.

Methods

Soil samples collected at different depths from a mangrove area located in Guarapari/ES were processed and plated on BDA medium for bacterial isolation. The isolates were subsequently subjected to enzymatic assays for lipases, amylases, cellulases, and proteases in solid medium supplemented with specific substrates. For the determination of amylolytic activity, after bacterial growth on starch-containing medium, an iodine solution was added, producing a blue coloration (complex formation with starch) (Hankin & Anagnostakis, 1975). Starch degradation was evidenced by a yellowish halo around the colony. Similarly, for the determination of cellulolytic activity, a colorless halo around the colonies grown in carboxymethylcellulose medium after Lugol addition characterized a positive result. Proteolytic activity was assessed by the formation of transparent or clearer halos resulting from casein hydrolysis in skim milk-supplemented plates (Sarath; De La Motte; Wagner, 1989). Lipolytic activity was determined using the Rhodamine B test (fluorescent dye) in culture medium supplemented with olive oil, Tween 80, and Rhodamine B (Kouker & Jaeger, 1987). Enzymatic activity was determined by measuring halo diameter in millimeters, where enzymatic activity (Pz) was calculated as the ratio between colony diameter and halo diameter, with results represented as follows: (Pz) = 1.0 (no activity); $0.64 < (Pz) > 1.0$ (positive activity); $(Pz) \leq 0.64$ (strongly positive activity). Bacterial isolates were also characterized by Gram staining.

Results

Bacterial colonies with distinct morphological characteristics regarding color, shape, elevation, and margins were observed. Amylolytic activity was confirmed in three bacterial isolates, one of which was strongly positive ($Pz \leq 0.64$). Of the nine isolates

analyzed in this study, six presented cellulolytic activity, five of them considered strongly positive. Five colonies showed positive proteolytic activity, three of which were strongly positive. Regarding lipolytic activity, the results were not fully confirmatory since no halos formed around bacterial growth; however, some changes such as colony and medium coloration were observed. Gram staining revealed six Gram-positive isolates, one Gram-negative isolate, and two inconclusive results.

Conclusion

This study makes a significant contribution to the academic and scientific field by providing preliminary information on the biotechnological potential of the microbiota associated with the mangroves of Espírito Santo. Furthermore, it paves the way for more in-depth investigations into the microbial diversity of mangroves in this region, including expanded sampling, metagenomic analyses, and evaluation of other metabolic activities of industrial interest.

Keywords: Mangroves, bacteria, enzymes, biotechnological potential.

Financial Support: Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico (CNPq), Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa e Inovação do Espírito Santo (Fapes).

MECHANISMS UNDERLYING THE EFFECTS OF *EUPHORBIA UMBELLATA* ON ENDOTHELIAL DYSFUNCTION

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Introduction: *Euphorbia umbellata* (Pax) Bruyns (Euphorbiaceae) is used for its anti-inflammatory properties and has recently shown potential to protect against endothelial dysfunction, at least in part, via arginase inhibition and enhanced NOS3 expression. This study further investigated additional mechanisms contributing to its vascular effects.

Methods: Polyphenolics and flavonoids of *E. umbellata* ethyl acetate bark extract (EA) were quantified according to the Folin-Ciocalteu method and the Brazilian Pharmacopoeia (5th ed, 2010), respectively. Cytotoxicity was determined using the MTT method, cytokine production was measured using enzyme linked immunosorbent assay, and antioxidant assays were performed using colorimetric methods. Male Wistar rats (*Rattus norvegicus*, 250–280 g, 12 weeks) were randomly assigned into three groups ($n = 3-5$): EA (30 mg/kg/day), sham (saline 1 ml/day), and negative control (dimethyl sulphoxide:saline, 1:5, 1 ml/day). Animals of EA and negative control groups were submitted to a streptozotocin-induced hyperglycemia model (Ethics Committee on Animal Use UEPG, #10922/2016). After 14 days of treatment, the serum was collected for analysis. Data were expressed as mean \pm SEM; $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Results: The EA polyphenolic content was 494.18 ± 4.52 mg of gallic acid equivalent/g of extract, and flavonoid content was 5.97 ± 0.04 mg of quercetin equivalent/g extract. These results are consistent with studies showing the presence of polyphenols as quercetin and gallic acid in *E. umbellata* polar extracts. The cytotoxicity on RAW 264.7 showed that cell viability was higher than 90% when the concentration of EA treatment was from 6.25 to 100 μ g/ml. In RAW 264.7 LPS stimulated cells, EA (100 μ g/ml) slightly ($p < 0.05$) inhibited the production of cytokines IL-6 (16%) and TNF- α (17%) compared to LPS. On the other hand, EA decreased superoxide radical production (39%) and showed a higher inhibitory activity in NO assay (96%) in a similar fashion compared to positive control L-NAME (91%). Our findings demonstrated that EA significantly ($p < 0.05$) enhanced NO_x levels in serum (32.16 ± 6.42 μ M) of hyperglycemic rats similar to sham animals (34.26 ± 5.63 μ M) compared to negative control group (17.58 ± 2.62 Mm), suggesting a positive effect on NO bioavailability. We also found that EA increased by 60% ($44.09\% \pm 3.69$, $p < 0.05$) the serum scavenger potential against ABTS^{•+} compared to negative control group ($27.52\% \pm 2.80$), similarly to normoglycemic rats ($47.82\% \pm 3.76$).

Conclusion: According to previous data of our research group, EA presents an anti-arginase effect along with increased NOS3 expression, strengthening the endothelium-dependent vasorelaxant response. Regarding reactive oxygen and nitrogen species can

contribute to NOS3 uncoupling and reduce NO bioavailability, treatments with antioxidant properties may prevent vascular impairment. Taken together, the EA from *E. umbellata* bark exhibits antioxidant mechanisms that could support its use as a complementary therapy for systemic cardiovascular complications related to hyperglycemia-induced endothelial dysfunction. These properties are also associated with an immunomodulatory effect.

Keywords: cell viability; cytokines; antioxidant activity; NO bioavailability; vascular benefits

Funding: Coordination for Higher Education Staff Development (CAPES); Brazilian National Council of Scientific and Technological Development (CNPq); and FINEP-CT/Infra.

IN-SILICO EVALUATION OF SILYMARIN COMPOUNDS AS INHIBITORS OF *HELICOBACTER PYLORI*'S BABA AND SABA ADHESINS

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Introduction: *Helicobacter pylori* is a bacterium that is able to colonize the human stomach, which can lead to the development of stomach cancer, and since the bacterium already shows resistance to the main antibiotics used in its treatment, there is the need for the development of new therapies against it. In order to colonize the stomach, *H. pylori* express a number of virulence factors that allow the bacterium to survive in such environment, and two of these virulence factors are the BabA and SabA adhesins, which bind to non-sialyl and sialyl Lewis antigens respectively, allowing the bacterium to adhere to the surface of cells that express such structures. In such context, silymarin, a compound made of flavolignans extracted from *Silybum marianum* L. Gaertn. seeds have already shown anti-*H. pylori* properties in vitro essays and can represent a new way of treating the infection, but there is no clear information about the mechanism of action. Therefore, this work aimed to evaluate the possibility of the silymarin main compounds, silybinin A and B, isosilybinin A and B, silychristin, isosilychristin, taxifolin and silydianin, to act upon *H. pylori*'s BabA and SabA adhesins via molecular docking. **Methods:** The compounds (ligands) were drawn in MarvinSketch and their geometry and protonation were optimized in the Avogadro software, while the BabA (PDB: 4ZH7) and SabA (PDB: 4O5J) structures were obtained in the Protein Data Bank and optimized in the PDB2PQR platform. The binding site was obtained through the SuperStar software and docking was performed in the GOLD software, both contained within the CCDC library, using 10Å as the binding site radius and ChemPLP as scoring function and the results were analyzed in the DiscoveryStudio software. **Results:** The molecular docking for BabA resulted in fitness scores ranging from 47,57 (silydianin) to 57,75 (isosilybinin A) while the one for SabA resulted in fitness scores ranging from 50,48 (taxifolin) to 74,79 (isosilychristin), which show that all the analyzed compounds possess a favorable interaction profile with the adhesins' binding sites. Moreover, it has been identified that all the compounds are able to stablish strong hydrogen bonds and hydrophobic interactions with multiple amino acid residues of the binding site, including those that are known to mediate the adhesin activity of the virulence factors, such as CYS189, GLY191, ASN194, ASP233 and SER244 of BabA (isosilybinin A is able to interact with CYS189, GLY191 and SER244), and such as LYS152 and GLN159 of SabA (isosilychristin is able to interact with both). **Conclusion:** This study found that all the eight main silymarin compounds are able to stablish strong interactions with amino acid residues in the binding site of both BabA and SabA, which can possibly result in their blocking and thus the disruption of the ability of *H. pylori* to bind to cells that express the target Lewis antigens.

Keywords: *Helicobacter pylori*; silymarin; virulence factors; adhesins; molecular docking.

Funding: UFES and FAPES.

THE EFFICACY OF A NEW FIBRILLAR GELATIN-BASED HEMOSTATIC AGENT IN PEDIATRIC CRANIOTOMY SURGERY.

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Introduction

Pediatric neurosurgical procedures are complex due to the delicate anatomy and physiological variability of young patients. Among these, craniotomy (or trepanation) is frequently performed for ventriculoperitoneal shunts (VPS), external ventricular drainage (EVD), stereotactic biopsies, and endoscopic third ventriculostomies. Given the high risk of intraoperative bleeding and associated complications, effective hemostasis is crucial to reduce morbidity and ensure safe outcomes. Fibrillar gelatin-based hemostatic agents (HBGF) have been developed from denatured animal collagen, offering a fibrous, absorbent, and biodegradable structure that promotes platelet adhesion and clot formation. This study aimed to evaluate the efficacy, safety, and handling performance of a fibrillar gelatin-based hemostat in pediatric trepanation surgeries.

Methods

This prospective longitudinal study was conducted at the Hospital Infantil Nossa Senhora da Glória (HINSG-ES). It was approved by the Ethics Committee for Research (CEP/UFES), protocol No. 4.316.934, in accordance with Resolution 466/2012 of the Brazilian National Health Council. The sample included 150 pediatric patients (0–18 years) undergoing neurosurgical trepanation procedures using the fibrillar gelatin-based hemostat (GELITA TUFT-IT®, Gelita Medical GmbH, Germany). Data were collected through surgeon-completed performance questionnaires and patient medical records. Variables included age, sex, diagnosis, surgical type, hemostasis time, and postoperative complications. The hemostat was assessed for efficacy, fluid absorption, tissue adherence, handling, repositioning, and overall performance, rated on a five-point scale (excellent to poor). Statistical analysis employed Fisher's Exact Test using IBM SPSS v.24, with a significance level of 5%.

Results

The mean patient age was 4 ± 1 years; 53.3% were female. The majority (37.3%) were infants under one year old. Follow-up exceeded one year for 47.3% of participants. Intraoperative bleeding was classified as mild or normal in 95.4% of cases, moderate in 3.3%, and severe in 1.3%. Hemostasis was achieved within 30 seconds in 96% of surgeries. The hemostat demonstrated excellent absorption in all cases (100%) and excellent handling in 97.3%. Tissue adherence and repositioning ability were rated "excellent" in 98% and 98.7% of procedures, respectively. Efficacy in controlling intraoperative bleeding and cerebrospinal fluid leakage was considered "excellent" in 98.7% of cases. A statistically significant association was observed between excellent tissue adherence and hemostatic efficacy ($p = 0.04$). No postoperative complications related to the product, such as infection or encapsulation, were reported.

Conclusion

The fibrillar gelatin-based hemostatic agent (GELITA TUFT-IT®) proved to be a safe, effective, and easy-to-handle material for bleeding control in pediatric neurosurgical trepanations. It ensured rapid hemostasis, excellent tissue adherence, and minimal postoperative complications. The findings support its integration into pediatric neurosurgical protocols as a reliable hemostatic adjunct. Future research should explore long-term tissue integration, cost-effectiveness, and comparative performance with other hemostatic materials.

Keywords: Hemostatic agents; Hemostasis; Neurosurgery; Pediatrics; Trepanation

Funding: This study was supported by the Institutional Scientific Initiation Program (PIIC/UFES 2024–2025) of the Federal University of Espírito Santo (UFES); CAPES and FAPES

OCULAR SAFETY OF SOURSOP SEED OIL AND NANOEMULSIONS ASSESSED BY HET-CAM ASSAY

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Introduction: Soursop (*Annona muricata*) seed oil is rich in bioactive compounds such as fatty acids, which contribute to skin health, and acetogenins, known for anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and wound-healing activities, supporting its cosmetic potential. Despite these properties, systematic safety data are limited, especially regarding ocular irritation. Nanoemulsification is commonly used to improve stability and bioavailability of lipophilic compounds, raising the question of whether it may alter the oil's irritation profile. Hens' Egg Test – Chorioallantoic Membrane (HET-CAM), has become a widely accepted alternative to the Draize rabbit eye test, providing reliable and ethical data without animal use. This study aimed to evaluate the ocular irritation potential of soursop seed oil (SSO) and two nanoemulsions: N1, containing 5% oil and 5% Span 80/Tween 80 mixture, and N2, containing 10% oil and 10% Span 80/Tween 80 mixture, using HET-CAM model.

Materials and methods: HET-CAM assay was performed using fertilized White Leghorn eggs (n = 3 per group). The eggs were incubated for 10 days from the day of laying, in an incubator at 37.5 °C and 62.5% relative humidity. On the tenth day, ovoscopy was performed to identify the air chamber, from which the shell was removed so that the shell membrane was exposed. After CAM exposure, 300 µL of each sample were applied for 20s and rinsed with 5 mL of 0.9% NaCl. NaOH 0.1 N was used as positive control and NaCl 0.9% was used as negative control. Irritation was assessed by monitoring hemorrhage, hyperemia and coagulation within 5 min, and the Irritation Score (IS) was calculated.

Results: SSO presented an IS of 17.40, classified as severe irritant. N1 and N2 showed IS values of 19.66 and 19.36, respectively, both also classified as severe irritants. Negative control (NaCl 0.9%) showed IS = 0.0 (non-irritant), while the positive control (NaOH 0.1 N) had an IS = 20.53 (severe irritant). Both nanoemulsions produced irritation scores close to the positive control, indicating that their effects were comparable to those of NaOH. Furthermore, no differences were observed between N1 and N2, suggesting that increasing oil and surfactant concentrations did not mitigate or exacerbate the irritant potential. Acetogenins are known to exhibit interesting biological effects but are also linked to ocular and mucosal irritation, which may explain the severe effects observed for SSO. In contrast, the surfactants (Span 80/Tween 80) are recognized as safe for cosmetic use and are not associated with ocular irritation at the tested concentrations. These findings suggest that the irritation observed is primarily attributable to the oil itself rather than to the emulsifiers.

Conclusion: These findings demonstrate that SSO and its nanoemulsions present a severe ocular irritation potential, which precludes their use in eye-area formulations. Applications should therefore be restricted to non-ocular cosmetics, such as skin and hair products. Future studies should explore reformulation strategies to improve safety profiles. Importantly, this study reinforces the value of HET-CAM as a sensitive and validated replacement for the Draize test, supporting ethical and reliable approaches for early-stage ocular safety assessment.

Keywords: Chorioallantoic membrane; Ocular toxicity; Cosmetic toxicology, Acetogenins.

Funding: Espírito Santo Research and Innovation Foundation (FAPES, Brazil).

SELECTIVE ANTITUMORAL ACTIVITY OF AVOCADO SEED COMPOUNDS AGAINST GASTRIC ADENOCARCINOMA

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Introduction: *Persea americana* (Laureaceae) seed is an industrial byproduct rich in secondary metabolites such as acetogenins. The antitumoral activity of acetogenins containing tetrahydrofuran rings is well established in literature, however there are few studies exploring the effect of aliphatic ones, such as the ones found in avocado seed. In this context, this study aimed to screen the antitumoral properties of avocado seed extract rich in acetogenins and to evaluate *in silico* interaction between the compounds and claudin-18 (CLDN18.2), which is a highly selective marker protein that is expressed in differentiated gastric mucosal membrane epithelial cells. **Methods:** Avocado seeds were collected, grounded and dried. After 7 days of maceration in ethanol 70%, the product was filtered and solvents eliminated by rotary evaporation and lyophilization to obtain the crude extract. Chemical characterization was performed by high resolution mass spectrometry. Antitumor assays were performed according to MTT method and expressed by IC₅₀ values (means \pm SD) of three triplicates at following tumor cell lines: AGS (gastric adenocarcinoma), HCT-116 (colon cancer), HepG2 (liver cancer) A549 (lung cancer), MCF7 (breast cancer) and 4T1 (breast cancer with 6-thioguanidin resistance). Fibroblast cells (L929) were used to determine safety and to calculate selectivity index. Cisplatin was included as standard antineoplastic. Molecular docking on AutoDock Vina was used to analyze ligands interactions with CLDN18.2. **Results:** Crude extract is mainly composed of long chain unsaturated fatty acids, polyhydroxylated compounds and acetogenins. Mass spectrometry signals were attributed to compounds such as oleic acid, chlorogenic acid, perseitol, persenone, avocadene, avocadyne and its esters. The avocado seed extract inhibit the growth of all tested cells at concentrations lower than 400 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, with IC₅₀ and IS values equals to $12.16 \pm 0,6221 \mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ (IS = 9.12) for AGS; 188.60 ± 23.6230 (IS = 0.59) for HepG2; 216.03 ± 6.4609 (IS = 0.51) for MCF7; 221.10 ± 6.6640 (IS = 0.50) for HCT 116; 240.90 ± 31.0194 (IS = 0.46) for A549; 351.60 ± 7.8885 (IS = 0.32) for 4T1; and 110.93 ± 7.1728 (IS = 0.51) for L929. Avocado seed had better results in AGS, where it achieved IC₅₀ statistically equal to cisplatin ($11.39 \pm 0,3305 \mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$), but with higher selectivity index. Considering these results, molecular docking was performed in CLDN18.2. Target active site is mostly composed of hydrophobic residues, as Ala140, Val144, Phe147, Trp148, Phe171, Leu175, Phe176. Hence, avocado acetogenins were able to establish many hydrophobic interactions, with binding energies of -5.5, -5.1 and -5.6 kcal/mol for persenone A, B and C respectively. Other lipophilic compounds achieved similar results, while polar ones had close binding energies through other intermolecular interactions. The polyhydroxylated substances established fewer but stronger interactions, mostly hydrogen bonds between ligand hydroxyl groups and macromolecule polar residues (including Glu47 and Ser150). **Conclusion:** Therefore, avocado seed compounds, including aliphatic acetogenins, did not show broad spectrum

cytotoxic effect, however, they demonstrated specific anti-gastric cancer activity *in vitro*. Further studies are required to elucidate its mechanism of action and to determine structure activity relationship for active molecules.

Keywords: Natural Product; Avocado seed; Gastric Adenocarcinoma.

Funding: Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa no Espírito Santo

EVALUATION OF THE ACTIVITY OF *CALOPHYLLUM BRASILIENSE* AGAINST *HELICOBACTER PYLORI* AND UREASE INHIBITION

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Introduction: *Helicobacter pylori* is a bacterium known for its ability to colonize the human stomach, causing diseases such as gastritis and gastric ulcers, and is the main factor associated with the development of gastric cancer. The use of medicinal plants has been highlighted in the search for new compounds with pharmacological potential. In this context, previous studies indicate that the bark of *Calophyllum brasiliense* Camb., popularly known as "guanandi", has anti-*H. pylori* and antiulcer potential. However, there are no studies in the literature linking its leaves and fruits to combating this microorganism. Therefore, given the need to seek therapeutic alternatives for the eradication of this bacterium, the present study sought to evaluate the anti-*H. pylori* and urease inhibitory activities of extracts and fractions from the leaves and fruits of this plant species. **Material and methods:** The crude extracts of the leaves and fruits of *C. brasiliense* were characterized by Fourier transform ion cyclotron resonance mass spectrometry. In parallel, the anti-*H. pylori* activity was evaluated by determining the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) through broth microdilution and the activity on the urease enzyme by spectrophotometric assays. **Results:** Mass spectrometry identified several compounds in the leaves and fruits, including coumarins, chromanones, and xanthenes. The dichloromethane fractions from both the leaves and fruits demonstrated the greatest ability to inhibit the growth of *H. pylori* bacteria. Regarding urease inhibition, the dichloromethane and ethyl acetate fractions from the fruits demonstrated the greatest potential activity, while the leaf fractions showed no significant activity, demonstrating that the action on this enzyme is likely associated with compounds identified only in the fruits. **Conclusion:** *C. brasiliense* extracts, especially the dichloromethane fractions from the leaves and the dichloromethane and ethyl acetate fractions from the fruits, can be considered promising study targets for the prevention and treatment of *H. pylori* infection and related diseases.

Palavras-chave: *Calophyllum brasiliense*; *Helicobacter pylori*; Urease.

Apoio financeiro: FAPES, CNPq and CAPES

IN SILICO EVALUATION OF FLAVONOIDS FOR INHIBITION OF THE ENZYME DAH7PS OF HELICOBACTER PYLORI

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Introduction: *Helicobacter pylori* is a microaerophilic, Gram-negative bacterium that colonizes the human gastric mucosa and constitutes the main risk factor for gastric adenocarcinoma. Increasing bacterial resistance and adverse effects of conventional treatment encourage the search for therapeutic alternatives, including natural compounds with antimicrobial potential, and also new targets. The 3-deoxy-D-arabino-heptulosonate 7-phosphate synthase (DAH7PS) is in the shikimate pathway producing aromatic compounds in *H. pylori* and it can be considered a potential target for new drugs. Therefore, this study aimed to perform an *in silico* search of flavonoids reported to have anti-*H. pylori* activity and evaluate their capacity to interact with the target enzyme of bacterial metabolism, DAH7PS. **Materials and methods:** The flavonoids were selected from a literature review using PubMed and Scielo, and an in-house database was constructed. The 2D structures of the compounds were drawn using the MarvinSketch software. The physicochemical and pharmacokinetic properties were predicted by SwissADME to select those with the best properties. The ligands were initially obtained in SDF format from the PubChem database, then subjected to geometric optimization in WebMO using the MOPAC package and converted to .mol2 format in Discovery Studio software, ensuring suitability for molecular docking. The three-dimensional structure of DAH7PS was obtained through homology modeling and validated with a Ramachandran plot using the SwissModel server. Subsequently, molecular docking assays were performed in SwissDock/AutoDock Vina, with pose analysis in Discovery Studio. **Results:** 40 flavonoids with anti-*H. pylori* activity already described were identified, of which 10 were selected for presenting the best pharmacokinetic and physicochemical properties (good solubility with logS ranging from -4.97 to -2.66, adequate partition coefficient ranging from 0.5 to 3.11, high gastrointestinal absorption, and compliance with Lipinski's rule). Molecular docking indicated relevant interactions with the target enzyme, highlighting isowighteone, which presented the lowest binding energy (-8.399 kcal/mol), suggesting greater affinity for the active site. Other compounds, such as genistein (-7.955 kcal/mol), lutein (-7.871 kcal/mol), and luteolin (-7.836 kcal/mol), also exhibited favorable values, close to those of the best candidate, reinforcing their inhibitory potential. The analysis of isowighteone interactions revealed the formation of hydrogen bonds with Glu, Arg, Thr, and Ile residues, as well as π -alkyl interactions with Pro and Ile, and π -cation interactions with Lys. **Conclusion:** In summary, the results obtained demonstrate that different flavonoids have the potential to interact with the DAH7PS enzyme, essential for *H. pylori* metabolism, with favorable binding energies and consistent pharmacokinetic properties. These findings reinforce the relevance of flavonoids as promising candidates in the search for new inhibitors, contributing to alternative therapeutic strategies for combating this bacterium.

Keywords: *Helicobacter pylori*. flavonoids. *in silico* evaluation.

Acknowledgment: FAPES (Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa e Inovação do Espírito Santo) and UFES (Universidade Federal do Espírito Santo).

EVALUATION OF THE ANTIBACTERIAL EFFECT OF THE CHALCONE MOLECULE INCORPORATED INTO MESOPOROUS SILICA NANOPARTICLES

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Introduction

The rise in bacterial resistance and the side effects of specific antibiotics is highlighting the need for new, more effective and specific antibacterial agents. In this scenario, nanocarriers containing bioactive molecules are emerging to increase drug availability, control drug release, reduce adverse effects, and improve treatment adherence. Among several nanocarriers, mesoporous silica nanoparticles of the MCM-41 type are promising due to their high surface area, large pore volume, biocompatibility, and FDA-recognized safety. The study sought to synthesize these nanoparticles, incorporate a bioactive molecule into them, achieve controlled release, and evaluate their behavior *in silico* and *in vitro*. A type of chalcone, CH58, was chosen as the bioactive molecule. Chalcones are an important class of natural products (flavonoids) that can be easily synthesized and structurally modified.

Methods

For the synthesis, CTAB, a cationic surfactant, was dissolved in water in a basic medium. Subsequently, the silicate source, tetraethylorthosilicate, was added, and the mixture remained at a controlled temperature for two hours. The mixture was then filtered, oven-dried, and calcined in a muffle furnace at 500°C. This process resulted in the production of MCM-41 mesoporous silica nanoparticles. Characterization was performed using nitrogen adsorption to calculate the surface area (SBET), pore diameter (Dp), and volume (Vp), in addition to thermal analysis (thermogravimetry). For incorporation, MCM-41 was in contact with a 2000 µg/mL CH58 solution in solvent for 48 hours, and release was quantified using a UV-VIS spectrophotometer, comparing it with the previously prepared calibration curve. As an *in silico* test, docking was performed to evaluate the interaction of CH58 with the elastin ClfA of *Staphylococcus aureus*. Finally, to confirm the results of the *in silico* test, an antibiogram was performed on the pure and released samples applied to diffusion discs.

Results

The characterization of MCM-41 showed values consistent with mesoporous nanomaterials (SBET of 997 m²/g, Dp of 3.1 nm, and Vp of 0.187 cc³/g). Thermal analysis confirmed typical losses: 6% water in the 25-150°C range, 4% silanol groups in the 150-700°C range, and a residual mass of 90% at higher temperatures. CH58 exhibited absorption at 314 nm, with the equation of the generated line being $y=0.0808x+0.0229$ and $r^2=0.9996$, demonstrating a good correlation. In the incorporation assay, 19.2% of the drug was incorporated into MCM-41, of which 8% was released, corresponding to a

concentration of 1.6 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Docking demonstrated that the interaction energy of elastin with CH58 was -8.4 kcal/mol, indicating affinity for the site of action (ClfA). The antibiogram of the released sample showed a 1 cm halo, while for the pure sample at a concentration of 1500 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, the halo was 1.5 cm, while for the solvent it was 0.8 cm and the positive control, 3.0 cm.

Conclusion

Therefore, it was possible to synthesize silica nanoparticles, incorporate the drug, and obtain controlled release. The inhibition zone of the pure and released samples against *S. aureus* was observed, suggesting that this nanosystem has great potential as an antibacterial drug candidate.

Keywords: Silica Nanoparticle; Chalcone; Antibacterial; Docking; ClfA.

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EVALUATION OF TWO NAPHTHOPYRANONES ISOLATED FROM *PAEPALANTHUS BROMELIOIDES* AS CHEMOPREVENTIVE AND THYMIDYLATE SYNTHASE INHIBITORS

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Introduction: Cancer is a global health concern due to its growing number of cases. In Brazil, is expected around 700.000 new cases between 2023 and 2025, being breast prostate, colorectal, lung, stomach and cervix cancer the most prevalent. Due to the low selectivity of anticancer drugs, the search for novel molecules is necessary and the natural products can be a source for suitable scaffolds to be explored. In this way, the objective of this study was to isolate two naphthopyranones, paepalantine (**1**) and 5-methoxy-3,4-dehydroxanthomegnin (**2**), from *Paepalanthus bromelioides* S. (Eriocaulaceae) and evaluate their cytotoxic activity. **Methods:** The crude extract was prepared through maceration of the floral heads in MeOH. Column chromatography (CH₂Cl₂ to obtain **1** and CH₂Cl₂/Ethyl Acetate 1:1 to obtain **2**) was used and the substances were characterized by ¹H NMR and mass spectrometry. The cytotoxicity and selectivity index (SI) was assessed for the colorectal (HCT-116) and gastric adenocarcinoma (AGS), which are cancerous cell lines and the non-cancerous cell line of fibroblast (L-929) by the MTT method. Results were expressed as mean of cytotoxic concentration (CC₅₀) ± standard deviation. Molecular docking was performed in GOLD, using GoldScore as main function and ChemScore for rescore, with thymidylate synthase (PDB: 6QXH). The docking was validated by redocking the crystallized ligand. **Results:** The cytotoxic concentration (CC₅₀) obtained for HCT-116 and AGS cells were, respectively 61.75 ± 3.92 μM and 137.55 ± 20.61 μM for **1** and 206.96 ± 4.95 μM and 144.77 ± 0.17 μM for **2**. Since the CC₅₀ **1** was near superior as the control (5-FU: 37.00 ± 18.22 μM) molecular docking in TS was carried out. TS is responsible for the biosynthesis of thymidine, an essential nucleotide for DNA, by the conversion of uridine monophosphate (dUMP) to thymidylate (dTMP). The docking results were slightly better for **2** (Goldscore: 55.04) than **1** (GoldScore: 52.37), which were close to fluorodeoxyuridylate (FdUMP, GoldScore: 61.24), the metabolite of 5-FU that is responsible for TS inhibition. **1** and **2** presented a CC₅₀ of 153.68 ± 13.15 μM and 287.62 ± 12.06 μM, respectively. Thus, **2** had a better SI for AGS (1.99) than **1** (SI: 1.12), but for HCT-116 **1** was much more selective (SI: 4.9) than **1** (SI:1.53). **Conclusion:** Despite the molecular docking showing slightly superior results for **2** and better *in vitro* results for **1**, the structural motifs of the scaffold of both molecules can be further explored, to achieve better CC₅₀ and selectivity. Synthetic derivatives from juglone or 1,4-naphthoquinone may contribute to a deeper understanding of the interactions with TS and even other important cancer targets. The

development of mucoadhesive formulations can be an alternative to improve selectivity as well.

Keywords: *in vitro*, *in silico*, naphthopyranones, colorectal cancer, gastric cancer

Funding: This study was funded by the Foundation of Support to Research and Innovation of Espírito Santo (FAPES), PROCAP DOUTORADO 2024 n° 14/2023 – grant number 2024-H3X2T.

CHEMICAL PROFILE EVALUATION AND ANTITUMORAL ACTIVITY OF *TAMARINDUS INDICA* L. SEEDS ON THE MOST INCIDENT CANCERS

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Introduction: Cancer is a current social, economic, and public health problem, considered one of the main causes of premature death worldwide. In Brazil, is estimated 704,000 new cases are expected between 2023 and 2025, except for non-melanoma skin cancer, the most common types of cancer account for about 70% of cases, including female breast and prostate cancer, colorectal, lung, stomach, and cervix. In this scenario, the search for new therapeutic alternatives or complementing current ones is crucial, considering the resistance to treatments and the toxicity of existing medications. The use of medicinal plants is used method to explore pharmacological properties and is a valuable shortcut for the development of new drugs. Aiming antitumor potential, it is important to search for plants known for their antioxidant and anti-inflammatory potential, such as *Tamarindus indica* L. (Fabaceae). Seeking to expand the knowledge about this plant species, added to the need to propose new therapeutic alternatives, the present work aimed to evaluate the chemical profile of *T. indica* seeds and the cytotoxic activity against the most incident cancer cell lines. **Materials and methods:** The crude extract (CE) was obtained from the maceration of the pulverized seeds in methanol, and the CE fractionation was performed in a SPE-C18 cartridge (Welchrom®) with 25% methanol (Fr25%). The chemical profile was evaluated by Liquid Chromatography combined with Mass Spectrometry (LC-MS). The cytotoxic activity was assessed using the MTT method in tumor cell lines 4T1 (breast carcinoma), HCT-116 (colorectal carcinoma), A549 (lung carcinoma), AGS (gastric adenocarcinoma) and non-tumor fibroblast L-929, for analysis of the Selectivity Index (SI). Molecular docking analysis was directed on thymidylate synthase (TS), target enzyme for colorectal carcinoma treatment with 5-fluorouracil (5-FU), and matrix metalloproteinase 9 (MMP-9), an enzyme overexpressed in gastric and colorectal cancer. **Results:** LC-MS analysis suggested the presence of 2,2'(tetradecylamino)diethanol (2,2TD), trans-cinnamic acid (tCA), epiandrosterone (EPI), 1-(2-hydroxyethyl)-2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidinehydroxide (HTH) and 1,3-dicyclohexylurea (DCU), which were used for docking analysis, predicting a score of 62.0, 43.3, 41.8, 40.4 and 39.7 respectively, compared to 5-FU, with a score of 61.3 for TS inhibition. For MMP-9, DCU scored 48.0, tCA 47.7, 2,2TD 46.5, HTH 41.8, and EPI 40.6, compared with 60.4 for marimastat (standard substance). The mean cytotoxic indices (CI₅₀) obtained for HCT116, A549 and AGS cells with the CE were 242.75µg/mL, 208.95µg/mL and 79.37µg/mL, while for the Fr25%, 199.55µg/mL, 266.70µg/mL and 105.6µg/mL, respectively, also indicating a selective cytotoxic effect for AGS, with SI of 10.12 and 7.62 for EC and Fr25%. The CI₅₀ of 4T1 was higher than the concentrations assessed (800µg/mL). tCA exhibited goods scores for inhibition of both enzymes, and it has been described in the

literature that some cinnamic acid derivatives have affinity for the MMP-9 active site and can block the enzyme's catalytic site. While 2,2TD showed the best score for TS inhibition, no association was found in the literature for this activity, which may be due to its long aliphatic chain. **Conclusion:** Therefore, the substances noted in the seeds of *T. indica* demonstrated cytotoxic activity, possibly presenting a synergistic effect between them.

Keywords: *Tamarindus indica*; Ethnopharmacology; Seeds; Cytotoxic. MTT.

Financial support: Foundation of Support to Research and Innovation of Espírito Santo (FAPES).

EVALUATION OF THE HEPATOPROTECTIVE EFFECT OF *PERESKIA ACULEATA* MILLER IN AN EXPERIMENTAL MODEL OF ACETAMINOPHEN-INDUCED TOXICITY

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Introduction

Drug-induced hepatotoxicity is a major public health concern, with acetaminophen (paracetamol) being the leading cause of acute liver failure in Western countries. At therapeutic doses, paracetamol is considered safe; however, overdose leads to severe liver injury due to oxidative stress, mitochondrial dysfunction, and necrosis. Therefore, the search for natural hepatoprotective alternatives is of great relevance. *Pereskia aculeata* Miller (ora-pro-nóbis), a Brazilian plant rich in flavonoids and phenolic compounds, has shown antioxidant properties, suggesting potential hepatoprotective activity.

Methods

Firstly, the *in vitro* antioxidant activity of OPN extract was assessed using the ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP) assay. For the *in vivo* analysis, male Swiss mice (n=60) were randomized into four groups: control (vehicle), acetaminophen (300 mg/kg), OPN 300 (300 mg/kg of OPN extract + acetaminophen), and OPN 1000 (1000 mg/kg of OPN extract + acetaminophen). Treatments were administered orally for five days, followed by a single dose of acetaminophen. Blood and liver samples were collected for biochemical assays (ALT, AST), histopathological evaluation, oxidative stress biomarkers (ROS, TBARS, AOPP), and DNA damage (comet assay). Data were analyzed using one-way ANOVA followed by *Tukey's post hoc* test, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Initially, it was observed that 1 mg/mL of OPN extract exhibited ferric reducing capacity equivalent to 19 µg/mL of ferrous sulfate (19.12 ± 0.84). In the *in vivo* experiments, paracetamol administration significantly increased ALT and AST levels compared with the CON group. Pretreatment with OPN at 1000 mg/kg reduced both enzymes, indicating attenuation of hepatocellular injury. Furthermore, the group treated with OPN 1000 mg/kg showed a smaller necrotic area in liver tissue, indicating a hepatoprotective effect. Regarding antioxidant activity, the OPN 1000 mg/kg group exhibited significantly lower ROS production levels (17.254 ± 913 a.u.) compared to the APAP group ($81.863 \pm 1,640$ a.u.). APAP exposure elevated AOPP (CON: 0.78 ± 0.07 ; APAP: 1.28 ± 0.05 µmol/mg) and TBARS (CON: 0.018 ± 0.002 ; APAP: 0.043 ± 0.001 µmol/mL), reflecting oxidative damage to proteins and lipids. These markers were significantly reduced in animals treated with OPN, particularly at the 1000 mg/kg dose, demonstrating its antioxidant and hepatoprotective effects (AOPP: 0.92 ± 0.08 µmol/mg; TBARS: 0.025 ± 0.004 µmol/mL). Moreover, pretreatment with OPN 1000 mg/kg attenuated DNA fragmentation in hepatic cells (APAP: $57.1 \pm 0.6\%$; OPN 1000: $42.7 \pm 3.4\%$).

Conclusion

The findings demonstrate that *Pereskia aculeata* Miller extract exhibits a hepatoprotective effect against paracetamol-induced hepatotoxicity, particularly at a dose of 1000 mg/kg. This protective effect is attributed to its antioxidant properties, which contribute to the attenuation of oxidative stress and cellular damage. Thus, OPN extract represents a promising natural alternative for complementary strategies in the prevention of drug-induced liver injury.

Keywords: Ora-pro-nóbis, paracetamol, hepatotoxicity, oxidative stress, antioxidants.

Funding: UVV, LFFT, PPGCF, FAPES

EVALUATION OF ENZYME PRODUCTION BY FUNGI FROM A MANGROVE IN ESPÍRITO SANTO

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Introduction: Located between the ocean and the continent, mangroves are cradles of biodiversity that harbor significant biotechnological potential. Brazil has the second largest extent of mangrove ecosystems worldwide, which stretches along the entire coastline. This ecosystem exhibits unique characteristics due to its abundance of organic matter and unusual concentrations of oxygen, carbon, salinity, among other minerals. These conditions are responsible for the development of specialized microorganisms, among them fungi, capable of producing biomolecules with antimicrobial, antitumoral, bioremediation, and biofertilizer potential, in addition to applications in diverse industrial sectors. Among these, enzymes like cellulases, which are important for agricultural, fermentation, textile, pulp, and mainly biofuel industries, and amylases, which are widely used for the production of various syrups, to assist in fermentation processes, and in the manufacture of detergents. Therefore, it is essential to investigate the molecules produced by mangrove-derived fungi, more specifically enzymes, given their promising biotechnological applications across multiple areas. **Materials and Methods:** Soil samples were collected at depths of 10 cm and 30 cm, as well as endophytic fungi from Guarapari–ES, stored under sterile conditions and transported under refrigeration. Shortly after collection, 10 g of soil were diluted in saline solution with Tween 80, shaken, incubated, and subjected to serial dilutions. The samples were plated on selective medium (DRBC) and incubated for 15 days at 28 °C. Colonies were transferred to BDA medium and purified until monospore cultures were obtained. Enzymatic assays evaluated two main activities—amylolytic and cellulolytic—using culture media prepared with the necessary substrates and revealed with iodine/potassium iodide solution, with positive activity being considered when clear halos were observed around the colonies. **Results:** To date, 46 fungi have been isolated based on their morphology. During the isolation process, diverse macroscopic characteristics were observed, such as the production of pigments, viscous or colored liquids, and yeast-like growth, demonstrating the variety of species present in the samples. However, some characteristics appeared repetitive, which may indicate the presence of the same species. Genetic identification is therefore necessary to reduce costs and time with isolations and enzymatic assays, as well as to provide more detailed information about each identified species. Among the isolates, all showed cellulolytic activity. Although different microorganisms produce cellulase, only

some fungal strains are major producers of this enzyme, making it necessary to perform quantitative assays to confirm this biotechnological potential. Regarding amylase, only 63% of the isolates showed activity, which is commonly produced by soil fungi but was present in most of the endophytic fungi isolated in this study. **Conclusion:** The results obtained in this project demonstrate the richness of mangroves and the need to preserve them, as their high biodiversity makes them a habitat for species with great biotechnological potential, such as fungi, which can increasingly be used to support the growth of industrial sectors in a sustainable way, reducing environmental impacts.

Keywords: Mangrove. Fungi. Enzymes. Biotechnological Potential. Industry

Financial Support: CNPq.

EVALUATION OF THE ANTIMICROBIAL AND ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY OF MELATONIN LOADED INTO MESOPOROUS SILICA NANOPARTICLES

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The growing problem of antimicrobial resistance has sparked a series of research projects aimed at addressing this public health issue. Currently, several distinct methodologies are being presented and studied, including the potential of melatonin in sepsis due to its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antibacterial effects in a multidrug resistance setting, and the effect of nanoparticles, particularly on drug delivery, stability, and permeability. Thus, this study aims to evaluate the antimicrobial potential of melatonin incorporated into mesoporous silica nanoparticles. Silica, obtained by the sol-gel method, together with the incorporation and impregnation of melatonin, form the system studied, and its release profile was evaluated in PBS buffer by UV-VIS absorbance readings. To evaluate its antibacterial, antioxidant, and cytotoxic effects on erythrocytes, disk diffusion, ABTS assay, and hemolysis test methods were used. No visible inhibition zones were observed; however, considerable antioxidant activity and low levels of cytotoxicity to red blood cells were observed. Melatonin, a stabilizing agent for hemolysis induced by nanocomposites, facilitates advances in their intravenous use. It is hoped that this study and others in this field will lead to new adjuvants and even potential clinical drugs to control the phenomenon that threatens global health: bacterial resistance.

Keywords: Melatonin. Nanoparticles. Mesoporous silica. Microorganisms. Bacterial resistance.

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INFLUENCE OF L-ARGININE ON CELL VIABILITY AND OXIDATIVE STRESS IN MCF-7 CELLS.

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Introduction: Reactive oxygen species (ROS) are increased in cancer cells, exerting effects on tumor cells that vary depending on their concentration. Therapeutic strategies for breast cancer (BC) have been widely studied because, although many treatments are effective, comorbidities often worsen the prognosis and reduce survival. The use of L-arginine (L-ARG) in dietary supplementation for cancer patients has shown positive results due to its relevance in different body systems, but its use may have direct effects on tumor cells by increasing oxidative stress in luminal A cancer cells, inducing apoptosis. Therefore, the purpose of this study was to investigate the effect of L-ARG treatment on cell viability and the antioxidant mechanism of tumor cells. **Material and Methods:** MCF-7 cells (Luminal A) were subjected to different concentrations of L-ARG (800/1600/3200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) for 48h. The AlamarBlue® assay was used to measure proliferation and evaluate cell viability. The evaluation of catalase, gp91phox subunit and CtiP expression was performed by Western Blot and the ImageJ software was used to measure the densitometry of the band of each protein. The data were analyzed in GraphPad Prism® 8.0.2 software and the one-way ANOVA test was applied. **Results:** Treatment with L-arg reduced cell viability in a dose-dependent manner; at a concentration of 3200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, there was a greater reduction in viability (0.45 ± 0.03) when compared with the NT group (0.76 ± 0.09). Furthermore, there was a significant reduction in CAT when compared with the NT group (NT: 1.22 ± 0.034 ; 800 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$: 0.83 ± 0.05 ; 1600 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$: 0.83 ± 0.06 ; 3200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$: 0.71 ± 0.05 ; $p<0.05$), an increase in gp91phox after treatment with 1600 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and 3200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of L-ARG when compared to NT and 800 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ (1600 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$: 0.90 ± 0.05 and 3200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$: 1.1 ± 0.06 NT: 1.2 ± 0.08 ; 800 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$: 0.60 ± 0.08 ; $p<0.05$), and CtiP was increased after L-ARG treatments when compared to NT (800 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$: 0.66 ± 0.05 ; 1600 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$: 0.76 ± 0.03 ; 3200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$: 0.90 ± 0.02 , respectively, vs. NT: 0.46 ± 0.03 ; $p<0.05$). **Conclusion:** These findings show that L-arg reduces cell viability by decreasing CAT and increasing CtiP and gp91phox, increasing oxidative stress and consequently leading to apoptosis. These results may indicate that L-arginine has potential as a therapeutic strategy in breast cancer to enhance treatment.

Keywords: Reactive Oxygen Species (EROS); Therapeutic Strategies; Cell Culture.

Acknowledgments: UFES, FAPES, CAPES, LABIOM, LUCCAR, LOCE.

IN VITRO EVALUATION OF THE ANTIFUNGAL MECHANISM OF THE ETHYL ACETATE FRACTION OF THE ETHANOLIC EXTRACT OF THE BARK OF *MYRACRODRUON URUNDEUVA*

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Introduction: The incidence of invasive mycoses caused by opportunistic fungi has increased significantly in recent decades. Worldwide, fungal infections are estimated to cause over 1.5 million deaths annually. Among them, cryptococcosis stands out as a cosmopolitan and potentially fatal systemic mycosis that affects approximately one million people each year, mainly in the context of the HIV epidemic. However, the development of new antifungal agents remains a major challenge, since fungi are eukaryotic organisms that share several biochemical and genetic similarities with their human hosts, which limits the identification of selective and safe therapeutic targets. In this context, plant-derived extracts have emerged as promising alternatives, offering bioactive compounds with potential to yield more effective and less toxic antifungal drugs. To evaluate, *in vitro*, the antifungal activity of the hexane, dichloromethane, ethyl acetate, *n*-butanol, and aqueous fractions of the ethanolic extract from the bark of *Myracrodruon urundeuva* (commonly known as “aroeira”) against *Cryptococcus* strains.

Methodology: The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was determined using the broth microdilution method, according to the CLSI (2008) guidelines. The MIC was defined as the lowest concentration that completely inhibited visible microbial growth. For ergosterol quantification, *Cryptococcus* strains were treated with the MIC of the tested fraction or fluconazole, and the ergosterol content was determined spectrophotometrically after extraction with potassium hydroxide and *n*-heptane. The strains used were *C. neoformans* (H99 and WM 626) and *C. gattii* (R265 and WM 179).

Results: The ethanolic extract and its fractions exhibited MIC values ranging from 6.25 to 50 µg/mL against all tested strains. The ethyl acetate fraction (FAEM) displayed the strongest antifungal activity and was selected for further mechanistic analysis. Treatment with FAEM significantly reduced ergosterol levels compared with the control group ($p < 0.05$), similarly to fluconazole.

Conclusion: Among the bark fractions of *Myracrodruon urundeuva*, FAEM demonstrated the lowest MIC values and effectively decreased fungal ergosterol levels, suggesting its potential as a prototype for developing novel antifungal agents active against *C. neoformans* and *C. gattii*.

Keywords: Cryptococcosis; Treatment; Natural products; *Myracrodruon urundeuva*; Ethyl acetate fraction.

Financial support: UNIVALE; UFJF/GV

NEW TARGETS FOR METABOLIC ENGINEERING: HOW THE MAPK PATHWAY MODULATES BIOACTIVE METABOLITES IN *TRICHODERMA REESEI*

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The filamentous fungus *Trichoderma reesei* is of great importance in the industrial, agricultural, and biotechnological fields due to its high capacity to produce secondary metabolites (SM) with diverse properties, such as antitumor, antibiotic, antiviral, antifungal, and antiparasitic activities. Given the growing antibiotic resistance worldwide, the search for new bioactive molecules is intensifying, and *T. reesei* is a prominent player in the field of secondary metabolism. It is one of the most significant organisms in the agrobiotechnology industry and the most important producer of cellulases for second-generation biofuels. In filamentous fungi, SM synthesis is controlled by complex regulatory networks, including transcription factors and intracellular signaling pathways. Despite its ability to biosynthesize a wide variety of SM classes, a complete understanding of the genes, transcription factors, and regulatory pathways involved in controlling SM biosynthesis in this fungus remains largely unexplored. Interestingly, the MAPK pathway influences SM production in *Trichoderma*. Therefore, this study focuses on understanding how the MAPK pathway regulates the expression of gene clusters involved in SM biosynthesis in *T. reesei* in response to the presence of cellulose. To this end, the knockout strains $\Delta tmk1$, $\Delta tmk2$, and $\Delta tmk3$, and the parental strain QM6a, were grown on cellulose, and relative gene expression was analyzed using RT-qPCR. Our results showed that MAPK signaling individually and specifically influences the expression of genes and transcription factors associated with SM biosynthesis in *T. reesei*, with positive or negative effects depending on the gene or transcription factor analyzed. Additionally, *in silico* analyses to predict the phosphorylation site revealed that, although the MAPK pathway regulates gene expression within SM gene clusters, regulation can occur post-translationally through phosphorylation, primarily by intermediate protein kinases other than MAPKs. These kinases can be directly regulated by the MAPK pathway and thus directly modulate secondary metabolism in this fungus. Our results pave the way for future research, which will involve metabolomic profiling of fungal culture supernatants to quantify the production of these SMs and provide a more comprehensive understanding of how the MAPK signaling pathway regulates SM biosynthesis in *T. reesei*, beyond the transcriptional domain. Furthermore, these findings highlight their potential as a target for future genetic and metabolic engineering strategies aimed at increasing the production of these high-value biotechnological molecules through SM-superproducing strains.

Keywords: *Trichoderma reesei*, MAPK, Secondary metabolites, Gene expression, RT-qPCR.

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THEMATIC AXIS VII

Integrative Therapeutics: Advances in
Non-Conventional Approaches to Health

DIGITAL PATHOLOGY APPLIED TO HEAD AND NECK CANCER: AN EXPERIENCE OF THE HEADSPACE STUDY

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Introduction: Head and neck cancer (HNC) is the seventh most common cancer worldwide and one of the most aggressive and malignant types of cancer. Approximately 870,000 new cases and more than 440.000 deaths are reported every year, and squamous cell carcinomas (SCC) are the most common histological type in the oral cavity, oropharynx, larynx and nasopharynx. Moreover, the majority of cases are diagnosed at an advanced stage, which can compromise treatment efficacy. In this context, digital pathology is a promising tool to optimize histopathological analyses and improve cancer diagnosis. This method allows histopathological slides to be scanned, producing high-quality images that can be shared among pathologists to discuss different cases over long distances. Therefore, this project aimed to scan histopathological slides from patients with head and neck cancer recruited in the “translational study of head and neck cancer in south America and Europe”- “HEADSpAcE”, to obtain information to improve the diagnosis of these tumors.

Material and methods: Tissue images on the slides were captured using the Whole Slide Imaging (WSI) technique through the 3DHISTECH Panoramic DESK II scanner at the digital pathology platform in Vitória, Espírito Santo. This equipment has the capacity to scan the entire histological section on the slides, producing high-quality images at 116x magnification and applying during the process. The scanner also provides maximum resolution along the X, Y, and Z axes, maintaining image focus across the entire slides and avoiding out-of-focus and blurry areas. Thereafter, through the Panoramic Scanner Software, the images were processed, and all the digitized image segments were merged into a single file containing the complete tissue slides.

Results: As a result, a total of 654 slides were scanned between 2023 and 2024 through digital pathology. All digitized images were sent to the HEADSpAcE Datacenter at the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) and shared with pathologists from different centers to contribute to studies on head and neck cancer and support the development of strategies for early diagnosis. This approach also enables collaboration with other research institutes, allowing rapid analyses of histopathological slides and improving diagnostic confidence.

Conclusion: In conclusion, the application of digital pathology at HEADSpAcE proved to be a rapid, efficient, and low-cost method for multicenter studies involving histopathological analyses. Moreover, digital pathology and the Whole Slide Imaging technique offer a new approach for studying cancer and enable effective diagnosis. It also

allows remote case discussions among professionals worldwide, optimizing analyses and enhancing knowledge about oncology, particularly head and neck cancer, which is a highly aggressive group of malignancies.

Keywords: Digital; Pathology; Cancer; Scanner.

Funding support: Espírito Santo Research Support Foundation (FAPES) and National Council for Scientific and Technological Development (CNPq).

CAN REIKI IMPROVE THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF PEOPLE LIVING WITH HIV? A SCIENTIFIC ANALYSIS

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Introduction: Reiki is a complementary therapy that aims to balance vital energy through the laying on of hands, promoting benefits such as pain relief, stress reduction, and improved overall well-being. Although its effectiveness remains a topic of debate within the scientific community, studies suggest positive effects in several health conditions, particularly among patients with chronic illnesses. People living with HIV (PLHIV) often face significant psychological challenges, including anxiety, depression, social stigma, and chronic stress, which can negatively impact their quality of life (QoL) and adherence to treatment. This study aims to review existing literature on the effects and impacts of Reiki on the QoL of PLHIV, considering physical, emotional, and psychological aspects. **Methods:** A narrative literature review was conducted, focusing on articles published between 2010 and 2025 in the PubMed and SciELO databases. The descriptors used were "Reiki", "HIV", and "quality of life". Studies were included if they assessed the application of Reiki in individuals living with HIV and its effects on QoL, as well as symptoms of anxiety and depression. **Result:** The search resulted in a limited number of studies directly addressing Reiki and HIV. However, research on Reiki in other chronic health conditions has reported benefits such as reduced anxiety, improved mood, and enhanced immune function. Evidence suggests that energy-based therapies like Reiki can help reduce stress levels, promote relaxation, and support emotional balance in individuals facing chronic illness. Furthermore, interventions combining Reiki with complementary approaches such as music therapy have shown significant reductions in stress, anxiety, and pain, contributing to greater overall well-being when compared to the use of isolated interventions. These findings reinforce the potential of Reiki as an effective complementary strategy in the care of PLHIV. Although studies specifically focused on Reiki and HIV remain scarce, the benefits observed in similar chronic conditions highlight a therapeutic potential that deserves further investigation. It is essential to emphasize that Reiki should be regarded as a complementary, not substitutive, practice to conventional medical treatment. **Conclusion:** Despite evidence supporting the benefits of Reiki in reducing stress, anxiety, and depression, more robust clinical studies are needed to evaluate its specific effectiveness in PLHIV. Future research should employ rigorous methodologies to confirm these effects and contribute to the development of integrative care strategies for this population, promoting emotional and physical well-being in conjunction with conventional treatment.

Keywords: Reiki; HIV; Quality of life; Complementary therapy; Integrative health

NEUROPROTECTIVE POTENTIAL OF KEFIR IN AN EXPERIMENTAL MODEL OF EPILEPSY: COMPARATIVE EVIDENCE WITH CANABIDIOL

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Introduction: Epilepsy is a prevalent neurological disorder characterized by abnormal neuronal discharges that impair cognitive, psychological, and social functions. Although antiepileptic drugs (AEDs) remain the standard therapy, a substantial proportion of patients are refractory to treatment, highlighting the need for integrative and non-conventional therapeutic approaches. Recent evidence points to the gut–brain axis as a key modulator of seizure susceptibility, opening avenues for microbiota-targeted interventions. Kefir, a probiotic with well-established microbiota-modulating, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory properties, emerges as a promising neuroprotective candidate. Similarly, cannabidiol (CBD), a non-psychoactive phytocannabinoid, has been widely investigated for its anticonvulsant and neuroprotective potential. This study assessed the effects of kefir, alone or combined with levetiracetam (LEV), in comparison with CBD, on seizure activity and brain injury in mice subjected to pentylenetetrazole (PTZ)-induced seizures. **Methods:** Sixty male C57BL/6 mice (25–35 g) were randomly allocated into five groups (n=10): PTZ (0.9% saline, p.o.), LEV (50 mg/kg, p.o.), KEF (300 μ L/kg, p.o.), KEF+LEV (300 μ L/kg + 50 mg/kg, p.o.), and CBD (10 mg/kg, p.o.). Treatments were administered daily for five consecutive days prior to seizure induction with PTZ (60 mg/kg, i.p.). Seizure activity was evaluated using the modified Racine scale. Following euthanasia, brains were harvested for the assessment of oxidative stress, neuronal apoptosis, protein oxidation, and lipid peroxidation. Data were analyzed by one-way ANOVA ($p < 0.05$). The study was approved by the Animal Ethics Committee of UVV (protocol no. 601-2021). **Results:** Kefir significantly reduced seizure incidence (KEF: 11.3 ± 2.0) compared with CBD (23.0 ± 3.2), demonstrating superior efficacy. LEV alone partially reduced seizure incidence (31.7 ± 2.4) and prolonged latency (85.7 ± 4.7 s) relative to PTZ (40.2 ± 5.1 ; 78.6 ± 6.3 s), indicating a modest anticonvulsant effect. Importantly, the KEF+LEV combination further enhanced seizure protection (incidence: 19.0 ± 1.2 ; latency: 118.8 ± 9.0 s), potentiating the effect of LEV. Both kefir and CBD attenuated oxidative stress and neuronal injury markers, including DCF (KEF: 456.4 ± 7.3 ; KEF+LEV: 613.5 ± 4.5 ; CBD: 556.2 ± 17.8 ; LEV: 628.9 ± 10.8 ; PTZ: 236.8 ± 40.3), AOPP (KEF: 47.9 ± 4.8 ; KEF+LEV: 32.9 ± 4.9 ; CBD: 12.94 ± 4.19 ; LEV: 62.82 ± 8.36 ; PTZ: 92.5 ± 5.8), neuronal apoptosis (KEF: 2.6 ± 0.4 ; KEF+LEV: 2.7 ± 0.2 ; CBD: 2.4 ± 0.2 ; LEV: 14.9 ± 1.1 ; PTZ: 43.8 ± 2.3), and lipid peroxidation (KEF: 0.7 ± 0.03 ; KEF+LEV: 0.4 ± 0.03 ; CBD: 0.1 ± 0.03 ; LEV: 2.8 ± 0.1 ; PTZ: 1.1 ± 0.1). Notably, while kefir alone achieved effects comparable or superior to CBD, the combination KEF+LEV potentiated the protective

impact of LEV, enhancing seizure control and further reducing oxidative stress and neuronal apoptosis relative to the anticonvulsant alone. These findings indicate a synergistic or additive effect of kefir when combined with conventional AED therapy. **Conclusion:** Kefir produced significant neuroprotective effects, both as monotherapy and in combination with the AED levetiracetam, mitigating seizure severity and neuronal damage in an experimental epilepsy model. Its effects were comparable or superior to those of CBD, supporting kefir as a promising adjuvant approach in epilepsy management, through mechanisms involving gut microbiota modulation and neuronal protection.

Keywords: Seizures; Gut–brain axis; Antiepileptic drugs; Oxidative stress.

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KEFIR AS A NUTRITIONAL INTERVENTION: EFFECTS ON BIOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS OF INSTITUTIONALIZED OLDER ADULTS

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Introduction: Aging is associated with metabolic, physiological, and nutritional changes that compromise homeostasis and increase vulnerability to chronic diseases. Among the most relevant consequences are impaired hepatic function, alterations in glucose metabolism, and micronutrient deficiencies, all of which directly affect the health and quality of life of older adults. Kefir, a fermented beverage produced by the symbiotic action of lactic acid bacteria and yeasts, has attracted increasing scientific interest due to its probiotic properties and potential beneficial effects on biochemical, metabolic, and immunological parameters. **Objective:** This study aimed to evaluate the impact of daily milk kefir supplementation on biochemical parameters in institutionalized older adults in Vila Velha, Espírito Santo, testing the hypothesis that the intervention could improve nutritional and metabolic status, with particular emphasis on glycemia, hepatic enzymes, and Vitamin B9. **Material and Methods:** This experimental, prospective, controlled, and randomized study was conducted with institutionalized older adults of both sexes, aged over 60 years. Participants were allocated into two groups: milk kefir and placebo. Supplementation was administered daily for 90 days. Fasting blood samples were collected before and after the intervention to determine serum levels of Vitamin B9, glucose, aspartate aminotransferase [AST (GOT)], and alanine aminotransferase [ALT (GPT)]. Results were expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM) and statistically analyzed using the Student's t-test, adopting $p < 0.05$ as the level of significance. The study protocol was approved by the Research Ethics Committee (CAAE 84508224.9.0000.5064). **Results:** After 90 days, older adults supplemented with kefir exhibited significantly higher serum Vitamin B9 levels compared to the placebo group (13.52 ± 6.79 vs. 8.88 ± 2.80 ng/mL; $p < 0.05$), suggesting an improvement in the nutritional status associated with this micronutrient. A reduction in fasting glucose was also observed in the kefir group (79.30 ± 8.75 mg/dL) compared to the placebo (91.00 ± 9.24 mg/dL; $p < 0.05$), indicating a beneficial effect on glycemic control. Regarding hepatic function, the kefir group showed decreased AST (21.64 ± 2.87 vs. 25.24 ± 4.27 U/L; $p < 0.05$) and ALT levels (15.60 ± 2.83 vs. 19.57 ± 4.68 U/L; $p < 0.05$), suggesting a possible hepatoprotective effect of the supplementation. **Conclusion:** Daily supplementation with milk kefir for 90 days significantly improved the biochemical profile of institutionalized older adults, as evidenced by increased Vitamin B9, reduced fasting glucose, and decreased hepatic enzyme levels (AST and ALT). These findings suggest that kefir may serve as an adjuvant nutritional strategy, with potential benefits for

metabolic and hepatic health in older populations, representing a promising intervention for this frail group.

Keywords: Aging; Clinical Nutrition; Probiotics; Nutritional Intervention; Quality of Life.

Funding: Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa e Inovação do Espírito Santo – FAPES.

KEFIR PROBIOTIC AS A MODULATOR OF INFLAMMATORY, OXIDATIVE, AND REGENERATIVE BIOMARKERS IN AN EXPERIMENTAL MODEL OF ULCERATIVE COLITIS

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Introduction: Ulcerative Colitis (UC) is a chronic, multifactorial inflammatory bowel disease characterized by inflammation of the colon and rectum, leading to symptoms such as diarrhea, abdominal pain, and rectal bleeding. Conventional treatment, primarily based on corticosteroids and immunosuppressants, frequently results in adverse effects. In this context, milk kefir, a probiotic food with well-documented antioxidant and immunomodulatory properties, emerges as a promising therapeutic adjuvant. We hypothesize that supplementation with milk kefir can attenuate inflammatory damage and promote intestinal mucosal repair in the experimental model of UC. The objective of this study was to evaluate the effects of milk kefir on dextran sulfate sodium (DSS)-induced ulcerative colitis in a murine experimental model. **Materials and Methods:** Male C57BL/6 mice, weighing an average of 20 g, were randomly distributed into three experimental groups: H₂O (Control), DSS (Colitis Model), and DSS+Kefir (treatment with 107 CFU/day). Colitis was induced by the administration of DSS in the drinking water. Kefir treatment commenced on the 5th day following DSS administration and continued until the end of the experiment. The Disease Activity Index (DAI) was monitored daily. Following euthanasia, colon samples were collected for analysis of colon length, degree of inflammation, oxidative stress, cellular regeneration, and intestinal permeability. Statistical analysis included appropriate comparisons between groups for each evaluated parameter. The study was approved by the Ethics Committee on the Use of Animals (CEUA-UVV No. 673-2023). **Results:** Treatment with milk kefir demonstrated a significant attenuation of the clinical signs of colitis (DAI). The DSS+Kefir group exhibited a preserved colon length (H₂O: 7.24±0.27 cm; DSS: 6.27±0.35 cm; DSS+Kefir: 7.00±0.35 cm), a notable reduction in inflammatory markers TNF- α : (H₂O: 1,11 ± 0,12 a.u.; DSS: 3,53 ± 0,84 a.u.; DSS+Kefir: 2,69 ± 0,35 a.u.) and CCL2 (H₂O: 0,86 ± 0,32 a.u.; DSS: 2,61 ± 1,08 a.u.; DSS+Kefir: 1,08 ± 0,62 a.u.), and decreased lipid peroxidation (H₂O₂: H₂O: 1042 ± 186,0 a.u.; DSS: 3306 ± 374,9 a.u.; DSS+Kefir: 1538 ± 76,92 a.u.) and apoptosis (H₂O: 1,28 ± 0,92%; DSS: 3,42 ± 0,68%; DSS+Kefir: 1,05 ± 0,36%) compared to the DSS group. Regarding tissue repair, kefir increased the expression of stem cell markers LGR5 (H₂O: 0,96 ± 0,13 a.u.; DSS: 0,15 ± 0,01 a.u.; DSS+Kefir: 0,34 ± 0,13 a.u.) and BMI1 (H₂O: 1,33 ± 0,27 a.u.; DSS: 1,76 ± 0,21 a.u.; DSS+Kefir: 3,37 ± 0,64 a.u.). Furthermore, the treatment enhanced intestinal barrier integrity, evidenced by increased Occludin expression (H₂O: 1,43 ± 0,46 a.u.; DSS: 0,29 ± 0,15 a.u.; DSS+Kefir: 1,03 ± 0,35 a.u.) and reduced intestinal permeability (FITC-Dextran 4-kDa: H₂O: 0,81 ± 0,23 a.u.; DSS: 1,46 ± 0,40 a.u.; DSS+Kefir: 0,97 ± 0,25 a.u.). **Conclusion:** Milk kefir demonstrated expressive enteroprotective effects in

the DSS-induced murine model of UC. The findings indicate that this probiotic acts by simultaneously reducing inflammation and oxidative stress while promoting tissue regeneration and intestinal barrier integrity. These results reinforce the potential of milk kefir as a promising nutritional therapeutic strategy for the management of ulcerative colitis.

Keywords: Probitoics; Inflammatory Bowel Disease; Mucosal Repair; Antioxidants; Permeability.

Funding: Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa e Inovação do Espírito Santo - FAPES

POMEGRANATE HYDROALCOHOLIC EXTRACT AS AN INTEGRATIVE THERAPEUTIC STRATEGY FOR CARDIOVASCULAR PROTECTION ASSOCIATED WITH HORMONAL DEFICIENCY

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Introduction: The use of integrative therapies shows promise in preventing and managing cardiovascular diseases linked to hormonal dysfunctions. The deficiency of sex hormones observed after menopause is associated with increased blood pressure, endothelial dysfunction, and lipid profile alterations, thereby heightening cardiovascular risk. In this context, alternatives such as pomegranate extract have been investigated for their protective potential. Pomegranate stands out due to its phytoestrogens and antioxidant activity, which contribute to protective effects on the cardiovascular system, suggesting its use as an adjunct to conventional therapy in women. This study aimed to evaluate whether treatment with pomegranate hydroalcoholic extract (PHE) would improve coronary reactivity and cardiovascular parameters. **Materials and Methods:** In this study, 8-week-old spontaneously hypertensive female rats (CEUA-UFES, 054/2012) were divided into Sham and ovariectomized (OVX) groups which were treated for 30 days orally by gavage with PHE (250 mg/kg) or filtered water (V). At the end of the protocol, systolic blood pressure (SBP) was measured by tail-cuff plethysmography. Following euthanasia, blood samples were collected for biochemical analyses and nitrite level determination. The heart was excised and perfused using the Langendorff method, and a bradykinin dose-response curve was performed before and after perfusion with L-NAME. Protein expression of p-eNOS (Ser1177), p-eNOS (Thr495), total eNOS, p-AKT (Ser473), total AKT, SOD-2, and catalase was analyzed by Western blotting. Additionally, the septal branch of the coronary artery was used for *in situ* analysis of reactive oxygen species (ROS) staining. Results were expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean, and group comparisons were performed using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's *post hoc* test, or two-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni's *post hoc* test. **Results:** Treatment reduced SBP (Sham PHE: 151 ± 2.5 and OVX PHE: 151 ± 2.5 mmHg), enhanced bradykinin-induced relaxation (Sham V: 13 ± 1.8 vs. Sham PHE: 19 ± 1.8 and OVX V: 8 ± 0.9 vs. OVX PHE: 16 ± 1.9 %), an effect blunted by L-NAME (Sham V: 2 ± 1.7 , Sham PHE: 1 ± 1.5 ; OVX V: 1 ± 1.7 and OVX PHE: 3 ± 2.6 %), and decreased p-eNOS (Thr495) expression in both groups (Sham V: 0.23 ± 0.01 vs. Sham PHE: 0.12 ± 0.02 and OVX V: 0.19 ± 0.03 vs. OVX PHE: 0.12 ± 0.03 A.U.). Moreover, it prevented the increase in fluorescence intensity for ROS (OVX V: 0.96 ± 0.04 vs. OVX PHE: 0.76 ± 0.03 A.U.) and the reduction in nitrite levels (OVX V: 0.212 ± 0.04 vs. OVX PHE: 0.515 ± 0.07 μ M) in the OVX group. Regarding lipid profile, a decrease in total cholesterol and LDL was observed in the Sham-PHE group (CT: 38.9 ± 2.9 and LDL: 14.0 ± 0.6 mg/dL), as well

as decreased triglycerides and LDL in the OVX-PHE (TG: 37 ± 3.1 and LDL: 18.2 ± 1.5 mg/dL). **Conclusion:** In summary, these findings demonstrate the protective effects of pomegranate on the cardiovascular system, highlighting its potential as a complementary approach to conventional therapies in women with hormonal dysfunction.

Keywords: Antioxidants, Pomegranate Extract, Phytoestrogens, Hypertension, Coronary vascular bed.

Financial support: FAPES

EFFECT OF CHRONIC KEFIR TREATMENT IN FEMALE RATS SUBMITTED TO ACUTE MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION

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Background: Acute myocardial infarction (AMI) remains a leading cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide, being closely associated with pathological cardiac remodeling and oxidative stress. Non-pharmacological strategies, including fermented foods, have gained attention for their potential cardioprotective properties.

Objective: To investigate the effects of chronic milk-derived kefir treatment in female rats subjected to experimental AMI.

Methods: Female Wistar rats were divided into three groups: Sham (S), Infarct vehicle (IV), and Infarct kefir (IK). AMI was induced by coronary artery ligation, followed by kefir treatment for 60 days. Hemodynamic parameters, infarct size, collagen deposition, oxidative stress markers, and morphometric parameters were evaluated.

Results: Infarcted animals showed a significant increase in left ventricular end-diastolic pressure (LVEDP), whereas kefir-treated rats displayed reduced values, which were not different from the Sham group. Kefir treatment reduced infarct size by 26.4% and collagen deposition by 47.7% compared with the IV group. Regarding oxidative stress, kefir significantly decreased advanced oxidation protein products (AOPP) levels without altering thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS). No significant changes were observed in morphometric parameters or organ weight-to-tibia ratios, indicating no systemic toxicity.

Conclusion: Chronic kefir treatment attenuated post-infarction remodeling and reduced protein oxidative stress (AOPP) without inducing systemic toxicity. These findings suggest that kefir may represent a promising adjuvant approach to mitigate cardiac damage after AMI.

Keywords: Remodeling; Probiotics; Fermented milk; Oxidative stress; Cardioprotection.

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KILL CURVE AS A TOOL FOR SELECTING CRISPR/CAS9-EDITED CELLS.

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Introduction: The cell death curve is a fundamental dose–response assay used to determine the optimal antibiotic concentration capable of inducing death in specific cells. This assay is particularly relevant in genetic applications because it allows enrichment and selection of cell populations of interest, such as those subjected to genetic edits using the CRISPR/Cas9 system. In the context of CRISPR/Cas9, the curve indicates the minimum concentration of a given antibiotic necessary to enable separation of genetically edited cells from non-edited ones by using antibiotic resistance markers at the time of editing. Furthermore, the method enables selection of cells that have undergone editing, improving the efficiency of isolating desired cells. . **Materials and Methods:** This study was approved by the Ethics Committee for Human Research at the Federal University of Espírito Santo (Universidade Federal do Espírito Santo), CAAE: 2,171,595. All donors provided informed consent and assent. Adipose tissue fragments (5–10 mm) were collected from four individuals undergoing orthopedic corrective surgery at Hospital Estadual Infantil Nossa Senhora da Glória (HEINSG), Vitória/ES, and Hospital Estadual Dório Silva (HDS), Serra/ES. Mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) were isolated and expanded under standard conditions prior to assays. Four kill-curve assays were performed with human mesenchymal stem cells using puromycin at concentrations of 0.01 µg/mL, 0.05 µg/mL, 0.1 µg/mL, 0.2 µg/mL, 0.5 µg/mL and 1.0 µg/mL. Each assay used 42 wells of a 96-well plate, with 500 cells per well; control wells were run in quintuplicate. Cells were cultured for 10 days with medium changes every 2–3 days, and cell viability was assessed by the MTT assay with spectrophotometric readings at 570 and 620 nm. Data are presented as mean ± standard deviation (SD). **Results:** Cell viability showed an inverse relationship with puromycin concentration. Mean viabilities for wells treated with 0.01 to 0.5 µg/mL (vs. controls) were 95.23 ± 10.30%, 74.18 ± 1.04%, 64.53 ± 3.40%, 56.95 ± 2.63% and 7.03 ± 4.92%, respectively. The highest concentration, 1.0 µg/mL, produced the lowest viability (2.63 ± 0.28%). Results were plotted as a kill curve to illustrate the dose–response relationship. **Conclusion:** In this primary culture of human mesenchymal stem cells, puromycin’s toxic concentration is near 1.0 µg/mL. The established kill curve will facilitate more efficient selection of cells during CRISPR/Cas9 editing, increasing the likelihood of isolating genetically edited cells. This assay can be adapted to other cell lines, accounting for differences in antibiotic sensitivity.

Keywords (3;5): Curva de Morte Celular, Puromicina, CRISPR/Cas9, Células-Tronco Mesenquimais e Seleção Celular.

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PHYSICAL EXERCISE ENHANCES VASODILATION VIA CYSTATHIONINE- Γ -LYASE-DEPENDENT HYDROGEN SULFIDE BIOSYNTHESIS IN OVARIECTOMIZED RATS

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Introduction: Menopause, characterized by a decline in ovarian hormone levels, is associated with an increased risk of cardiovascular diseases (CVD), especially during the postmenopausal period. However, physical exercise has proven to be an effective strategy for mitigating the adverse effects of this phase on the cardiovascular system. **Objective:** This study investigated whether physical exercise improves vasodilation by increasing the production of hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) via the enzyme cystathionine- γ -lyase (CSE) in ovariectomized rats. **Methods:** The experiment was approved by the Animal Use Ethics Committee (06/2022) and conducted using Wistar female rats (eight weeks) with 180-210g, divided into four groups (n=84): Sham+Sedentary (SS), Sham+Exercise (SE), Ovariectomy+Sedentary (OS), and Ovariectomy+Exercise (OE). Seven days after surgical procedures, the exercise groups were subjected to a treadmill running protocol (60 minutes per day, five days a week) for eight weeks. Vasodilatory responses to H₂S, superoxide anion production, and nitric oxide (NO) levels were evaluated by one-way and two-way ANOVA. **Results:** Exercise reduced body weight gain (SS: 217.1 \pm 9.03; SE: 201.7 \pm 8.90; OS: 217.2 \pm 9.96; OE: 210.0 \pm 9.80g) and visceral fat accumulation (SS: 15.26 \pm 1.14; SE: 8.38 \pm 1.14; OS: 17.41 \pm 1.83; OE: 11.06 \pm 1.65g). Uterine atrophy confirmed the effectiveness of ovariectomy (SS: 0.92 \pm 0.09; SE: 1.05 \pm 0.07; OS: 0.38 \pm 0.07; OE: 0.39 \pm 0.08g). Exercise improved vasodilatory responses to L-cysteine (SS: 45.43 \pm 5.41; SE: 74.63 \pm 4.40; OS: 31.52 \pm 4.77; OE: 53.79 \pm 6.45%) and to the H₂S donor NaHS (SS: 34.82 \pm 3.68; SE: 53.64 \pm 5.06; OS: 32.38 \pm 2.60; OE: 44.04 \pm 3.80%). These effects were reduced by NO inhibition (L-NAME) and CSE pathway blockade (PAG). Exercise also decreased superoxide anion levels (SS: 42.55 \pm 2.11; SE: 18.67 \pm 2.07; OS: 39.54 \pm 1.03; OE: 29.11 \pm 5.63 a.u.) and increased NO bioavailability (SS: 20.42 \pm 2.61; SE: 35.74 \pm 3.18; OS: 17.96 \pm 2.68; OE: 32.98 \pm 4.40 a.u.). DHE fluorescence was lower, and DAF-2 fluorescence was higher in the exercised groups. These effects were diminished when either the NO or CSE pathways were inhibited. **Conclusion:** In conclusion, physical exercise promotes beneficial effects on vascular function in ovariectomized rats by modulating H₂S biosynthesis through a CSE-dependent pathway and acting in cooperation with NO. Additionally, exercise reduces oxidative stress and enhances NO availability, contributing to the preservation of cardiovascular health in this experimental model.

Keywords: Ovariectomy, Physical Exercise, Hydrogen Sulfide, Nitric Oxide, Vasodilation

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THE EFFECT OF DIFFERENT LIGHT PHYSICAL EXERCISE PROTOCOLS ON ANXIETY AND DEPRESSION PARAMETERS AND THEIR CORRELATION WITH DOPAMINERGIC AND SEROTONINERGIC SYSTEMS IN MICE CNS

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Introduction: Depression and anxiety are among the most prevalent and debilitating mental disorders, associated with alterations in monoaminergic systems, particularly in the prefrontal cortex (PFC). Despite the availability of effective pharmacological treatments, low adherence to medications and side effects limit therapeutic efficacy, reinforcing the need for non-conventional, complementary and non-pharmacological strategies. In this context, physical exercise has been proposed as a promising therapeutic alternative for mood disorders, although its neurobiological mechanisms are not yet fully understood. **Methods:** This study investigated the effects of different light-intensity exercise protocols on behavioral and neurochemical parameters in C57BL/6J male mice, weighing approximately 24 g, focusing on the influence of exercise intensity on mental health. Twenty-eight male animals were subjected to two swimming protocols for four weeks. Protocol 1 consisted of sessions starting at 60 minutes and progressively reduced to 40 minutes, with delayed introduction of breaks. Protocol 2 involved fixed 30-minute sessions with breaks from the first week. After training, animals were tested in the Elevated Plus Maze (EPM), Forced Swim Test (FST), and Tail Suspension Test (TST). For neurochemical analysis, the PFC was dissected and quantified for dopamine (DA), serotonin (5-HT), and their metabolites (DOPAC and 5-HIAA) using HPLC. The procedures carried out in this Project comply with the standards established by the National Council for the Control of Animal Experimentation (CONCEA) and were approved by the Ethics Committee on the Use of Experimental Animals (CEUA-UFES 25/2021). **Results:** Behavioral results showed that Protocol 1 induced a depressive-like profile, especially in the TST, suggesting that longer duration and lack of early breaks may have intensified stress. In contrast, Protocol 2 did not promote significant behavioral changes, maintaining a neutral profile. Neurochemically, Protocol 1 did not alter DA, 5-HT, or their metabolites, suggesting that the depressive-like behavior may be related to stress mechanisms, such as HPA axis hyperactivation. Conversely, Protocol 2 significantly reduced DA levels in the PFC without changes in DOPAC or 5-HT, suggesting a possible physiological dopaminergic regulation without negative behavioral impact. These findings demonstrate that light-intensity exercise exerts dose- and intensity-dependent effects, influencing both neurochemical and behavioral responses. Protocol 1, more intense and deregulated, was associated with depressive-like behavior possibly mediated by stress, whereas Protocol 2 induced dopaminergic modulation without behavioral impairment, suggesting physiological adaptation. **Conclusion:** In conclusion, exercise intensity and regularity are key determinants of its effects on mental health, emphasizing the importance of controlled protocols in both experimental and clinical studies. These results highlight the complexity of the relationship between physical exercise, monoamines, and behavior, and point to the need for further behavioral

and molecular studies to better understand the mechanisms underlying the neurobiological effects of exercise.

Keywords: Swimming. Mood disorders. Prefrontal Cortex. Monoaminergic system. Mice.

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GPER ACTIVATION PROMOTES SEX-DEPENDENT ANTICONTRACTILE EFFECT IN MESENTERIC RESISTANCE ARTERIES OF HYPERTENSIVE RATS: NEW THERAPEUTIC TARGETS FOR WOMEN'S CARDIOVASCULAR HEALTH

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Introduction: The G protein-coupled estrogen receptor (GPER) has emerged as a promising target by mediating rapid vasoprotective effects of estrogen. Its selective agonist, G-1, reproduces estrogen's vascular actions without activating classical receptors, representing an innovative alternative to conventional antihypertensive treatments. Systemic hypertension is among the leading causes of cardiovascular morbidity and mortality. In women, the risk increases after menopause due to declining sex hormone levels. However, G-1 mechanisms in resistance arteries, key regulators of blood pressure, remain poorly explored. We hypothesized that GPER activation reduces contractility of resistance arteries in hypertensive rats. Thus, we investigated the anticontractile action of G-1 in mesenteric resistance arteries of spontaneously hypertensive rats (SHR). **Materials and Methods:** Mesenteric arteries from female and male SHR (10–12 weeks, n=6–17, CEUA-UFES #36/2019) were assessed through a wire myograph system. Concentration-response curves were obtained for acetylcholine (ACh, 0.1 nM–10 μ M) and norepinephrine (NOR, 10 nM–30 μ M) in the absence or presence of G-1 (1 and 10 μ M) and pharmacological inhibitors: L-NAME (300 μ M, nitric oxide synthase - NOS), 1400W (10 μ M, inducible nitric oxide synthase - iNOS), L-NPA (2 μ M, neuronal nitric oxide synthase - nNOS), indomethacin (10 μ M, cyclooxygenase - COX), catalase (1000 U/mL, H₂O₂ degradation), and Tiron (10⁻⁴ M, O₂^{•-} scavenger). NO production was evaluated by DAF-FM fluorescence, and GPER protein expression by Western blot. Results were expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean and analyzed with one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's *post hoc* test, two-way ANOVA with Sidak's *post hoc* test, or Student's t-test ($p < 0.05$). **Results:** G-1 did not alter ACh-induced relaxation in either females or males. In females, G-1 (10 μ M) reduced NOR-induced pre-contraction (Basal: 1.15 \pm 0.09 vs. G-1: 0.50 \pm 0.09 mN/mm), decreased maximal contraction (Basal: 3.11 \pm 0.01 vs. G-1: 2.44 \pm 0.09 mN/mm), and shifted the curve rightward (EC₅₀ basal: 1.52 \pm 0.08 μ M vs. G-1: 2.34 \pm 0.12 μ M), indicating reduced sensitivity. In males, no significant changes were observed. Endothelium removal abolished this effect (Basal: 1.43 \pm 0.30 vs. +G-1: 1.66 \pm 0.30 mN/mm). NOS inhibition increased contractility (3.77 \pm 0.20 mN/mm), and co-incubation with G-1 prevented it (2.86 \pm 0.20 mN/mm). Selective inhibition indicated iNOS involvement (1400W: 3.04 \pm 0.30 vs. 1400W + G-1: 2.85 \pm 0.30 mN/mm). Under combined absence of NO/prostanoids, the anticontractile effect was abolished (L-NAME + INDO: 3.06 \pm 0.20 vs. +G-1: 3.30 \pm 0.20 mN/mm). Catalase (1000 U/mL) partially reduced G-1 action (2.65 \pm 0.20 vs. 2.93 \pm 0.20 mN/mm), while Tiron (10⁻⁴ M) had no effect. Fluorescence confirmed increased NO production in females with G-1 (ACh: 21.72 \pm 2.10 vs. ACh +

G-1: 42.28 ± 3.20 A.U.). GPER protein expression did not differ between sexes. **Conclusion:** G-1 exerts a sex-dependent, endothelium-dependent anticontractile effect in mesenteric resistance arteries, mediated primarily by eNOS/iNOS-derived NO and H₂O₂ in female SHR. Despite similar GPER expression, the functional response is sex-specific, revealing GPER activation as a potential therapeutic target for hypertension management and prevention of cardiovascular complications in women.

Keywords: GPER, G-1, hypertension, integrative therapy, women's cardiovascular health

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EFFECTS OF ELECTROACUPUNCTURE IN THE COMPLEMENTARY TREATMENT OF HYPERTENSION IN POSTMENOPAUSAL WOMEN: CORRELATIONS WITH THE PREDICTIVE CARDIAC INJURY MARKER NT-PROBNP

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Introduction: Population aging has been accompanied by an increase in chronic noncommunicable diseases, particularly cardiovascular diseases (CVD), the leading cause of death among Brazilian women, especially after menopause. The decline in estrogen levels during this period triggers significant metabolic and organic changes, such as obesity, hypertension, and diabetes, amplifying risk factors for CVD. Although pharmacological treatment is considered the main therapeutic approach, its use presents limitations and is not applicable to all women. In this context, and with a focus on comprehensive health promotion, integrative and complementary health practices (IChP), especially electroacupuncture (EA), have emerged as a safe and effective alternative, with promising evidence in reducing menopausal symptoms and cardiovascular risk factors, as well as in stress control and quality of life improvement. The aim of this study was to evaluate the effects of EA on blood pressure levels and the cardiac biomarker NT-proBNP in menopausal women attending the outpatient clinic of Cassiano Antônio de Moraes University Hospital (HUCAM). Our hypothesis is that EA treatment may contribute to reducing hypertension and levels of predictive markers for cardiovascular disease, thereby decreasing CVD risk. **Methods:** This was a longitudinal interventional study with paired samples, involving 31 menopausal women. Sample size was calculated based on Cohen's effect size, using R software. The study was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the Health Sciences Center/UFES (CEP), under approval number 6.100.927, on 05/05/2023, CAAE 68609822.0.0000.5060. Statistical analyses were conducted using paired t-tests, with a significance level of 0.05 and 95% confidence interval, in GraphPad Prism. The intervention protocol consisted of eight weekly EA sessions, performed with bilateral needling at Zusanli (ST36) and Neiguan (PC6) points. **Results:** EA reduced plasma levels of the cardiac biomarker NT-proBNP, with a 28.76% decrease after eight sessions. A significant reduction was also observed in systolic blood pressure (SBP), diastolic blood pressure (DBP), and heart rate compared to pre-treatment values. **Conclusion:** The results of this study demonstrate that EA exerts beneficial effects on clinical and laboratory parameters in menopausal women, promoting a significant reduction in NT-proBNP plasma levels, as well as statistically relevant decreases in heart rate, systolic, and diastolic blood pressure. These findings support the hypothesis that EA may contribute to improving cardiovascular function and quality of life in menopausal women.

Keywords: menopause, cardiovascular diseases, acupuncture, integrative and complementary practices.

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THERAPEUTIC POTENTIAL OF GPER AGONIST IN PERIVASCULAR ADIPOSE TISSUE: IMPLICATIONS FOR THE REGULATION OF MESENTERIC RESISTANCE ARTERY CONTRACTION IN BOTH SEXES

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Introduction: 17 β -estradiol (E2) induces potentially protective effects on the cardiovascular system, thus substances that interact with estrogen receptors have been studied and used as therapeutic tools. G-1 is an agonist of the G protein-coupled estrogen receptor (GPER), and its vascular effects have been investigated, being mainly represented by vasodilation, which has been described in mesenteric resistance arteries (MRA) of normotensive, hypertensive, and gonadectomized rats. However, its effects on contractile responses have been scarcely detailed, as well as its role in the function of mesenteric perivascular adipose tissue (mPVAT). Moreover, it is possible to envision a scenario in which GPER activation sustains important effects associated with mPVAT function and arterial contraction, indicating potential therapeutic targets. Therefore, the aim of this study was to investigate the influence of mPVAT on the effects of G-1 incubation in the contractile response of MRA from male and female Wistar rats. We hypothesized that mPVAT modulates the effects of GPER activation by G-1 differently between sexes. **Methods:** Male (300–400 g) and female (in diestrus, 200–250 g) Wistar rats aged 10–12 weeks were used. Vascular reactivity was assessed in MRA ($< 300 \mu\text{m}$) using a wire myograph through concentration–response curves to norphenylephrine (10 nM–30 μM), performed before and after incubation with G-1 (10 μM) and/or N^o-nitro-L-arginine methyl ester (L-NAME, 300 μM ; Sigma, St. Louis, MO, USA) for 30 minutes. Statistical analysis was performed by two-way ANOVA followed by Sidak's *post hoc* test ($p < 0.05$), and the differences in contraction response (%) at each concentration were expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean. CEUA-UFES 026/2024. **Results:** In the absence of mPVAT, only females displayed an anticontractile effect after incubation with G-1, reducing contraction at different concentrations (47.18; 53.63; 30.63; 29.13; 32.46 \pm 7.05%; $n = 7$). Notwithstanding, the presence of mPVAT reduced this effect observed in females (24.39; 18.20 \pm 5.55%; $n = 8$) and induced an effect in males that had not been previously observed (36.30; 19.18; 23.20 \pm 6.08%; $n = 6$). Incubation with L-NAME reversed the anticontractile effect in males (9.036; -8.872; -5.426 \pm 14.24%; $n = 5$) but not in females (156.3; 149.8; 113.6 \pm 36.56%; $n = 2$). **Conclusion:** The results indicate that the participation of mPVAT in the effects of GPER activation differs between sexes, as its presence reduces the anticontractile effect in females and induces it in males, possibly via nitric oxide (NO). In this sense, it is important to investigate which mechanisms would be involved in the anticontractile effect in females and how it is reduced by the presence of mPVAT, as well as to perform further analyses to strengthen the role of NO in the effect observed in males. Thus, the results contribute to the identification of a potential therapeutic target, expanding perspectives for future analyses that include a treatment protocol with G-1.

Keywords: Anticontractile; Estrogen; G-1.

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PROTECTIVE POTENTIAL OF MILK KEFIR AGAINST 5-FLUOROURACIL-INDUCED INTESTINAL MUCOSITIS

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INTRODUCTION: Cancer is the second leading cause of mortality worldwide and is characterized by uncontrolled cell proliferation. Chemotherapy, although effective, induces intestinal mucositis, a frequent adverse effect that primarily affects the small intestine, causing abdominal pain, nausea, and diarrhea. These symptoms compromise both patient well-being and adherence to cancer treatment. In this context, complementary therapies using probiotics, such as milk kefir, have gained attention for their ability to modulate the gut microbiota, reduce oxidative stress, and mitigate chemotherapy-induced toxicity. Therefore, the objective of this study was to evaluate the therapeutic effect of milk kefir in an experimental model of intestinal mucositis induced by 5-fluorouracil (5-FU). **MATERIALS AND METHODS:** Male Balb/c mice (22 g) were divided into four experimental groups (n=6): Control, 5-FU, 5-FU + kefir, and 5-FU + kefir capsule. Mucositis was induced with 5-FU (50 mg/kg, i.p.) for three consecutive days. Probiotic treatment began five days prior to induction and continued until day 11. The disease activity index (DAI) was monitored daily. On day 12, the small and large intestines were collected for intestinal motility, oxidative stress (ROS), and apoptosis analyses. The study was approved by the Animal Use Ethics Committee (CEUA UVV: N° 644-2023). **RESULTS:** Milk kefir attenuated the clinical signs of colitis (DAI), although the effects were not consistent throughout the experiment. No significant changes were observed in intestinal motility (Control: $35.74 \pm 22.74\%$; 5-FU: $52.43 \pm 8.50\%$; 5-FU + KT: $44.04 \pm 6.75\%$; 5-FU + KC: $43.30 \pm 5.98\%$) or intestinal permeability (Control: 0.55 ± 0.25 ng/ml; 5-FU: 1.00 ± 0.39 ng/ml; 5-FU + KT: 0.81 ± 0.25 ng/ml; 5-FU + KC: 0.76 ± 0.13 ng/ml) among the experimental groups. Treatment reduced oxidative stress levels (Control: 1661 ± 246.0 a.u.; 5-FU: 2632 ± 397.2 a.u.; 5-FU + KT: 1089 ± 151.2 a.u.; 5-FU + KC: 1362 ± 271.6 a.u.) and apoptosis (Control: $2.26 \pm 0.49\%$; 5-FU: $3.217 \pm 0.1115\%$; 5-FU + KT: $1.71 \pm 0.10\%$; 5-FU + KC: $1.59 \pm 0.39\%$). Furthermore, mucositis and treatments increased plasma TNF- α levels (Control: 139.9 ± 7.14 pg/ml; 5-FU: 182.9 ± 10.38 pg/ml; 5-FU + KT: 210.5 ± 15.71 pg/ml; 5-FU + KC: 222.0 ± 27.04 pg/ml). **CONCLUSION:** Kefir supplementation demonstrated an intestinal protective effect in a chemotherapy-induced mucositis experimental model, suggesting its potential as an adjuvant intervention in the management of gastrointestinal complications associated with cancer therapy.

KEYWORDS: Probiotics; Intestinal inflammation; Oxidative stress.

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